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Innovative development pathways of therapies in Neurodegeneration: what can be learned from Oncology market

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Abstract

Oncology innovation ecosystem went through a positive evolution over the last decades thanks to a convergence of cross-functional effort forces that fostered a continuous progress of drug development paradigms.

Slow progressing and aging related neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's, are known since decades to be a source of global healthcare and social economical concerns. Yet, the level of innovation in this field has historically been scarce. The misalignment among stakeholders around disease severity plus the perception of a highly risky market that requires long development cycles with weak clinical tools and high uncertainty, have made biopharmaceutical companies very reluctant to invest in this area over the years.

The goal of this study is to investigate how the use of accelerated development pathways have contributed to fuel innovation in oncology ecosystem and how can biopharmaceutical companies playing in the neurodegeneration field best apply these learnings. The study methodology uses quantitative data from Oncology drugs approved in US, case study analysis of first approved disease modifying therapies in Alzheimer's disease, and qualitative analysis from semi-structured interviews with senior stakeholders.

Results confirmed that the adoption of accelerated approvals in oncology ecosystem was a main force in the suggested conceptual model of "catapult innovation". This work shows how the appropriate use of value-based access strategies proved to be a key strength in Oncology accelerated development pathways. Findings show the drug price increased on avg. 26% (excluding inflation contribution) once it converts from accelerated to full approval and that market responds with higher levels of capitalisation to accelerated approvals. These pull dynamics were the propulsors for competition for higher investment in early biomarkers explorations in real clinical settings that led to advances in precision medicine approaches and speed of Oncology innovation cycle.

The study concludes on the different barriers and opportunities for companies playing in the Neurodegeneration field, demonstrating the potential to shift the paradigm with smaller cycles of limited accelerated approvals and dynamic access mechanisms that can bring gains for all the different stakeholders. Companies should leverage this market pull to invest in broader disease knowledge such as new endpoints development that benefit not only one drug but the broader portfolio. Case studies analysis prove the benefits of opposing leadership tensions, suggesting translating the "*cavalier versus conservative model*" to the way companies define the role each drug plays on a broader disease portfolio strategy. Companies that will be successful in adopting this new accelerated development paradigms in neurodegeneration field are the ones with leaders that can best discern the contextual environment. They will recognise the triggers that signal when best to go for a solo asset value maximisation strategy or when to play for the bigger disease portfolio strategy. For the latter, this can mean cavaliering some assets in a "speed-over-perfection" approach for the benefit of the broader portfolio and innovation in the disease ecosystem. It requires companies to build an Innovative Enterprise with increased levels of tolerance towards uncertainty, strong inter-helix connections and sustained financial commitments.

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NOTE on the structure of this dissertation:

*Along this paper the reader will find short “**Strategic Reflections**” in a blue paragraph.*

The goal is to promote critical thinking along the plot by introducing strategic questioning on the research topic and prepare for the discussion section.

1. Introduction

1.1. Aims of this dissertation

By **leveraging fungible strategies from Oncology ecosystem**, the research question of this dissertation is to appreciate:

- **How can biopharmaceutical companies best apply accelerated pathways in the development of innovative therapies for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases?**

There are multiple dimensions to this question. By the nature of the topic, many of these aspects are intrinsically scientific, however this is not the focus of this project. Instead, emphasis will be given to understanding the business and social sciences dimensions.

These could be clustered and analysed in different domain groups, such as:

- 1) Clinical development & Regulatory policies**
- 2) Pricing & Market Access Models**
- 3) Investment and Shareholder value**
- 4) Societal perception of unmet need and value
- 5) Data sharing initiatives & public/private partnerships

This project will focus mainly on the first 3 groups, even if sporadically some of the other aspects might be referred as context or come from the interviews.

Some of the more granular dimensions this project aims to understand are:

- How have accelerated pathways been established in Oncology? How different ecosystem stakeholders perceive the same level of regulatory flexibility when translated to AD space?
- What can be learned from oncology drug development risk-sharing among different stakeholders?
- What has been the impact for oncology company shareholders over the time with the introduction of policies such as accelerated regulatory pathways? what could be expected for companies playing in neurodegeneration field if they pursue similar venues?
- What are the best fungible examples that could be leveraged from oncology to apply to neurodegeneration?
- What are the key strategic decision-making considerations for Executives leading companies with a Neurodegeneration pipeline regarding long term benefit for stakeholders and innovative portfolio?

This project aims to provide insightful views on these questions from the three groups defined above. To understand the research questions, it was used a combined research approach based on literature review, quantitative data, case studies, and qualitative analysis of interviews made to key representatives, together with collected quantitative data.

The main high-level **hypothesis** is that:

*the correct use of accelerated regulatory pathways in oncology over the past years has contributed to stimulate different investment and sponsored innovation by progressively bring better drugs to oncology patients. And with the right approach from concerned stakeholders, similar strategies could also create similar **catapult effect*** and help foster innovation in the **neurodegeneration space****.*

* “**Catapult effect**” terminology is used here as an analogy to represent the effect of providing some inducement forces to support a matter, that would by itself attract and cumulate additional broader benefits that all together would develop it exponentially forward.

** When referring in the project to the general term of “**neurodegeneration**”, the narrowed scope that is intended to be understood is the group of slow progressing and high prevalence aging patient populations, such as Alzheimer’s disease and related dementias (see section 1.4 for further clarification).

1.2. Traditional drug development outline

The research and development (R&D) of a drug is guided by the ambitions of a Target Product Profile (TPP) that defines the desirable features for the new drug. (Tyndall et al., 2017).

In resume, once a drug target is identified, different candidate molecules are filtered and optimised (drug discovery). Then the best candidate is selected to go through the drug development stages. The drug development includes pre-clinical studies with animals, formulation development, clinical trials in humans, up through final regulatory approval and market access.

Fig 01 – Self-created illustration of high-level sequential step approach in the old drug Research & Development paradigm.

The clinical stages of drug development are the most critical, and their outcomes will have great impact on the product TPP and the broader commercial success of the medicine. The phase I is often in healthy volunteers, and the assets are mainly tested for their safety, pharmacokinetics, and pharmacodynamics, in other words to assure the drug is not toxic and is penetrating where it is supposed. The phase II is a very central step within the development journey, often split in Phase IIa Proof of Concept (POC) and Phase IIb dose-ranging studies. POC studies aim to give the first hint of outcome on drug efficacy against TPP ambitions and dictate the decision for further big investment sums. Phase III studies, also referred as ‘confirmatory trials’, serve to confirm to regulatory authorities the drug efficacy in a much larger number of patients.

This dissertation will primarily focus on the aspects inherent to drug development innovation, especially with regards to clinical development strategies and related regulatory and market access pathways.

1.3. Stakeholders in the industry

The journey from selecting a laboratory idea to progressing into clinical trials and continuing the pathway until commercialisation, requires the strategic collaboration of multiple intermediates with different skillsets and interests:

- **Private Biopharmaceutical firms**, represented by their Senior Executives and Shareholders with high influence over resource allocation and strategic decision making on company's value creation. In the last years the field saw a split in the type of value creation done by smaller biotech: often closer to academia, founded by venture capital, and dedicated to early-stage drug development; and 'big-pharma' that in-licenses asset from biotech once some proof of efficacy is showed, and specialised in the later stages of development and commercialisation.
- **Governmental Regulatory Agencies**, such as the Food Drug Administration (FDA) in US or the European Medicines Agency (EMA) in EU, play a key role setting the regulatory requirements for drug approval to protect the public health. Through their policies and risk-benefit incentives, they also have high strategic influence by setting the tone on the type of innovation biopharmaceutical companies prioritise.
- **Payors** in the healthcare system can be part of the public government or private insurance organisations (e.g., Medicare or Medicaid in US), depending on the country and context. The way these organisations establish and negotiate pricing and reimbursement requirements is a major pull for value-creation in the industry. There are also the Health Technology Assessment bodies (HTA), typically in Europe, that provide evidence-based recommendations to payors on how they should pay and reimburse therapies.
- **Academia, Scientific & Industry Communities, and Health Care Professionals** are especially important to bring onboard since early stages of development, as companies want to promote open innovation with solid scientific hypothesis. Besides, it is key to have an aligned perception of value of the drug under development from Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) and prescribers, that ultimately can prepare the broader ecosystem such as the media and general population, and impact commercial success.
- **Patients Associations, Philanthropic foundations, and broader society.** The welfare of patients and society at large are heavily impacted by how biopharmaceutical industry defines and delivers value. The patient associations, such as the Alzheimer's Association, or Philanthropic foundations, such as Michael J. Fox, are taking an increasing proactive role in influencing the strategic direction and outcomes of the development, regulatory approval, and commercial access of drugs.

As it will be analysed throughout this dissertation, these different stakeholders often have different needs and expectations from the development of new therapies. The tensions around their misalignment have been especially strong in the field of neurodegeneration. This paper also highlights how stakeholders alignment around the definition of value propositions in the neurodegeneration field lags behind Oncology.

1.4. The Epidemic of neurodegenerative diseases

According to Morant et al (2019) neurodegenerative diseases can be characterized by the progressive degeneration of nerve cells resulting in functional decline of cognition and/or movement.

In simplistic terms, one could split neurodegenerative diseases in two groups:

- The first group is composed of rare diseases (affecting less than 1 in 2000 people) often with genetic cause and earlier onset age. This group includes diseases like Huntington's disease (HD), Frontotemporal Dementia (FTD) or Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS).
- The diseases in the **second group are often progressing slower but affect a much broader aging population**, and their incidence increases drastically with age. Examples are Alzheimer's Disease (AD) and Parkinson's Disease (PD).

For the scope of this dissertation, when generically referring to 'neurodegenerative diseases' it refers to the second group.

The "Epidemic of Neurologic degenerative diseases" such as Alzheimer's are already known since decades to be a source of future global healthcare and social economical concern, driven by the increasing number of people above sixty-five (Petsko, 2012). In fact, it is expected that one in every two children born in 2010s will reach the age of 100 years (Scott, 2020). The total number of individuals with AD will double every 20 years and someone in their mid-eighties has around 50% of probability of suffering from either AD or PD (Sosa-Ortiz, 2012).

Currently is estimated around 0.7% of the global population has dementia translating to 51.6 million people worldwide. Epidemiology metrics show a continuous increase in prevalence, incidence, and mortality rates worldwide during the last three decades (Javaid, S. et al, 2021). Data from Alzheimer's Association (2023) show that between 2000 and 2019 the AD death rate in US increased 33% from people aged 65 to 74 but increased 78% for people aged 85 or older.

Fig 02 - US Annual Alzheimer's death rate (per 100000 people) on overall US population. Source: Alzheimer's Association (2023)

Already in 2012 Petsko described that if no Disease Modifying Therapy (DMT) that could halt or slow the progression of AD is found, by 2050 the costs of these diseases will represent a pressing health economic burden of more than \$1 trillion only in the United States.

Fig 03 - Worldwide increase in share of population over the age of sixty-five; black countries denoting countries where those over age of sixty-five make up for more than 20% of the population at the time of the article (2012) and projected in 2050, data mainly took from WHO and UN. Source: Petsko, G. (2012)

Studies indicate AD patients over 65 survive an average of four to eight years after diagnosis. Yet, some extreme cases can live up to 20 years with this disease. Patients from age 70 to 80 will spend on average 40% of this time in the severe stage (Alzheimer’s Association, 2023). So, the severity and long duration of this disease create a massive public health crisis.

One way to measure the burden of a disease is through its disability-adjusted life years (DALYs):

$$\text{DALYs} = \text{YLLs} + \text{YLDs}$$

YLLs: number of years of life lost due to premature disease mortality
YLDs: number of years lived with disease disability

DALYs measures indicate that AD is a very burdensome disease not only to the people with the disease, but also to their families and informal caregivers (Alzheimer’s Association, 2023). This represents a huge societal burden cost. Assuming by 2050 every family will have a relative with one of these diseases, with most patients carried at home, the psychological and financial burden of the family caregivers is of great concern. A report by the World Economic Forum and Harvard School of Public Health from 2011, indicates the predicted cost to society worldwide from mental illness and dementia disabilities is higher than that of cancer, diabetes and chronic respiratory diseases combined.

Despite these public health, economical and societal problems have been identified since decades, still in 2022, patient do not have access to DMTs. In fact, multiple stakeholders tried innovative pathways to bring the first DMT to market in 2021. Yet, it turned out to be very controversial at different levels, as it is explored later in this dissertation.

This raises a lot of strategic questions:

- Apart from the scientific challenges, could one argued that the governance policies, research incentives, and industry efforts have failed so far in the field of development therapies for neurodegenerative diseases?
- Are there any particularities to the business model of researching and developing therapies in this field that make the return on investment less attractive, compared to other fields of the business such as Oncology?
- Why the rich innovation breakthrough seen in previous decades on drug development for other therapeutic areas, such as HIV and Cancer, was never translated to the neurodegeneration ecosystem?
- Is the sense of urgency and tolerance from different stakeholder for riskier innovation and earlier investment in biomarkers exploration not as high in the public Agenda?

1.5. Regulatory context

The development and commercialisation of a new drug is a highly regulated business. Different Governmental Agencies make sure that the latest policies and regulatory requirements are followed before a company can introduce a new drug on the market. Yet, the choices about the sponsoring and approval of new drugs involve debates about societal goals and priorities, that go beyond purely scientific matters.

In Europe the regulations can be quite complex. For some products, EMA grants centralised drug approvals for a drug to be used across European market. But companies can also follow regulatory routes with National Agencies from specific member states to have approval only in one specific European country.

FDA is an agency within the US department of health and human services. Since the US represents the biggest market for most of the world pharmaceutical companies, FDA is the regulatory agency that has more influence on the strategies of most global biopharmaceutical firms. For that reason, **in the scope of this dissertation the angle of the US market, and FDA regulations, is prioritised.**

Overall, all regulatory agencies rely on traditional full approval pathways for the development of new drugs. It involves generating clinical evidence to show safety and efficacy in the patient population that shall be claimed on the product label. Full regulatory approvals require the drug to endure all the different clinical trials phases. It generally requires two positive Phase III trials showing statistically efficacy differentiation versus placebo on a clinical meaningful outcome, such as overall survival or performance in a clinical scale. For the firms developing the drug, the regulatory requirements of a traditional full drug approval translate into an average investment between 10 to 15 years, and up to \$6 billion, to bring a new drug to market (Rennane, S., 2021).

What are surrogate endpoints in drug development?

To understand the concept of a surrogate endpoint, it is important to appreciate the meaning around 'endpoints' and 'biomarkers' in the context of clinical development.

In simplistic general terms, an **endpoint** is:

an outcome or event that can objectively be measured in a clinical trial with the aim to determine if the therapy being studied is beneficial.

And a **clinical endpoint** is:

a direct measure of how the patient feels, functions, or survives.

The selection of the right endpoint is often the subject of debate (LoCasale, R.J. et al, 2021) as the endpoints favoured by one stakeholder (e.g., regulatory agencies) may not always be meaningful to other stakeholders (e.g., payors or patients).

A **biomarker** is defined as:

"any substance, structure, or process that can be measured in the body or its products and influence or predict the incidence of outcome or disease" (World Health Organisation, 2001).

Or as specified by FDA *"a marker, such as a laboratory measurement, radiographic image, physical sign, or other measure, that is not itself a direct measurement of clinical benefit".*

Biomarkers may, but not necessarily, correlate with patient's experience, sense of wellbeing and clinical health state. When a biomarker is used as a primary researched outcome in a clinical trial, they are often being used as a surrogate endpoint, meaning acting as a surrogate or substitute for a "clinical endpoint".

A *surrogate endpoint*:

acts as a surrogate or substitute for a "clinical endpoint" and instead of directly measuring the clinical benefit of primary interest, it is expected to predict the clinical benefit based on therapeutic, pathophysiologic, epidemiologic, or other scientific evidence (FDA website).

The use of surrogate endpoints may allow clinical trials to be conducted faster, at a lower cost, and/or for shorter durations. The key challenge to transform a biomarker in a surrogate endpoint is determining the association between the biomarker and the relevant clinical outcome (Strimbu, K. et al, 2011).

Most of the surrogate endpoints are biomarkers (some nuances in Oncology), but not all biomarkers are surrogate endpoints. Some examples of surrogate endpoints used in clinical trials:

- **Blood pressure**, a surrogate endpoint used for the clinical outcome of a **stroke**.
- **HIV viral load**, a surrogate endpoint used for the clinical outcome of patient **progression into acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS)**.
- **Progression Free-Survival** (length of time from study start until appearance of new lesion) used as a surrogate endpoint of **Overall Survival** clinical outcome (length of time from study start until death).

Response Rate Percentage of patients who achieve a response (tumor shrinkage) usually defined as greater than or equal to 30% decrease in the sum of diameters of target lesions
Progression-Free Survival Time from randomization to disease progression (defined as $\geq 20\%$ increase in the sum of diameters of target lesions with an absolute increase of at least 5 mm or any new lesion) or death
Disease-Free Survival Time from randomization until tumor recurrence or death from any cause
Time to Tumor Progression Time from randomization until tumor progression (does not include deaths)
Invasive Disease-Free Survival Relevant to adjuvant treatment of breast cancer and defined as the time from randomization until the date of the first occurrence of one of the following events: recurrence of ipsilateral invasive breast tumor, recurrence of ipsilateral locoregional invasive disease, a distant disease recurrence, contralateral invasive breast cancer, or death from any cause
Pathological Complete Response Rate Applicable in neoadjuvant treatment of cancer; percentage of patients who achieve a pathological complete response, which is defined as the absence of invasive neoplastic cells at microscopic examination of the primary tumor at surgery

Fig 04 - Example of surrogate endpoint measures commonly used by regulators to approve oncology drugs, based on the assumption that they are reliable predictors of overall survival (OS) clinical outcomes for patients. Source: Gyawali, B (2019)

From regulatory perspective, based on the level of clinical evidence to demonstrate the prediction of the specified clinical benefit, a surrogate endpoint (SE) is often referenced in three categories: as *candidate SE*, *reasonably likely SE*, or *validated SE*. However, some authors (Strimbu, K. et al, 2011) argue that becoming a validated surrogate endpoint is not black-or-white matter, but more of spectrum. In fact, they defend replacing the term “validation” by “evaluation”, to better describe the ongoing process of progressively understanding biomarker’s success at acting as surrogate for clinical endpoints.

Also considering that Neurodegeneration traditional clinical outcomes by themselves are more subjective than the ones used in Oncology. While one could use traditional clinical scales to ‘measure’ cognition, these are more subjective to be influenced by how patients and/or caregivers are feeling compared to a measure of overall survival used in Oncology. Hence, the even more urgent need to invest in the development of better endpoint markers in Neurodegeneration.

Section 507 of the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act includes a requirement that the FDA publish “*a comprehensive list of... (ii) all surrogate endpoints which were the basis of approval or licensure of a drug or biological product*” under both accelerated and traditional approval provisions. There is also a requirement to update the table every 6 months (Agyeman, A., 2022).

FDA website says that the acceptability of the surrogate endpoints described in the list for use in development program “*will be determined on a case-by-case basis, depending on the context such as: the disease, studied patient population, therapeutic mechanism of action and availability of current treatments*”. The FDA list includes 124 surrogate endpoints (consulted in H2 2022). Most of these are for cancer or viral and metabolic diseases. There is only one surrogate endpoint related to neurodegenerative diseases that is the reduction in amyloid beta plaques as surrogate to decrease of the progression of Alzheimer's disease.

Accelerated regulatory approval

The Accelerated Approval (AA) regulations were first established by FDA in 1992, designed to improve patients access to therapeutics for severe diseases, by allowing companies to begin marketing appropriate drugs earlier based on shorter clinical trials that identify preliminary efficacy improvements in surrogate outcomes (assuming no concerns from safety aspects). This regulation also requires companies to conduct longer post-marketing confirmatory Phase III trials to verify clinical efficacy to be able to convert the accelerated approval into a full approval (Richey, E., 2009). This regulation was first created to response to the AIDS Epidemic seen in the 80's and early 90's when HIV was identified, and AIDS was a leading cause of death for Americans with no approved treatment on the market. The AA approvals were based on HIV viral load surrogate endpoints, which allowed much faster development programs than if FDA had required to show Phase III evidence on AIDS-related deaths outcomes. Of course, the first HIV approved therapies had its limitations. But over time FDA flexibility together with an energized industry, scientific community, and advocacy, have generated positive drug innovation and currently most people can get HIV under control with the available treatments on the market (Ghiasvand, H., 2019). Given the sharp rise of cancer as a Public Health problem, in 1995 the Office of the President of the United States decided to expand the use of AA regulations to Oncology setting, to facilitate shortened development timelines and early access to novel cancer agents based on earlier analysis of surrogates endpoints.

FDA latest regulations describe that a surrogate endpoint that:

- is **“known to predict clinical benefit”** could be used to support **traditional full approval** of a drug;
- is **“reasonably likely to predict clinical benefit”** could be used to support **accelerated approval** of a drug.

The AA regulations represented a tentative to balance the benefit of early access of drug for severe diseases based on certain empirical evidence with the risk of bringing an ineffective drug to market. If drugs are found to be ineffective after reaching the market, public health concerns are raised with payers bearing the costs of a drug that could potential not bring value to patients. On the other hand, the interval between the time an effective drug could have conceivably been available and the time it becomes available also raises concerns, especially when depriving people suffering from severe diseases that have no other treatments available. Patient advocates, industry, academics, and regulators seem to align that in most of these cases it is desirable to speed initial marketing approval without proof of clinical benefit as these people are willing to take greater risk for earlier access to novel therapies (Califf, R., 2017). The philosophy of shorter clinical trials with faster entry to market is also supported in advances in real-life settings of clinical electronic records, information storage and analytic methods, that allow better tracking of data for a marketed drug throughout its lifecycle. This real-world evidence (RWE) could be used as a complement to traditional clinical trials data, namely in improving the knowledge of correlation between a surrogate endpoint and its clinical outcomes (Dagenais, S. 2021).

It is argued by some stakeholders that waiting for long clinical trials could be unethical for critical diseases that urge for more creative innovation. Patients in more advanced stage of disease decline faster, so treatment effect and outcomes in these populations can be more rapidly observed. Thus, for these reasons these patients are often the primary focus of clinical trials under traditional regulatory paradigms. However, these patients are less respondent to innovative disease-modifying therapies, and not the ones that would benefit the most from these drugs. So, the use of surrogate endpoints through accelerated approvals is also seen as an efficient model to disrupt this problem and promote investment in clinical trials that use biomarkers to identify the patients that could benefit the most from a therapy, often the ones still in the early stages of the disease (Scott, T., 2014).

1.6. Intellectual property (IP)

As a market entry barrier that protects firms R&D investment, Intellectual Propriety (IP) legal requirements are major factors influencing access of new innovative medicines (Tenni, B. et al, 2022). The patent system plays a critical role in spurring innovation. The IP specificities in the biopharmaceutical industry are complex, but in simplistic terms the patent that is filled in early drug discovered when a new candidate is select is the most important aspect. This grants the firm 20 years of market exclusivity on that drug indication since the date of its filling.

There are also other requirements besides the patent itself, such as regulatory data exclusivity, orphan exclusivity or paediatric rewards that instead start counting only once the drug receives market authorisation. Orphan legislation and paediatric rewards are in place to provide incentives in drug development of rare diseases and paediatric populations, perceived as less economically interesting market and with lack of return on investment (Mulber, A. 2019). So, thanks to this

additional legislation Orphan drugs in rare disease benefit from 10 years market exclusivity kicking off from start of market approval, regardless of the time it took to develop the drug. This resulted in companies changing their strategic focus to rare diseases, that despite their low volume are not only incentivised with additional market exclusivity but also with premium prices.

Fig 05 - Self-created illustration of the life cycle of a hypothetical drug candidate selected in 2020 that takes 10 years to develop & reach the market, highlighting that a long drug development pathway can jeopardize the trade-off equilibrium of getting enough market exclusivity time to justify its high R&D investment.

However, these extra incentives are not applicable to the group of high prevalence neurodegenerative diseases aim of this dissertation, such as Alzheimer's or Parkinson's. Furthermore, these diseases progress slower than most of typical rare diseases, thus heavily suffering from longer clinical development trials that compromise their period of market exclusivity. The main protection that companies have to their R&D investments is the market exclusivity given by the patent filled when the candidate drug is selected. Generally speaking, the longer the drug development journey, the less time these drugs will benefit from market exclusivity to recuperate their return on investment.

1.7. Oncology ecosystem

Cancer mortality dropping faster than incidence

Fig 06 - Left: World's leading cause of death from 2000 to 2019, where it can be seen the faster increase of Alzheimer's and other dementias compared lung related cancers. Source: WHO. **Right:** Detailed death rate for all types of cancer since the 90's, denoting an overall positive decrease. Source: IHME.

Apart from acute cardiovascular and respiratory illness, Cancer is among the top of chronic diseases with leading causes of dead worldwide. In 2019, there were 18.1 million new cases diagnosed and 9.5 million of all cancer related to deaths worldwide. However, the death rates of the different types of cancer have declined substantially since the 1990s. A rise in incidence could reflect a real increase of new cases, but also could be linked to better diagnosing capabilities that detects new cases, even when they cause no clinical outcomes during someone's life.

The fact that oncology death rates are dropping faster than incidence, reflects the positive progress of the available diagnostics and treatments against the disease over the past 30 years.

With overall decline in death rates, the number of cancer survivors have significantly increased in countries where oncology drugs have been made available over the past decades. For all cancers in US there was an average increase of 17% between the late 70s and early 2010s of people living longer than five years following diagnosis.

Fig 07 - There has been a general increase for all types of cancers on avg five-year survival rates in US between the periods of 1970-77 to 2007-2013. Indicating a higher % of people who live longer than five years following the diagnosis. Source: Roser, M. et al (2018)

As of January 2022, there are 18.1 million cancer survivors in US, and this number is projected to grow to 26 million by 2040 (NCI). Like the progress seen on the therapeutic control of AIDS, the positive epidemiologic numbers in oncology signal the successes achieved with the higher number of earlier access of cancer therapies through accelerated approval in the US market.

Fig 08 - Number of new oncology drugs launched over the past two decades has considerably increase. The US had the biggest boost of new drugs hitting the market. Source: IQVIA

Speed of innovation in Oncology

IDEA pharma, a leading consultancy group focused on pharmaceutical industry, distinguishes both the capacity for Invention and Innovation, as two key aspects to prosper in the field.

Invention being described as the ability to creating novelty, meaning breakthrough candidates with potential for being first-in-class drugs; and *Innovation* as the creation of meaningful value from inventions, in other words, the pathway of how the novel ideas/drugs can reach the market successfully.

The business of effectively developing and bringing drugs with greater value to the market, as per IDEA pharma definition of innovation, seems to have catapulted in oncology over the past decades.

The converging of different appetites and multi-stakeholders' efforts have made the success of oncology drugs to progressively induce successive efforts and investments. When compared to other drugs in different therapeutic areas, new oncology drug reaching the market were more often first-in-class, meaning with a new and unique mechanism of action (DiMasi, J., 2019).

Oncology drugs were approved twice as fast by FDA as Neurology drugs. Benefiting from expedited approval pathways, nearly half of the trials from 2013-15 were approved based on phase II data (Albrecht, B., 2018). These aspects seem to have contributed for general shortening of product life cycle in oncology. This shows the pull for both disruptive and incremental innovation in the field.

Fig 09 - Shortened speed of innovation in Oncology: time without competition of drugs with similar modes of action (even if not in the same tumour type or line of therapy) may now be as short as one to two years. Source: Albrecht, B., 2018, McKinsey

The intensity of competition in bringing new value to market seems to pull for further drugs with increasing targeted differentiation. The follow-on drugs tended to be more focused on subsegments of cancers and targeted patient populations identified through biomarkers, for which the drug brings more value (Albrecht, B., 2018).

The adaptive regulatory pathways with the appropriate risk approach seemed to play a catapult role on this increased speed of innovation in Oncology. This will try to be better understood in the literature review and analysis section.

1.8. Innovation challenge in Neurodegeneration drug development

Two distinct types of drugs can be developed for neurodegenerative diseases: the ones that relieve some symptoms but without targeting the primary physiopathology route cause, referred to as symptomatic drugs; and the ones that aim to obtain an enduring clinic benefit by targeting the underlying pathophysiology cause of the disease, often referenced as Disease Modifying Therapies (DMTs). Systematic search showed that in contrast of EMA that generally still uses the “disease modification” terminology, FDA started to use as of 2018 the term “persistent effect on disease course” (Morant *et al*, 2019).

Lack of disease-modifying solutions brought to market

A therapy that would allow a delay of 5 years in AD if available by 2025, would decrease the total number of patients by 50% in 2050 (Cummings *et al.*, 2018). However, as of 2018, only around seventy drugs with DMTs potential could be found in the global neurodegeneration R&D pipeline. This sum is less than half the number of novel clinical programs seen just for a single sub-indication for oncology (Cummings *et al.*, 2018; Thomas, D., 2019).

The drugs on the AD development pipeline aiming to potentially reverse progression of disease follow different mechanics strategies. The two strategies with stronger evidence target the accumulation of malign forms of beta-amyloid or the tau proteins. These are thought to correlate with progression of disease towards cognitive decline. The drugs targeting directly these pathways represent more than 60% of the pipeline. The other 40% are also thought to play a role either downstream or upstream of beta-amyloid and tau accumulation (Thomas, D., 2019).

Fig 10 - Overview mechanism of action in AD development pipeline with potential for DMTs as of Feb 2019. Source: Thomas, D., 2019 (BIO)

The “valley of death” or “lost in translation crisis”, often referred to describe the challenging gap that is to move a molecule from lab “bench” to the patient “bed”, is especially big in neurodegenerative diseases drug development compared to other therapeutic spaces (Seyhan, A., 2019). By 2021 FDA had approved only six drugs with indication for the treatment of Alzheimer’s disease (AD). Five of these drugs, are expected to treat its symptoms only temporarily, not to interfering with underlying brain changes or alter course of the disease. After these first five symptomatic treatments, there was a gap of almost two decades without any new drug reaching the market for AD.

Finally, the sixth drug came only in 2021. Aducanumab, often known by its brand name, Aduhelm, from the American company Biogen. This was the first ever approval of a DMT thought to address the underlying biology of AD, through reduction of beta-amyloid plaques in the brain, rather than treating its symptoms. The process followed the FDA accelerated approval pathway and became a very controversial case study that will be analysed further in this paper.

The development of a DMT in the field of AD takes an average of 13 years, cost \$5.6 billion, and the value of its return in investment is very uncertain (Scott, T., 2014). Together with the lack of appropriate policies, this seem to have retracted private investment and willingness to compete for innovation in this ecosystem, like what is seen in HIV or Oncology field. Diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's often progress slowly. The use of traditional clinical outcomes assessment endpoints in the clinical trials (e.g. questionnaires of clinical dementia rating scores going from 2 to 3), makes the trials last for several years just to try to demonstrate statistically significant data in Phase II proof-of-concept and establishing an optimal dose. So, companies had to be motivated to devote several years of patent life to Phase II and Phase III trials.

Despite the societal demand for DMTs, the financial costs and risk associated with AD drug development has historically discouraged potential firms to invest in developing drugs in this field. This ultimately decreased the availability of new innovative therapies for people with or at risk for this devastating disease (Cummings, J. et al, 2016). Already in 2008, Cummings suggested some strategies to speed clinical trials in the field of neurodegeneration, such as focusing on enrichment of clinical trials population (e.g., with genetic marked sub-population that could be fast progressors, etc.) and investing on biomarkers (e.g., resonance imaging, cerebrospinal fluid tau and amyloid PET, etc.), as alternative to traditional scales of clinical observation. As represented in Fig. 11, firms could choose between potential biomarkers to be explored in earlier clinical development and, depending on risk appetite, decide on best trade-off between trial duration and level of evidence that it predicts a clinical outcome for patients.

Fig 11 - Time versus confidence trade-off in the level of evidence in clinical studies. Source: Cummings, J. (2008)

Positron Emission Tomography (PET) is an imaging technology often used in oncology drug development to access the tumour response rate to a therapy. More recently PET scan started to be proposed as a biomarker in AD to visualize the presence of beta-amyloid plaques in the brain, a prime suspect of killing nerve cells and cause cognitive impairment in these patients (before PET

technology this could only be assessed through brain examining at autopsy). An example of an even faster and lower evidence biomarker would be Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), that measures small changes in blood flow that occur with brain activity.

However, the good trade-off between long trials based on traditional clinical assessment and faster trials based on surrogate endpoints still seems to be very controversial in the space of Alzheimer’s disease, unlike in the Oncology space. Alzheimer’s disease progresses from a pre-clinical stage, where there is absence of clinical signs and the presence of at least one biomarker; to prodromal stage, also referred as mild cognitive impairment, where some mild signs start to appear; to the later stage of AD Dementia. In general, biomarkers start to be noticed in the disease journey much before any clinical signal or symptom, such as the clinical assessment of cognitive impairment. The accumulation of amyloid plaques in the brain are showed to be one of the first biomarkers appearing in the early pre-clinical stages of AD, and when it reaches a tipping point there is a later spread and accumulation of tau protein throughout the brain (Takahashi, R., 2017). For either of these two targets, there could be different biomarkers depending on the type of technology or body fluid analysed. For example, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) collection through lumbar puncture (needle inserted between lumbar vertebrae) often gives an earlier detection than PET as illustrated by Fig. 12:

Fig 12 - Hypothetical model of dynamic AD biomarkers through disease progression. Source: Adapted from Selkoe, D. (2016)

As it will be explored in the later sections of this paper, the Neurodegeneration ecosystem still does not have the right pull for using biomarkers such as amyloid PET to bring DMTs to the market. Whereas the drug development field in Oncology has radically evolved throughout the years with the use of precision medicine approaches targeting specific targeted populations with the use of biomarkers, the Neurodegeneration field still lags years behind.

1.9. Neurodegeneration vs Oncology

R&D spending and its investment funding

The overall investment in in drug R&D of biopharmaceutical firms present in US market has increased over the past years, apart from a flat period between 2008-2014 (Fig.13 left). A big

driver conditioning the amount of money these firms invest in R&D is the amount of revenue expected to earn from a new drug, plus specific policies related to therapeutic space.

The link between the amount invested in R&D and new drug approvals can be argued. New drugs approvals had a declining valley aligned with similar period of lower R&D investment (Fig.13 right), yet the relationship behind these tables can be complex. First, there is a lag between the period of R&D investment and its translation into new drug approvals. Second, fluctuations in R&D costs can also be linked with macro events such cost of capital and cost of labour. Third, the number of new drugs approved decrease if there is high rate of clinical trial failures even with enlarged R&D investment.

Fig 13 - Left: Annual R&D spending by PhRMA Member Firms (Billion \$); **Right:** Number of New Drug approvals (five-year Moving Average). Source: US Congressional Budget office (used PhRMA annual reports data)

PhRMA – Pharmaceutical Research and Manufactures of America - represent the leading biopharmaceutical research companies devoted to discovering and developing medicines present on the American market

However, it is generally understood that if the firms expected profitability of a new drug declines (due to changes in policies that would require longer development and less time of market exclusivity, lower price prospects, market size, etc.), it will have less returns on its R&D investment. The company will have less pull incentives to continue to invest in R&D, and at some point, this will mean less innovative drugs on the market. Elasticity of innovation of all global biopharmaceutical firms seems to be specifically sensible to changes in expectations of profitability and demand in US market (Blume-Kohout, M., 2013).

Fig 14 - 2009 -2018 venture funding for companies with R&D pipeline with lead products in Oncology *versus* companies with lead products in Alzheimer's Disease. Source: Thomas, D., 2019 (BIO)

Fig 14 shows venture investment into US companies with lead early-stage novel drug programs in AD is 16 times below the capital funding of companies with early-stage oncology drugs in their pipeline, \$1 billion versus 16,5 billion from 2008 to 2017. With 9 companies with lead AD drugs

being financed each year, compared to 79 companies with oncology drugs financed each year by investors (Thomas, D., 2019).

Despite the much bigger venture capital funding of oncology novel R&D drugs, dementia is the chronic disease with highest healthcare direct costs in the US:

Fig 15 – Contrast between venture Capital funding of novel R&D vs US Healthcare Direct Costs (2008-2017) for highly prevalent chronic diseases. Source: Thomas, D., 2019 (BIO)

The data above shows a big contrast between where majority drug R&D venture funding is going, Oncology, versus where there is highest need to find innovative solutions to reduce healthcare burden costs, Dementia. The need for very long clinical trials to detect clinical effects in slow progressing diseases such as Alzheimer is one of the reasons for this. In fact, on average, Neurodegenerative drugs take around 60% longer to reach approval than drugs from other disease areas (Thomas, D., 2019). This decreases the time of patent market exclusivity and the financially attractiveness for investors compared to the much fast-paced and dynamic drug development environment in oncology (Blume-Kohout, M., 2012).

Dealmaking activity

Deal activity in neurological diseases is approximately one third of that in oncology, which is by far the leading therapeutic area receiving more investment through dealmaking (Yachu, S., 2021). The intensity of dealmaking also oscillates based on the perception of how attractive the return on investment of having a pipeline with drugs under development in that specific area. For example, dealmaking activity had a sharp decline in 2019 once disappointing clinical results from leading biopharma. However, the very last three years the interest and confidence in the field seems to start to rump up following some positive signals in the field, such as positive results from Phase II programs and willingness from policy makers to find creative pathways to support pull neurologic therapies to market.

The most common types of deals seen in the area are partnerships. This shows that investors are yet not so much looking to buy companies with Alzheimer’s drug pipelines, or in-licensing some of their drugs, but instead look for joint partnership to co-share costs and risks together.

Fig 16 - Number and type of deals in Alzheimer’s disease space, 2016 up to November 2021. Source IQVIA

FDA first accelerated approval of the first disease modifying therapy on late 2021, has help foster interest in the field that could translate in growing deal activities beyond 2022, and also the level of M&A and assets in-licensing activities (Bhambra, R., 2022).

The breakdown of biopharma partnerships by therapeutic area in 2022, reflects this raising activity, with already Neurology appearing in the podium as the third therapeutic area with most deals, even if still considerable behind oncology (Fig 17):

Fig 17 - Biopharma partnerships in 2022. Source: Giglio, P. (2023)

2. Literature review

Despite the bone of this dissertation being on strategic innovation, the overall topic is quite vast. A contributing factor for going for a broader scope, lies with the belief that the art of innovating when bringing a new drug to market is dependent on the holistic understanding of its interconnected disciplines. This is where the future change makers in the industry need to excel to be able to break its long development cycles. The literature researched varied from more traditional management publications on Innovation and Strategic Leadership, to more precise research publications applied to the field of drug development.

The selection of the literature has mainly been done by a “snowball method” where references of references have been explored to identify relevant articles.

2.1 Strategic innovation in drug R&D

Diverse literature is published on the general topic of innovation, and its strategic leadership component. Wynn, A. et al (2018, 2020, 2022) describe along its trilogy of innovation books for business leaders, how the keys for innovation are interlocked between the *processes*, the *organisation* and the *people* that play in a certain environment. In the context of drug development, the innovation network is especially complex, made of an ecosystem-wide endeavour that needs integrated contribution from all the different stakeholders.

This section 2.1 describes some literature and theories related to innovation in research and development, namely on:

- 2.1.1 Intermediaries involved
- 2.1.2 Pull & push strategies
- 2.1.3 Decision Making & risk taking

2.1.1 Innovation intermediaries

Research and development of new drugs is mainly an area of open Innovation, where ideas and processes are part of a collaboration among different stakeholders and institutions with different backgrounds. The Triple Helix model, first introduced by Etzkowitz in 2003 describes the interactions among the main institutional spheres: **Science (S)**, **Industry or Business (B)** and **Governance (G)**.

Fig 18 – Intermediaries in the triple Helix model from Ranga and Etzkowitz

It has been showed that the successful relations between the different players are pivotal to innovation and economic growth. Ivanova (2014) describes a three-step mechanism to generate this growth through “*knowledge production, wealth creation and normative control*”. Particularly, the interface spaces between Three Helix spheres can make a significant difference in brokering the different spheres together to share risks or promote clarity of communication around decision making and diffusion of knowledge (Etzkowitz, 2010).

In 2013, Ranga and Etzkowitz (FIG. 19) further reframed the Triple Helix Systems a set of:

- 1) Components, as the wide range of actors playing around its different spheres.
- 2) Relationships between its components.
- 3) Functions, represented as the innovation processes undertaken.

Fig 19 – representation of Ranga and Etzkowitz triple helix systems

In the context of drug development innovation, one could argue that **other important helixes are missing in the initial triple helix model from Etzkowitz**. The **public and societal sphere** are fundamental and influence drastically the perception of the risk when bringing a new drug to the market, with a certain efficacy level and at a determined price. Also, given the cultural differences in each society, the extent to which each Helix influences drug development innovation is expected to vary depending on the countries.

Authors such as Chesbrough (2012) also explored the impact of Intellectual Propriety (IP) as a pivotal point influencing the intermediaries involved in open innovation. Defending strong IP protection measures can make a difference to motivate the Business sphere to collaborate more confidently with the other helixes.

It is interesting to verify the Triple Helix theories thinking on circular innovation that appears iteratively on the interphase of different helixes through creative reconstruction, with sustained effort, that at some point can catapult into disruptive innovation, somehow in opposition of Schumpeter's theory of creative destruction. Open innovation with good helix interphases, when well applied to drug development in neurodegeneration could help accelerate transition to high-risk, higher gain development models and bigger disrupted innovation for the long run to all stakeholders involved in the field. Like venturing in accelerated regulatory pathways; taking more risk in sharing data with competitors that could allow learnings in optimal combination of drugs through external collaborations among different companies; or government venturing as entrepreneur (Albert N., 2009).

As the Government been as far removing innovation barriers in Neurodegeneration like it has been seen in Oncology?

Literature highlights the potential for collaboration among public and private sector stakeholders to improve the productivity and efficiency of research and development (R&D) investments. Albert N. (2009) defends that the marginal social benefit of government as entrepreneur is greater than marginal social costs, assuming its involvement is efficient. In its book, Albert characterises government as entrepreneur, when putting in place a specific subset of government policy actions that take entrepreneurial risk.

With regards to the outcomes in Neurodegeneration drug development innovation, it seems Business and Governmental forces have provided limited effect so far, or could the blocking point be on the societal axis to recognise the needs and accept these risks like they do in oncology?

Bendicken L. (2020), health economist focused on the relationship between drug prices and innovation, defends the role of government should be limited to funding basic science discovery research, where it can solve a problem of lack of 'appropriability', meaning the degree to which social returns to innovation are privately appropriated. On the other hand, he argues that for the development stages the government should rely on the private market, where small biotech companies would naturally compete to make the best early-stage development of promising molecules and then sell it to bigger pharma that will take it to market.

Within the Societal Helix, "Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs)" are pivotal actors influencing the different stakeholders in the innovation ecosystem when developing a drug. They were born by the mid-1950s with pharmaceutical industry and regulators making use of expert physicians and scientist in a specific therapeutic area to support communications among the different helix interphases when developing and commercializing a new drug. As Foucault would put it, they were part of a different historical period with other epistemological assumptions that accepted a different scientific discourse. Scher, J. (2021) has critical view on KOLs and advocates for a shift in the industry from

traditional KOLs to Innovation and Knowledge Leaders (IKLs). Challenging the former to go from focusing on prescribing habits and treatment recommendations to scientific knowledge and innovative work (see Table 20). Striking an increased balance between investing in innovation vs opinion dissemination, that is needed with the evolution of the current scientific period of drug development.

Characteristic	IKL	KOL
Function	Scientist	Influencer
Aim	Gain of knowledge	Gain of influence
Motivation	Hunger for knowledge	Hunger for status
Key process	Innovation	Implementation
Data source	Own	External
Data handling	Data generation	Data dissemination
Concept	To be devised/conceived	Pre-formed
Instrument	Experiment	Steering committee
Study type	Investigator-initiated	Industry-sponsored
Project	Public initiative	Industry symposium
Involvement with industry	Early- and late-stage research	Late-stage research — post asset approval
Drug analogy	Originator	Biosimilar
Newspaper section analogy	Front page	Opinion page

IKL, innovation and knowledge leader; KOL, key opinion leader.

Fig 20 – Comparison of IKLs and traditional KOLs. Source: Scher, J. (2021)

2.1.2 Push and Pull strategies

The definition of innovation may vary depending on the authors. However, all seem to align that it can “either be imposed under pressure of an external agent or may be voluntary as the behaviour is more conducive to reaching a certain goal” (J. Pierson, 2011).

In other words, innovative behavior can be “*Pushed*” by government or other parties; or it can be “*Pulled*” as a result of the perceived needs of the environment.

Mueller-Langer, F (2013) explored different push and pull mechanisms that either subsidize research input or reward its output, in the context of drug research & development:

Fig 21 - Example of Push and Pull incentives in R&D. Source: Mueller-Langer, F (2013)

The literature shows how “Push” techniques could help “pay for effort”, often recurring to policies that reduce early costs for industries; whereas “Pull” mechanisms focus on creating market demands, in other words “paying for results” (Grace, C., 2009).

Overall, literature shows that the best strategies in drug research & development are the ones that are equally supported synergistically by a combination of push & pull mechanisms. It is obvious that external funding grants coming from organisation such as US National Institutes of Health or UK Medical Research Council can support the initial investment of small companies; however, to have sustained efforts along the full innovation value chain with risky assets, industry expects eventual return of its investment through successful sales in the long run.

As Grace, C. (2009) put it, the initial “push” could be more effective when the level of effort is easy and industry already has high tolerance for risk, but “pull” strategies will be needed when business is more risk adverse, being more determinant to sustain adoption in long-term transformational innovation. As it will be seen in the analysis sections, the Oncology ecosystem has benefited both from more push and pull incentives than the Neurodegeneration arena. In Oncology there has been an especially strong pull from the market thanks to the use of accelerated development pathways and its consequent shorter innovation cycles. According to literature one could argue that this same pull mechanism would be even more beneficial in the neurodegeneration space, as it is a much more risk adverse business space.

2.1.3 Decision making and risk taking

Long literature exists on different theories surrounding decision making and risk taking. Mante-Meijer & Loos (2008) suggested that “*If the perceived risks are too great, people abstain from making a decision and keep things as they are*”. Douglas & Wildavsky (2004) reinforce the impact of cultural differences towards risk taking, defending that in individualist settings people focus more on personal gain while in regulated cultures people are more concerned in not breaking the rules.

Merckler, M. (2020) developed a framework for understanding how management decision errors, such as:

- unwise intervention strategies,
- well-intended work on the wrong problems,
- or ignorance of significant correlations,

may lead to iatrogenic outcomes, defined as the unintentional genesis of different problems. In most cases the impact of these problems can certainly go behind the organisation, affecting the broader societal innovation target.

Summary of Strategic Leadership Decision Errors		
Category type	Strategic decision process stage	Error type
I	Correlation	Alpha error. Misunderstanding the forces at play. Mistakenly claiming a correlation or relationship.
II	Correlation	Beta error. Misunderstanding the forces at play. Mistakenly claiming no correlation or no relationship.
III	Vision	Visioning error. Pursuing/solving the wrong issues, problems, or goals.
IV	Innovation	Innovation error. Proposing inadequate tactical alternatives. Choosing poorly.
V	Action	Inaction error. Not acting when you should.
VI	Action	Action error. Acting when you should not.
VII	Multiple stages	Cascade error. Errors interact. High cascade iatrogenesis risk.

Strategic leadership decision process: seeing what needs to be done, understanding the forces at play, generating and choosing from possible solutions, and making the call to act or to not act.

Fig 22 - Strategic Leadership decision errors. Source: Merckler, M (2020)

Merckler work could be of fungible application to the strategic decisions done by Biopharma Leaders with regards to sponsoring investment in innovative development pathways, accelerated regulatory approvals, or value-based pricing strategies. Biopharmaceutical drug development environment is complex, fast, and highly knowledge intense. The potential benefits of a successful strategy are high. As reasoned by Jarzabkowski and Wilson (2006), in these types of ecosystems the most efficient strategies are emergent rather than deliberated formatted, but these also increased the chances of errors.

D. Kahnemam (2013) explains in his book *“Fast and Slow thinking”* that we have a “System 1” that is a fast, unconscious, effortless and without self-warmness type of thinking, that often does 98% of our thinking. The other 2% being slow type of thinking that is deliberate and conscious, that he refers as “System 2”. According to Kahneman, some decision makers think they are in system 2 when they are in system 1. This consciousness is important for the different strategic actors playing in pharmaceutical R&D to minimize biases and decision errors. However, given the complexity of decision-making in pharmaceutical R&D, intuition (system 1 thinking according to Kahneman et al.) should not be ignored.

Trubel, H. (2022) surveyed senior decision-makers across the pharmaceutical landscape, to better understand the range of their biases and mitigation factors related to pharmaceutical R&D decision-making. The top biases identified are confirmation bias, champion bias and over-reliance on inside view. These can be mitigated, for example using “Input from Experts” for a confirmation bias. Interestingly the low ranked biases, as loss aversion, storytelling and the sunk-cost fallacy are the tougher to be mitigated.

Fig 23 - Biases and mitigation measures in pharmaceutical R&D decision-making. Source: Trubel, H (2022)

2.2 Innovative dimensions in Oncology

This section 3.2 describes available literature related to drug development innovative approaches in **Oncology**, namely in the spheres of:

- 3.2.1 Clinical development paradigms
- 3.2.2 Regulatory pathways
- 3.2.3 Pricing & Market Access
- 3.2.4 Investment & Shareholder value

2.2.1 Innovative in clinical development paradigms

According to Uber (2019), three of the most impactful factors contributing to drive innovation in the field of oncology drug development are:

- Advances in the molecular understanding of the disease,
- The Societal necessity,
- Adaptability of Regulators (specifically FDA) to support risker and disruptive clinical trials innovation.

Fig 24 - Drivers for Innovation in Oncology clinical development. Sources: from Huber, M. (2019)

The advances in the molecular understanding of cancer come together with maturation of Precision Medicine in Oncology. Lu et Al (2014) describes Precision Medicine as being the “*medical model centered on appropriate diagnostic testing based in tumors genotype to enable more customized treatments for subpopulation of patients*”, sometimes inappropriately used interchangeably with the term Personalised Medicine, that relates relating to the development of drugs that are unique to an individual patient.

Schwaederle et al. (2015) demonstrated in a meta-analysis of over 500 phase II trials that targeted subpopulations that received drugs based on expression of predictive biomarkers had better Response Rates (RR), Progression Free Survival (PFS) and Overall Survival (OS) compared to those patients where drugs were used in a nontargeted manner, confirming the superiority efficacy of precision medicine strategies in Oncology:

Fig 25 - Positive effect observed on Ph II clinical trials that target sub-populations versus trials with broader and non-personalized patient populations. Source: Schwaederle et al. (2015)

Work from Schwaederle highlights the big positive effect that strong biomarkers that allow for targeted precise medicine approach has had on Oncology clinical development. One could reflect that the lack of similar targeted approaches in Neurodegeneration, may contribute for historical ineffective results in that field.

The literature highlights the higher use of innovative clinical development paradigms in Oncology, such as the use of seamless and adaptive trials or the use of expansion cohorts, are rarely seen in other therapeutic areas. In other therapeutic areas, such as Neurology, it is still common practice to see rigidly designed trials that follow a fixed protocol without taking into consideration new incoming scientific data. In contrast, in innovative Oncology adaptive designs it is common practice to see certain aspects of the study (e.g., dose, patient numbers, enrichment of biomarkers defined sub-populations, number of cohorts and study objectives, etc.) being modified based upon real-time learnings as the study progresses (Mahajan, R. et al, 2010).

Theoret, M. et al (2015) describes how the paradigm in Oncology clinical development has been shifting from a rigid phased approach (Fig. 26 A) to an interactive and progressive paradigm where efficacy signals are assessed earlier (Fig 26 B):

Fig 26 - A: Old sequential phased approach; **B:** New Clinical Development paradigm used in Oncology; Source: Theoret, M. (2015)

This evolution has been possible in part thanks to the use of additional Expansion Cohorts (ECs) in ongoing trial, rather than a rigid standalone trial. This ECs are often used to explore additional

early development objectives, such as biomarkers development, keeping a continuous safety assessment. In this new development paradigms, there is potential for earlier observation of preliminary antitumor activity, including new unestablished surrogate endpoints that could support accelerated approval while longer confirmatory trials are ongoing to confirm a clinical benefit for a regular full approval.

An interesting example of use of ECs in first-in human studies is the Merck pembrolizumab program. This study suffered various protocol amendments to fulfil additional development objectives, accounting for efficacy endpoints conventionally used in Phase2/3 trials, and ultimately provided sufficient evidence to support accelerated approval in various melanoma populations (Theoret, M. et al, 2015) as seen in the image below:

	+14	+52	+103	+260	+254	+500	+20
IND submission Total pts = 18 Pts = melanoma and refractory carcinoma × 3 design (3 doses) OUTCOME = MTD	Amendment 1 Total pts = 32 OUTCOME = safety OUTCOME = preliminary efficacy	Amendment 2 Total pts = 84 Pts = melanoma OUTCOME = safety OUTCOME = preliminary efficacy	Amendment 3 Total pts = 187 (179) Pts = melanoma, NSCLC OUTCOME = safety OUTCOME = preliminary efficacy	Amendment 4 / 5 Total pts = 447 (439) Pts = melanoma, NSCLC OUTCOME = safety OUTCOME = preliminary efficacy	Amendment 6 Total pts = 701 (693) Pts = melanoma, NSCLC OUTCOME = safety OUTCOME = preliminary efficacy	Amendment 7 Total pts = 1047 Pts = melanoma, NSCLC OUTCOME = safety OUTCOME = preliminary efficacy	Amendment 8 Total pts = 1067 Pts = melanoma, NSCLC OUTCOME = safety OUTCOME = preliminary efficacy
	Expansion cohorts melanoma N = +7 (total = 14)	Expansion cohorts melanoma N = +52 (total = 66)	Expansion cohorts melanoma N = +50 (total = 116)	Expansion cohorts melanoma N = +148 (total = 412)	Expansion cohorts melanoma N = +100 (total = 512)	Expansion cohorts melanoma N = +230 (total = 742)	Expansion cohorts melanoma N = +0 (total = 742)
	Expansion cohorts RCC N = +7 (total = 7)		Expansion cohorts NSCLC = +35 (total = 35)	Expansion cohorts NSCLC = +112 (total = 147)	Expansion cohorts NSCLC = +154 (total = 301)	Expansion cohorts NSCLC = +154 (total = 301)	Expansion cohorts NSCLC = +20 (total = 571)
			Expansion cohorts PK - N = +6				
			Expansion cohorts PK/PD - N = +12				

Fig 27 - Example of expansion Cohorts in pembrolizumab First-in-Human (FIH) study: The initial regulatory application submitted in 2010 for pembrolizumab was to enrol 18 patients with melanoma plus 14 additional patients in an EC with melanoma and renal cell cancer. Over the next 2.5 years, 8 protocol amendments were filed, enabling the FIH study to be expanded to 9 distinct ECs enrolling a planned 1,100 patients. Source: Huber, M. (2019)

These seamless development paradigms, makes the use of the terms “phase 1”, “phase 2” etc. in Oncology sound too restrictive (Dasari, S. et al, 2014). The level of maturity of precision medicine Oncology also promoted the invention of new clinical trial strategies, such as *basket* and *umbrella* trial designs (Woodcock, J., 2017). These master trials allow subpopulation of patients expressing a specific genetic signature, to significantly increase their changes of having an innovated and efficacious therapy:

Fig 28 - Basket trial: single targeted therapy evaluated in patients with multiple different tumour types but only including patients having the target lesion. **Umbrella trial:** single tumour histology with different genetic lesions treated with different lesion-specific drugs. Source: Huber, M. (2019)

In fact, Pembrolizumab (commercial name Keytruda from Merck) was also the first drug being granted accelerated approval for use, in 2017, based on a molecular biomarker, instead of a traditional hepatologic diagnosis (Prasad, V., 2018). This approval represented a significant innovation breakthrough in precision oncology, displacing the traditional classification of cancers by the histological site of origin (breast, lung, colon cancer, etc.) towards a tissue agnostic drug that is approved based on genetic makeup.

Similar strategies, trying to stratify patients subpopulations based on biomarkers, have not yet been successful in the Neurodegeneration space.

Despite clear benefits from these tissue-agnostic approvals, literature also refers the following points of attention for stakeholders (patients, physicians, payers) that could serve as fungible lessons for other disease areas:

Points of attention on biomarker specific and tissue-agnostic approvals in Oncology <i>Adapted from Prasad, V. (2018)</i>	
Population size uncertainty	More difficult to guarantee if the claims on product label works equally in all tumour types, and this means increased uncertainty on its efficacy for payers.
Diagnostic testing in clinical practise	Pembrolizumab approved for all patients with genetic marked solid tumours, but which populations will be tested for this genetic diagnostic? Assuming total costs of diagnostics for all cancer patients, these could go up to 360 million, so payers need to consider economical cost burden of testing + treatment
Incorporating of drug in clinical practise	Approval is tissue-agnostic, but the inclusion in clinical practise protocols might still need to include tissues
Clinical trial infrastructure	Tissue-agnostic approvals poses a challenge to how clinical trials infrastructures have traditionally been set-up, where each centre screens for its own studies specialised on the type of tumour and not across genetic markers

Oncology is paving the way in this type of biomarker-specific development plans. Still even in Oncology the challenge remains of having advanced diagnostics - a single test that adequately

characterizes all targetable genomics - affordable at daily practise. Progressive collaboration across institutions and the use of Real-World Evidence data collected prospectively from clinical practise could foster the identification of relevant biomarkers. The use of RWE, together with available data from published clinical trials data can help develop disease progression models and better understand how patients flow through different stages of disease, and ultimately support better design of clinical trials with right identification of surrogate markers of patients subgroups with higher unmet need (Dogenais, S., 2021).

2.2.2 Flexible regulatory pathways

As described in the introduction section, traditional drug development paradigm has historically relied on slow standardised sequential steps with respective regulatory milestones, and often disconnected to the companion diagnostics development processes that appeared later, mapped by Dhingra, K. (2015) on Fig. 29. This creates limitation to empower agile drug approval and sponsor innovation.

Fig 29 - Traditional (linear, sequential, slow) development paradigm for **Medicines (Top)** and **Companion Diagnostics (Down)**. Source: Dhingra, K. (2015)

In Oncology space, the increase in the overall survival (OS) from the trial enrolment to death, was primarily viewed as the most clinical meaningful endpoint for clinical studies. As pointed out by Augustus S. (2011) this compromises innovation as it creates very large and costly trials, and thus less attractive for companies to invest. And adds ethical and feasibility hurdles for the control harm patients, that often opt for other therapies, switch study arms, or even withdraw study before it ends.

The Accelerated Approval (AA) from FDA and Conditional Marketing Authorization (CMA) from European Medicines Agency (EMA), reflect some flexibility and attempt to break this old paradigm.

The primary aim of this section of Literature review is to get a deeper understanding on what was published on these regulatory pathways, that have mainly been used in Oncology.

Literature on FDA Accelerated Approval (AA)

This pathway shows a recognition from US Authorities that an approval of a drug with an unvalidated surrogate marker presents uncertainty about drug true clinical benefit, often less present on a traditional approval. It shows flexibility and pragmatism from FDA to apply a model where it temporarily accepts a certain level of uncertainty in severe diseases, while attempting to fully validate the surrogate in real world. For example, with label describing the effect of the drug on the reduction of tumour size, and incomplete evidence of clinical benefit until the label is converted once full approval available with confirmation on clinical outcomes (Russel, K., 2004).

In 2004 Dagher, R. et al, was the first author making an historical review of the first decade of accelerated approval experience in US. At that time, already 18 different anticancer drugs for 22 indications had been approved under the AA pathway. In the table from Fig. 30, Dagher captured the key specificities of the first three oncology drugs ever receiving an accelerated approval and their conversion to full approval:

Product	Year confirmatory trial(s) initiated	Year accelerated/regular approval granted	Indication	Endpoint(s) supporting accelerated approval
Docetaxel (Taxotere)	1994	1996/1998	Second-line breast cancer	Response rate
Irinotecan (Camptosar)	1995	1996/1998	Second-line colon cancer	Response rate
Dexrazoxane (Zinecard)	1995	1995/2002	Reduction of doxorubicin cardiomyopathy	Cardiotoxicity, response rate to assess potential tumor protection

Fig 30 - First three Oncology drugs ever receiving an FDA AA. Source: Dagher, R (2004)

- In 1995 doxrazoxane (Zinecard) was the first oncology drug granted the AA based on tumor response rate. The sponsor was required to demonstrate that continue treatment resulted in clinical benefit, for which initiated a Phase III study that was not completed, but the drug got later conversion to regular approval in 2002 based on meta-analysis evidence generated from literature.
- Docetaxel (Taxotere) and Irinotecan (Camptosar) were granted accelerated approval in 1996 based on objective response rates in single arm studies and had 3 ongoing Phase III randomized studies ongoing at the time of AA. They received the regular full approval in 1998 based on longer survival demonstrated in these randomized studies.

In 2009 Richey, E. et al reviewed FDA data on submitted AA indications to try to understand if access to breakthrough therapies was improved or instead unsafe and ineffective drugs were unblocked to patients.

Fig 31 - Timeline of FDA AA events since its birth up to 2008. Source: Richey, E. (2009)

Richey showed that the AA process in Oncology gained full traction in the early 2000s with a slight decrease around 2004; coinciding with some drug failures to show clinical benefit in confirmatory Phase III and consequently with a recommendation from the Agency at the time to “*base initial AA applications on surrogate clinical outcomes reported on interim analysis of phase III rather than on final analysis that identified improvements in surrogate clinical measures for patients enrolled on phase II trials*”. This approach would later be challenged by other authors, as making the AA process too reactive and against the strategic goal of this pathway.

Kim and Prasad (2016), Naci, H. (2017) and Kunnumakkara, A. et al (2019) showed some worries with approving drugs based on surrogate endpoints with reduced evidence of correlation with overall survival and limitations of post-marketing commitment studies (sometimes continue to rely on surrogate endpoints or not fully completed) which led increased uncertainty on those drugs approved under AA. Albeit contra-argument that part of the goals of AA was precisely to shift the regulatory paradigm in accepting more risk in controlled manner by starting with smaller populations and developing companion diagnostics, before extension to border populations.

By 2018 Beaver, J. et al. published a review describing the 25-Year experience of FDA with Oncology AAs by searching on FDA databases. Beaver’s data review showed that from inception up to 2017 AA were granted for almost 100 indications with tumor response rate endpoint accounting for 87% of these approvals. Overall, Beaver et al (2018) defended that AAs have generally reflected an earlier access to the market of safe and effective cancer drugs. They showed that the use of AA has increased over time (Fig. 32) with the clinical benefit not being verified only in 5% of indications.

Thus, defending that AA in oncology has been a successful strategy of balancing risk uncertainty while allowing enough regulatory flexibility to make safe & effective drugs available sooner to patients.

Fig 32 - Oncology AAs and Regular Approvals by year since first approval in 1995 to 2017. Source: Beaver, J. et al (2018)

Two years later, in 2020, Chen, E. et al did a retrospective review from cancer drugs approved from January 1992 to July 2019 using FDA website and previous systematic reviews:

Characteristic	FDA approval type, No. (%)		Characteristic	FDA approval type, No. (%)	
	Accelerated	Regular		Accelerated	Regular
No. of drugs	194		Period		
FDA approval status	89 (45.8)	105 (54.1)	1992-1995	0	2 (1.0)
Converted to regular	50 (25.7)	NA	1996-1999	6 (3.1)	6 (3.1)
Accelerated only	37 (19.1)	NA	2000-2003	9 (4.6)	7 (3.6)
Withdrawn from market	2 (1.0)	NA	2004-2007	9 (4.6)	18 (9.3)
Basis for approval (end points)			2008-2011	8 (4.1)	11 (5.7)
Response rate	80 (41.2)	47 (24.2)	2012-2015	23 (11.8)	25 (12.9)
Progression-free survival	9 (4.6)	58 (29.9)	2016-2019	34 (17.5)	36 (18.6)
First vs repeated approvals			Postmarketing efficacy requirement		
First-surrogate based	28 (14.4)	36 (18.5)	OS or PRO not reported	58 (29.9)	55 (28.4)
Repeated	61 (31.4)	69 (35.6)	OS or PRO known	31 (16.0)	50 (25.7)

Fig 33 - Cancer drugs approved under accelerated and regulatory approval 1992-2019; OS: Overall Survival; PRO: Patient Reported Outcomes. Source: Chen, E. et al (2020)

Similar to the studies of Kim and Prasad (2016), Chen also showed that the cases with low correlation between surrogate endpoint and overall survival were equally seen in accelerated and regular approvals, meaning that this is not an exclusive issue of the accelerated pathways.

From other angle, Subbiah, V. (2022) defended that early regulatory approval in oncology is especially important in health equity, as all patients may not have equal access to a clinical trial participation; and promoting uptake of real-world biomarker testing, which would otherwise be limited in absence of approved therapies. Ultimately Subbiah adds that relying on the benefits of granting accelerated approval in these precision oncology indications for patients with limited to no therapeutic options, have outweighed the risks above identified. Adding that *“just as precision oncology aims to match the right patients to the right drug; the accelerated approval approach can be the right match for precision oncology”*.

Contrasting FDA AA to Conditional Marketing Authorization from EMA

Whereas the Accelerated Approval regulations is in place since 1992, the equivalent pathway from European Medicines Agency (EMA), called *Conditional Marketing Authorization (CMA)* was only launched in 2006. One thing that is common in the two processes is the fact that most drugs approved through CMA and AA pathways are cancer treatments (FDA and EMA source).

Tafari, G. et al (2014) made a comparative qualitative analysis through interviews to 7 EMA and 6 FDA Senior regulators to study how EMA and FDA decide which cancer drugs make it to market and identified key drivers for differences in decision-making. Unlike FDA, EMA does not put great focus on the use of surrogate endpoints as key feature for conditional marketing authorization (CMA). There is also misalignments on how both agencies consider endpoints in oncology, with EMA starting to adopt progression-free survival as the preferred primary endpoint FDA considers PFS as a surrogate marker to OS for some cancers, while as a measure of clinical benefit for other cancers (Salcher-Konrad, M., et al, 2020).

The table below details the differences between CMA and AA path:

	EMA Conditional Marketing Authorization (CMA) <small>European Medicines Agency. Conditional Marketing Authorisation: Report on Ten Years of Experience at the European Medicines Agency. London, England: European Medicines Agency; 2017</small>	FDA Accelerated Approval (AA) <small>Naci H, Smalley KR, Kesselheim AS. Characteristics of preapproval and post approval studies for drugs granted accelerated approval by the US Food and Drug Administration. JAMA. 2017; 318(7):</small>
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive benefit-risk profile and ability to provide comprehensive data through post marketing studies • Marketing authorisation reviewed every year until conditions fulfilled • Can only be granted for first marketing authorizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows market entry of drugs based on surrogate endpoint that is “reasonably likely” to predict clinical benefit (as opposed to validated surrogate endpoint) • Clinical benefit to be confirmed through post marketing trials • Can be granted for first and following indications of approved medicine
Eligibility criteria	Product must fulfil one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treat, prevent, or diagnose seriously debilitating or life-threatening diseases • Used in response to public health emergency situations • Are designated as orphan medical products 	Product must fulfil all the following : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address an unmet medical need in the treatment of a serious condition • Provide a meaningful advantage over available therapies (where a therapy exists) • Shown to be effective based on an endpoint “reasonably likely” to predict clinical benefit
Evidence assessment	Requires that four criteria are fulfilled : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive benefit-risk ratio is established • Manufacturer is likely to be able to provide additional data • Product fulfils an unmet medical need • Benefits to public health of immediate available of the product outweigh the risk of incomplete evidence 	Same requirements as for regular approval, albeit the evidence standard is different: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficacy can be demonstrated based on a surrogate endpoint that was determined to be “reasonably likely” to predict clinical benefit. • FDA <u>accepts that evidence will generally come from fewer, smaller, and shorter trials.</u>
Consequences for failure to comply with post marketing conditions	Assessment report by EMA, which can result in one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Letter to the company ▪ Oral explanation by the company ▪ Initiation of procedure to vary, suspend or revoke approval ▪ Inspection 	May result in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Withdrawal of approval ▪ Civil monetary penalties of up to US\$ 250.000

Hoekman, J. (2015) and Salcher-Konrad, M., et al (2020) also reviewed the key distinctions between the American and European approaches. They found that in both markets, decisions to pursue approval via the AA or CMA pathway are often made late in the process of bringing a drug to market. They constated that specially EMA seems to see it as a “*wait and see*” or “*rescue option*” to grant approval. Hoekman claimed CMA is not often used as a proactive planned pathway to obtain early access, suggesting companies need to use it more strategically as an early phase 2 submission, instead of later rescue option when phase 3 data is not strong enough. Some of the reasons are cited for this cautious mindset of companies in Europe, such as:

- “Always apply for full marketing authorization, as to avoid post marketing regulatory burden and increase chances of favourable assessment by reimbursement agencies”
- “Preferred certainty about regulatory procedures with the standard marketing authorization route”
- “Choose to file for full marketing authorization as safer bet”

In contrast, FDA is using AA more to its full potential. Their quantitative and qualitative analysis show US is using regulations to proactively influence the future of innovation in the therapeutic areas and promoting focus biomarkers development, while EMA seems more focused on an overall balanced risk/benefit.

It seems to exist some differences on the way the two agencies define the seriousness of the medical needs that can qualify for these pathways with EMA stating an “*Seriously debilitating or life-threatening diseases*” and FDA an “*Unmet medical need in treatment of a serious condition*”. The definition in EMA seems to go more in the direction of “life-expectancy” & “death-threat”, whereas in US seems to focus more on the fact there is “still no solution in the market” for a serious disease.

Definitely the major difference identified is the way the two agencies manage uncertainty, with FDA having a driving attitude to take risks and favor quicker access to new treatments, unlike EMA.

The fact that a global company needs to navigate these different geo regulatory requirements can put additional barriers for innovation on the design of global clinical trials and the access of innovative drugs to patients. There is a need to push for continuous regulatory bridges so that authorities across the world create a global robust framework for access to market of innovative therapies.

“Limited Approval” philosophy

Dhingra, K. (2015) challenged traditional drug development in Oncology, and developed a philosophy meant to go beyond the already existing AA and CMA regulatory pathways. Dhingra initially refers to it as “Limited Approval”, meant to be a flexible approach for novel targeted drugs based on limited initial clinical investigation. He defends when minimum criteria are fulfilled (a known drug target and mechanism of action, the ability to define a target population, no unusual toxicity in the clinic, etc.) a limited approval should be given. Translating in lower number of patients needed in initial trials than those typically required for AA/CMA, advocating for a stronger focus on biomarker evidence and PK/PD modeling correlations.

Dhingra viewpoint is such that the initial approval is “*not the end of investigation of the drug*” rather “*end of the beginning*”, expecting the first limited approval to be carefully restrained to a limited group of patients and with strong emphasis shifted to collecting real-life performance data, electronic medical records, and data mining analysis. This would mean faster knowledge evolution in post-marketing setting, that would require high agility from companies and regulators with regards to short label modifications, considering the ‘*drug approved label as a true living document*’. In such a model, data-driven flexibility for use of biomarkers for patient selection would be required. It would also require important Trade-off from stakeholders, with gains in terms of the time and money required to obtain first approval of a drug yet having strong commitment mechanisms to limit off-label. Therefore, requiring transparent collaboration across all development helixes. Dhingra defends the shift of the environment to this paradigm shall change the industry behavior and focus research on transformative drugs. Plus, fitting well with emerging pay-for-performance innovative models being adopted by payers.

“Adaptive Pathways” paradigm

Between 2014 and 2016 EMA explored similar concepts of innovative regulatory paradigms of the “limited approval” theory from Dhingra, K., launching a pilot project initially referred as “adaptive licensing” that was later renamed to “Adaptive pathways “. More precisely Medicines Adaptive Pathways to Patients (MAPP).

Fig 34 - Differences between existant CMA regulatory process and trial pilot concept of “Adaptive Pathways” of EMA

Dr Hans-Georg Eichler, EMA’s Senior Medical Officer, described the adaptive pathways concept as a response to problems which have long existed in medicines regulation but have grown more acute, the so-called access-versus-evidence conundrum, with conflicting tensions:

Fig 35 - Access versus Evidence conundrum (Adapted from Eichler, 2016)

The problem statement being how to find more innovative ways to handle increased uncertainty where real world treatment experience does not contribute to evidence generation of new innovative therapies.

- Light blue: patients treated with no active surveillance
- Yellow: patients in observational studies, registries
- Red: patients in Randomized Clinical Trials

Fig 36 - Conceptual model of transitioning the approval of medicines towards an adaptive licensing paradigm

In adaptive pathways concept, the real-world data starts appearing earlier between the initial license and full license. There is no abrupt decrease of Randomized Control Trials (RCTs) data

after license, instead there is a progressive and slow increase of patients treated in the first years. This had perceived benefit identified from these innovative pathways across different stakeholders:

Fig 37 - Potential benefits for different stakeholders from an adaptive drug approval (based on feedback from adaptive pathways pilot).

EMA’s adaptive pathways pilot was primarily meant to be a learning exercise and was closed in 2016, two years after it started. It provided valuable insights on opportunities to be seized, but also on barriers to overcome. There were 62 submitted drug proposals, 18 passed to Stage II, and 6 progressed to formal regulatory scientific advice. As expected, cancer drugs represented large part of those. The final report on the adaptive pathways pilot conveyed the approach could support medicine development, through fostering innovation in areas of public health high unmet need where design of randomised clinical trials is difficult (e.g., Alzheimer’s). Yet, most of the proposal did not completely fulfil the criteria for the pilot, and most of drugs ended up pursuing traditional regulatory routes. The key reasons for non-acceptance were: 1) development programs did not afford scope for expansion using real-world data; 2) proposals of areas where treatments already existed, thus reducing unmet need; 3) already in late stage of development and too late to make plan changes. The report from EMA showed some concerns of stakeholders in relaxing standards, and overall operational barriers to have the right mechanisms in place to define how to use real world data and make sure companies would comply to restrict use requirements once initial limited approval was granted. Raising the importance of strong involvement of patients and healthcare professional in the process. A main point of reflection was related to the limited thought given to value proposition, reimbursement strategies and the lack of involvement of payers in the pilot.

Finally, it was recognised the need for continued efforts to improve the access to medicines and ensure healthcare systems are sustainable and that requires innovative cultural changes on the industry ways of working:

Fig 38 - Cultural shift needed in order to shift industry’s paradigm to an adaptive development approach

2.2.3 Access & Pricing innovation

In the US, unlike in Europe, pharmaceutical firms can set prices for prescription medicines at whatever the market will bear. Even if the push for value-based pricing is slowly arriving to US, the prices in that market are still not fully tied to the “value of the drug”. Often the same drug is priced much higher in US than in peer nations (Waldrop, T. 2021).

In Europe once a drug is approved for marketing by the regulatory agency, Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies are responsible for modelling evidence (medical need, clinical efficacy, healthcare budget impact, etc.) that is used for pricing & reimbursement decision making by payers (such as the national health funds, health insurers, etc.).

Institute for Clinical and Economic Review (ICER) is an organisation founded in 2005 attempting to provide similar source of evidence free from conflict of interest for US. However, its price recommendations are seldom implemented (Kaltenboeck et al, 2020). Controversially, health economist Craig Garthwaite said in an interview to the Incidental Economist that he does not believe ICER is an independent organism, as a lot of funding comes from payer-based foundations and stated its goal as to lower spending in drugs. Garthwaite claims that on its own to be a bad goal, that should instead be a goal to focus on high-value spending (Bendicksen, L. 2020).

The term Market Access is commonly used in pharmaceutical industry to describe the process by which the product is made available and affordable for all patients for whom it was approved on its Marketing Authorisation by the respective country regulatory agency. For the pharmaceutical company, an ideal Market Access outcome generally means achieving an optimal price with maximum reimbursement for the regulatory approved population, however, in practise it's more about striking a fair balance between these variables:

Fig 39 - Three variables that need careful trade-off to obtain optimal Market Access of a new medicine. Source: self- created image based on literature from Toumi, M et al (2016)

For payers in pharmaceutical business, the concept of measuring the “*value for money*” of a drug, follows more the economics *subjective theory of value*. Meaning that is not determined by its inherent costs of good or production, but by the importance of their outcomes to the patients and the healthcare system, *based on payer’s subjective perception of a medical unmet need in society and how the therapy addresses that need* (Toumi, M et al., 2016). It is also important to understand that value-based Access is a concept that is broader than just value-based Pricing.

For example, in Oncology, the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) tries to assess the value of cancer therapies by calculating a Net Health Benefit scores using measures of clinical benefits demonstrated in the randomized clinical trials, often projecting the probability of overall survival at a certain time interval (ASCO Value Framework). The perception of the value of outcomes of a medicine can, however, differ depending on the stakeholders. MacEwan, J. et al (2019) suggested that there is sometimes a divergence between the meaningful of efficacy endpoints between clinicians and patients. While clinicians assume the value of surrogate endpoints, such as stable disease/Progression-Free Survival, only have value if they increase Overall Survival, patients demonstrate strong preference for longer periods of stable disease, even when no impact on Overall Survival.

Huber (2019) showed (Fig 40) that median price for oncology drugs approved in US, between 2009 and 2014, were higher for the ones approved with Tumour Response Rate surrogate endpoint, than Overall Survival.

Median yearly cost in the US of 51 new oncology drugs approved between 2009 and 2014 [3].		
Total oncology drugs approved by the FDA from 2009 to 2014	Primary endpoint for approval (% of total; N)	Median price per year of treatment
51	ORR (35%; 18)	\$137,952
	PFS (35%; 18)	\$102,677
	OS (30%; 15)	\$112,370

Fig 40 - Mean yearly price in US of 51 new oncology drugs per endpoints used between 2009 and 2014. Source: Huber (2019)

ORR (Overall Response Rate): measure that describes how tumour responded during therapy, often measured by change in its size through imaging techniques; PFS (Progression free survival): Length of time patient live without disease getting worse; OS (Overall Survival): Length of time from start of treatment that the patient are still alive

Mailankody, S. (2015) also did a similar analysis on US drug costs during 5-year period and found little difference between those approved on basis of time-to-event endpoints such as overall survival and those based on surrogate endpoints, such as tumour Response Rate, suggesting the price models were mostly reflecting what the market would bear.

Fig 41 - Linear regression analysis of Drug Price versus:

A) Surrogate endpoint Progression-free survival B) Overall survival clinical outcome. Source: Mailankody, S. (2015)

Vokinger, K. (2021) analysis of cancer drug pricing in US and EU, concluded that the launch prices were always higher in US, where they often increase faster than inflation. Vokinger found launch prices and post-launch prices increases were not associated with clinical benefit.

Redistributing risk & financing innovation via new pricing Strategies (focus US Market)

Pharmaceutical companies have been using different strategies to obtain a positive coverage decision at an optimal price, with a trend to move to dynamic models based on drug value supported by pertinent evidence. The more traditional strategies are merely based on financial agreements, such as volume discounts, patient assistance schemes, or even emerging financial risk-sharing schemes such as rebates.

The more innovative pricing models, start to follow Performance-Based Agreements (PBA) risk sharing approaches. These are schemes to enable outcomes-based pricing, where payers often use a warranty approach to agree to a price under the insurance that the product will deliver a predefined health outcome in a defined patient population (Simon, F., 2014).

Fig 42 - Redistributing reimbursement risk via new pricing solutions. Source: Simon, F., 2014

Two examples of PBA approaches are: Coverage with Evidence Development (CED), where the drug is reimbursed ('covered') only during limited period/setting with requirement to collect further evidence; and Pay for Performance (P4P), payors only pay for the drug if a prospectively agreed patient benefit is realized.

Coverage with Evidence Development (CED)

Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS), the largest government payors in the US, can opt to reimburse promising therapies under limited circumstances when cost-benefit of the drug is uncertain, and demand additional evidence to be developed to secure/expand coverage.

The point estimate of a drug cost-effectiveness may be within an accepted threshold (e.g., £30,000 per quality-adjusted life-year). But a high variability in the drug effectiveness data and/or cost could mean a high risk of the drug not being cost-effective, hence needing to collect more data to increase confidence in the decision for reimbursement.

Hutton, J. et al (2007) debated the criteria for therapies to be considered for CED, as adapted in the illustration 43 below:

Fig 43 - Illustrative representation of when to consider therapies suitable for CED approach. Horizontal axis represents the likely performance of the drug, and vertical the degree of uncertainty. Source: adapted from Hutton, J. (2007)

Based on the level of uncertainty and expected drug clinical benefit on the targeted patients, Hutton suggested three areas: beneath 0A when the drug should have direct full coverage, with a positive balance between expected benefit and the degree of uncertainty; between 0A and 0B when CED is recommended for those with potential benefit, but still some degree of uncertainty; and above 0B, where CED could be considered if tackling severe unmet need with limited alternative options for treatment.

When considering CED its important to use the conditional reimbursement in ways that strategically sponsor continuous drug development innovation. For example, making sure the requirements for additional data collection will not prevent optimal study designs that could reduce incentives for patients to participate in trials.

Pay for Performance (P4P)

When designing clinical trials, companies aim to enrich the study with patients who will more optimally respond to drugs, via protocol inclusion and exclusion criteria. This search for better clinical outcomes in a restricted patient population, may also be allied with an opportunity for a drug premium price. In fact, the model of smaller targeted populations with differentiated health outcomes has been compensated with premium prices (seen in the space of rare diseases, precision oncology, gene therapies, etc.) versus an older pharma model that chased big volumes at the sacrifice of clinical differentiation.

Huber (2019) recognises that simple focus on cost is too simplistic for this industry, pointing to the delicate balance existing between giving patients access to potential clinical valuable new drugs, but also the financing of the healthcare system through payers reimbursements. Simplistic pricing discounts cannot be the appropriate solution for such complex environment, where all players aim to foster innovation to market, while ensuring the right drugs are used in right patient population (Gronde, 2017).

On the other hand, P4P approaches allow the needed flexibility to bring some inherent uncertainty to the market yet pull the system to focus on medical value instead of volume.

In this model, should a treatment not achieve expected efficacy in the real world, companies could reimburse the Payers and Patients for the costs of first treatment cycles. This thus incentivises a drug development innovation that maximises a personalised number of respondent patients, rather than simply maximizing the number of patients treated. In value-based Access is important also to use “Prior Authorization Requirements” at the right balance. These are mechanisms that require pre-approval from payers, such as health insurances, before the care is prescribed and covered. This can limit coverage when prescribed for indications where there is still insufficient supporting evidence, which could be positive to limit payer’s budget in patients where cost-effectiveness is not guaranteed, and at the same time allow the flexibility to ask for it when patients have no other alternatives while generating real-world knowledge.

There are barriers on implementation of these models, as described by the Chief Medical Officer of Express Scripts, Dr. Steve Miller *“industry has seen multiple attempts at outcomes-based reimbursement, but most have collapsed under their own weigh”*. One blocking point in US being their structuring between the company and a specific payer, and difficult to expand to additional payers and broadly accelerate a shift to value-based reimbursement (Ornstein, C., 2017).

Value-Based Pricing: the price of innovation & healthcare sustainability

Most authors in health economics agree that one of the main goals of developing and marketing medicines is to improve overall population health and incentivise focus on societal priorities, using for that metrics that estimate the years of full health gain from an intervention, such as quality-adjusted life years (QALYs). To give perspective on this concept, we could think of a gene therapy for inherited disease that results in vision loss. If target is set to achieve a cost of \$150,000 per QALY gained and the value-based price of the treatment would be \$217 for children aged 3–15 years, for children for children < 3 years it could increase to \$482 (Kaltenboeck et al, 2020). Also, for very rare disease with small pool of patients eligible for treatment, normally there is greater willingness from governments to pay higher prices as incentive for investing in developing drugs for small patient populations.

Dr Peter Bach, active physician in the field of health policy, contrasts the concepts of value ceiling and price ceiling. He defends putting price controls on drugs can have negative consequences as pharma might abandoned riskier research. However, setting a value ceiling, like \$150K per QALY, can be a good target, as if we start going for more than that, payers might not have money to pay for other areas of value. Given the example of much seen investment in oncology, and lack of development of drugs in other severe diseases because of the lack of value ceiling rewards (Bendicksen, L. 2020).

The main challenge of a Value-based pricing (VBP) model is to balance the right level of pricing incentives with the sustainability of the whole healthcare system. Moreno, S. (2019) defends this approach ultimately leads to win-win outcomes for the whole pharmaceutical ecosystem as payers have the mechanisms to signal what are the priorities in healthcare, while incentivising the industry to focus on meaningful innovation.

Fig 44 – Self-created figure representing the challenges of VBP. Source: based on insights from Moreno,S. (2019)

The main point for controversy arises from how the payer's gotten to define drug's therapeutic value (Angelis A, et al, 2017). To tackle this, Moreno (2019) defends that is fundamental to remove any ambiguity around the 'value framework' used by payers, as they signal the preferred type of medicine innovation, whether prioritising specific areas of medical need or gain in patients' quality-adjusted life years. He argues further on the importance of clarification of value frameworks to offer some level of certainty to the industry that its innovation efforts are done in the right direction and could generate therapeutic value and gain premium price. And ultimately reasoning that predictable price frameworks and market conditions are a key driver to foster innovation against cancer.

The Market Access context can become especially complex in cases of regulatory Accelerated Approvals with the use of surrogate biomarkers that are reasonably likely, but not yet fully proven, to translate in clinical benefit outcomes in the target population. However, even for AA, payers would like to see stronger correlations between surrogate endpoint and the clinical benefit to get a positive pricing & reimbursement consideration (Kaaniche, A., 2015). Which brings us to a "chicken and egg" conundrum, as the primary goal of AA is to allow more balanced risk of opportunity of earlier access for innovative therapeutics in areas of great unmet need, for which the correlation with a full clinical benefit is not yet established.

It is important to consider that two-thirds of cancer drugs have their regulatory approval based on surrogate endpoints (Lakdawalla, D. et al, 2017). Anderson, M. (2022) defends the importance for payers to use innovative models that grant positive recommendations to novel medicines based on yet uncertain evidence, combined with stronger monitoring of real-world efficacy, with potential value-based triggers for price renegotiations. Some examples of this are already successfully seen in US, however an assessment done by Cherla, A. et al (2021) found that many cancer drug indications that received accelerated approvals in US, are later denied by European payors due to uncertain evidence from unvalidated surrogate measures which were the basis for US regulatory approval. This confirms the more stringent and risk adverse approach of Europe versus US payors, as already seen in the regulators.

2.2.4 Investment and Shareholder value

At Institute of Medicine (IOM) conference, when venture capitalists were surveyed about which therapeutic areas in life sciences offered most promising investment opportunities, Oncology was largely seen as the best opportunities, whereas Neurodegenerations diseases fell significantly behind, with only 8 percent of investors viewing the field favourably (IOM, Washington, 2014).

Investors often value a firm by its market capitalization, which fluctuates depending on the total number of outstanding shares multiplied by their stock market price. In biopharmaceutical industry, the share price is known to oscillate over time depending on the expected profitability of the portfolio, with companies competing for investor by offering returns with share price gains. These fluctuations are often interpreted by shareholders as indicator of the company's innovation potential (Rothenstein, J., 2011). Investors in this industry are very sensible to company news related to products regulatory approval, being often more volatile to negative than positive news (De Schrijver, J., 2013; Mahlich, J. et al, 2021).

Moreno, S. (2019) argues that the sustainability of biopharmaceutical industry is dependent on continuously maintaining an attractive Return on Investment (RoI) to avoid their prospective shareholders to prioritise other more lucrative industries and risking to diminish the influx of investment needed to fund R&D innovation. He considers that when there is high uncertainty about the future pipeline innovation, the companies may tend to concentrate efforts in maximizing profits from existing products. Especially considering that the cost of bringing an innovative new drug to market has more than tripled in the past years, due to the requirements of long Randomized Clinical Trials (RCTs) (Serkaya, A., 2016). Thus, defending that improving profit predictability of future innovation is key to ensure companies can practise value-based innovation. This way of thinking could even be more intensified in venture capital firms, that use investment funds to try to generate high returns. Even if some venture capital people in biotech are certainly driven by the mission of developing new innovative drugs, the investors providing the actual capital are often not tied to biopharma as a sector. In this environment the volatility can be even higher than the traditional ecosystem where big pharma dominates the early R&D.

The tension between Innovation and Financialization

Unlike the neoclassical view where a company's goal is profit maximization, Lazonick, W. (2013) theory of Innovative Enterprise defends it is instead to "transform technologies, access markets and generate products better than those previously available".

Tulum, O. et al (2019) applied this theory to analyse the tension between *innovation* and *financialization* of pharmaceutical companies operating in the US and suggested that there is a productivity problem on innovation in this industry. Tulum points the highly financialized business model driven by the ideology of maximising shareholder value as the root cause for the problem. In fact, the author argues that shareholders are the ones that contribute the least to the enterprise value-creation process, but yet the ones with bigger power to extract its value. To better navigate the challenges of innovation the industry needs more Innovative Enterprises, governed in a way that make best use of the rich innovation ecosystem that exists in the US. These enterprises make decisions that are driven to create value for shareholders and all other stakeholders, including the broader society. And do that by combining strategic control, organisational integration, and financial commitment (Fig 45):

Fig 45 - Concept of how Innovative Enterprises best tackle innovation. Source: self-created based on Tulum, O. et al (2019)

Underinvestment from private firms in innovative long-term research

Using evidence from oncology clinical trials, Budish, E. et al (2015) showed that private firms invest more in late-stage cancer drugs and little in early-stage and cancer preventive drugs that require longer time to bring to market. “Short-termism” and “fixed patent term” were two of the potential causes identified as drivers for private companies to move away from long-term research investment.

It is known how clinical trials for chronic diseases can be extremely long and expensive. Depending on disease progression, more observation time is needed to detect significant differences in treatment outcomes (such as mortality). Surrogate endpoints, as controversial as they can be, are a strategic tool to dramatically reduce the length of the trial.

Fig 46 – Data on historical funding of oncology clinical trials from 1973 to 2011. Source: Budish, E. et al, 2015

Presents the cumulative distribution functions (CDF) of clinical trial lengths for privately financed and publicly financed trials.

The privately financed CDF lies above the publicly financed CDF at almost every clinical trial length.

The vertical line at 20 years denotes that the patent system should offer zero incentive to develop drug compounds that take longer than 20 years to develop.

Of the few trial taking longer than 20 years, essentially 100 percent are publicly funded.

TABLE 5—HISTORICAL CASE STUDIES OF FDA-APPROVED CHEMOPREVENTION DRUGS

	Approval indication	Surrogate endpoint used?	Primarily publicly funded?
BCG (Bacillus Calmette-Guérin)	bladder carcinoma in situ	no	yes
Diclofenac	squamous cell carcinomas	yes	no
Celecoxib	familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP)-related cancers	yes	no
Photofrin	esophageal carcinoma	yes	no
Tamoxifen	breast cancer	no	yes
Cervical cancer vaccines	cervical cancer	yes	no

Approved Chemo Preventive drugs that help lower person's risk of developing cancer.

Table illustrates that that all **six oncology preventive drugs approved** at the time, **either relied on the use of surrogate endpoints, or were approved based on publicly financed clinical trials.**

This confirms there is need for policy strategies that help maximise private investment in innovate R&D drugs and social welfare. Budish showed that policies such as: the start of patent clock at commercialization, more push subsidies for programs with long commercialisation lags, and allowing companies to rely more on surrogate endpoints could be some of these strategies. To support the last hypothesis, it was analysed how longer commercialization lags for US cancer patients diagnosed in 2003 and resulted in almost 900 000 lost life-years, which were valued at \$100,000, and thus estimating a social value of the life-years lost in this cohort of patients of around 90 billion per year.

Small biotechnology start-ups, which often have only a single research project, are more likely to continue to invest funds to progress development from Phase1 to Phase2, even when prospects are relatively dim. However, this does not mean that they will be more successful in Phase2/Phase3 than more mature companies. In fact, Comanor, W. (2010) showed it could be quite the opposite. Companies with bigger portfolio often have broader range of projects to invest and solid processes in place to ask the right questions early on development that allow to properly gauge investment risk. Nevertheless, the secret for the innovation ecosystem to thrive might be on the synergic collaboration between the different cultural approaches from different types/sizes of companies, balancing the right level of efficiency and risk taking.

Market reactions to announcements of drug approvals

Literature shows that drug approvals from regulatory Agencies heavily affect companies stock prices, especially for smaller companies (De Schrijver, J.,2013). After all, agencies decide whether the investment are allowed to generate revenue or not (even if the exact amount of revenue also depends on further payer negotiations on pricing & reimbursement). These approvals can be a live or death sentence for smaller clinical stage companies that have only one or two drugs in the

pipeline and are betting everything on their successful approvals to attract investment or be acquired by bigger pharma. Literature also shown that the magnitude of a negative reaction from the market tends to be larger than the positive reaction (Sarkar, S., 2006). And that increased media presence and a high level of mediatic attention on a specific drug/company generate additional trading volume (Himmelmann, A. and D. Schiereck., 2012).

A positive Phase II trial is a major value creation event taking a lot of uncertainty about future earnings of a product, and risk for share price volatility. Yet a small biotech company with a single product who files at the regulatory agency even after successful phase III still has on average 10%-20% of product being rejected (De Schrijver, J., 2013).

Studies from Rothenstein et al (2011) on the public announcements of regulatory approvals and clinical trials results, describe that the average stock price from 60 days before the actual announcement day was positive for positive regulatory decisions and negative for negative decisions, giving insider trading as the most likely explanation for the stock price anticipation. Literature also show that clinical trials results are more prone for insider trading as there is more people involved and thus higher changes of leakage. In fact, people that are aware of results before they are made public, including company employees, researchers and agency staff are often paid by investment firms to provide 'expert opinions' which are then used by these firms to take trading positions while the non-public information is not yet reflected in the market but expected to move in that direction (Steinbrook, 2005). Whereas decisions made by the regulatory agencies are taken relatively quick by a small group of people.

There are also described differences in the way the market reacts to approval announcements depending on which market the companies are listed. Stocks of companies listed in NASDAQ seems to react more than the ones listed in NYSE (De Schrijver, J.,2013). This being explained by the fact that companies listed in NYSE are often larger and with more products already in the market and new announcements affecting less their profits. These companies also constantly report on new products under development and as consequence the distribution of daily returns in previous window might already contain event-driven returns, which makes it more difficult that FDA announcement come as a shock and identify extreme returns. On the other hand, companies listed in NASDAQ, known for its high-tech stocks, often shown exceptional daily returns with positive FDA announcements resulting in very positive daily returns and negative announcements in very negative daily returns.

Literature findings from J. Donavon (2018) suggested the type of disease (for example if cancer or neurology) has little impact level of market returns in an event of a successful new approval. However, the fact that is a more novel application type, i.e., completely new molecule, completely new MoA, etc. have a positive effect on returns. Market rewards novelty, it just happened that in the past decades oncology brought more novelty to the market than neurodegeneration. But certainly, the arrival of the first disease modifying therapies in neurodegeneration shall bring similar market responses as the arrival of immunotherapy did in oncology some decades ago.

One could speculate that the market would react more to announcements of accelerated approvals as by design they are meant bring more novelty to the market than a traditional approval. On the other hand, as they have post-marketing commitments that if not fulfilled could make them withdraw from market, this could add more uncertainty to the investors. As I did not find any published literature specifically comparing the market returns in communications of accelerated versus full approvals, I cannot confirm which of the hypothesis is more plausible.

3. Methodology

To design my research method for this project I have used the research onion model presented by Saunders et al (see Fig 47):

Fig 47 - Signalled in red the design followed for this project according to Research Onion model from Saunders et al (2007)

Philosophy

The existent different types of evidence (scientific and social) related to the use of accelerated pathways in drug development from the angles of different stakeholders and how it correlates to innovation in the biopharmaceutical industry could be viewed as an “objective reality”.

In this project an interpretivist research philosophy has been applied, with an ontological view of knowledge as subjective to interpretation depending on the stakeholders social/cultural/business constraints.

Research Approach

This project follows partially an Inductive approach, starting from literature review to research questions. The different type of data collected is used to make sense of the patterns that come out of the analysis, to ultimately formulate and propose new hypothesis, framework models or recommendations. It also has some deductive components, as in the beginning of the project some high-level hypotheses are formulated from the literature review, oncology Quantative data and Alzheimer’s drugs case studies. These are further assessed against the final qualitative data collected from Stakeholders interviews, through qualitative analysis.

Research Strategy

From the deductive approach, the literature review and some of quantitative data collected makes it possible to formulate some initial hypothesis to test if some of those can explain the best strategies to adopt accelerated pathways in neurodegeneration drug development ecosystem.

For the inductive part I will use grounded theory strategy, meaning that data collection starts without the formation of an initial theoretical framework, and it is used to inform and explore the development of new suppositions and recommendations. The case study research is also analysed to gain in-depth understanding of issues in a real-life setting.

Research Methods

Mixed method using two types of quantitative and qualitative research data. However doing mainly qualitative analysis.

Quantitative Data Oncology (<i>US data</i>)		
Clinical data & Regulatory pathway	Pricing & Access	Investment and Shareholder value
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FDA list of AA vs full approval conversion, per oncology indication and endpoint used 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oncology drug prices at the time of AA vs full approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cumulated Abnormal returns (CARs) of oncology company's stocks at AA vs full approval announcements
Qualitative Data Oncology and translation to Alzheimers' case studies		
Case Studies	Aduhelm & amyloids drugs (first disease modifying drugs) approved in Alzheimer's Disease <i>Geo scope of data focused on US</i>	
Interviews	Ecosystem Senior Stakeholders with expertise across Oncology and Neurodegeneration (Clinical development, Regulatory, Pricing & Acces, Executives & Investors)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Semi-structured interviews (N=8) 	

Time Horizons

Cross-sectional approach was used since it provides a snapshot of the status of drug development literature, oncology quantitative data and interviews done to ecosystem stakeholders just in a single point in time.

Research Techniques and procedures

Where it is necessary to understand reasons for stakeholders opinions, Saunders (2007) recommends conducting qualitative interview (semi-structured and in-depth, unstructured interviews). This provides the researcher the opportunity to "probe" answer, where the interviewees need to further explain their responses.

A part of my interviews was structured based on the formulated hypothesis and theories. However, part of the structure was also adapted during the interview, and depending on area of expertise of the interviewee, the content of discussion dived towards how they see the challenges in neurodegeneration drug development. This unstructured part was very important to be able to understand the subjective perceptions of the different intermediaries.

I used some of the hypothesis formulated based on oncology literature and collective quantitative data to probe the interviewees, and test how they perceive the challenges to adopt Oncology strategies to neurodegeneration space. The recent case studies on Alzheimer's drugs were the

perfect real-world exercise to get deeper on their perception of what should be done better. These interviews were done during Q1 2023 when lot of pivotal events of these cases were just unfolding, so this prompt an even deeper case-based discussion.

To organise the primary data, I used existent background hypothesis and theories. By using this research approach, my own perceptions also played a role in the research process. The questions I selected, the way I formulate them and finally the way I interpret the material from the interviews and correlate it with the broader background data will affect the results to some extent.

Quantitative Data Sampling

Regulatory data

Consulted from FDA website table of all new drugs and biologics applications based on surrogate approvals available as of September 30, 2022.

The table describes the information about when the company applied for AA, when AA was approved and when it was converted to full approval or withdrawn. It also provided the dossier reference for searching the details of endpoints used for each AA, and the post-market commitments.

FDA table had initially 286 raw data points. The approvals related to Oncology were filtered. From those, I excluded the ones where surrogated endpoints were not found. The products of companies not publicly listed on the stock market were also excluded for the final data collection.

Pricing data

The analytical database tool of drug pricing, *AnalySource*, was used for pricing data collection. From each drug its Wholesale Acquisition Cost (WAC) unit price at year of drug Accelerated Approval, and at conversion to drug full approval were collected. To be more precise, the higher registered price that year, at least one month, after the accelerated or full approval were searched.

As the full approval typical happens several years after the accelerated approval, there is a natural contribution of inflation in the price increase of the drug. To discount the contribution of inflation considering

Drug accelerated approval PRICE A at YEAR X → Drug full approval PRICE B at YEAR Y

It was calculated what would be the PRICE A at YEAR Y with the natural inflation (PRICE C). For that it was used the CPI inflation calculator tool from the US Bureau of labour statistics website: https://www.bls.gov/data/inflation_calculator.htm

Then I subtracted the PRICE C to the PRICE B, to have the amount of “real” price change of the drug from its accelerated to full approval. To calculate the % of price increase I divided the amount of price change by the initial PRICE A.

Stocks data

To quantify how the market reacted to the announcements of both accelerated and full approval the used Cumulated Abnormal Returns (CAR) concept was used. CAR describes the value gained

from a company stock at a given time period, considered the relationship of the market as a whole and the stock's actual value.

I used *yahoo finances* historical data to extract the data and make, for each drug, the following:

- Calculated the stock daily returns of the company on the day the approvals were announced (DAY 1), in the following manner:

$$\text{Daily returns} = \text{Adj close for DAY 1} - \text{Adj close DAY 0}$$

- The same formula was used to calculate the company stock daily returns for the day accelerated approval and full approval were communicated.
- *Vanguard 500 index fund* was used as a proxy for the whole market daily returns, representing the natural macro volatility.

Finally, the CAR was calculated for each drug, for both the accelerated and full approval moments:

$$\text{CAR} = \text{Company stock daily returns} - \text{Vanguard daily returns}$$

Companies were categorised in groups such as being Fortune 500 (Y/N), or in which stock market were listed (NYSE vs NASDAQ).

Qualitative Data Sampling

Selection of Case Studies

The literature section explores several authors' reviews on oncology development cases. These provide perspective on innovative drug development approaches championed within oncology environment, that allowed to build the initial hypothesis background of this project.

Then the recent Alzheimer cases of Aduhelm & three follow-on drugs were selected. These are very rich case studies with fresh real-life examples of some of the pains and success of trying to disrupt an ecosystem that was stagnated for decades.

Selection of stakeholders for interviews

The main criteria for the selection of the interviewees were to make sure I had a panel with diverse angles of expertise, from different organisations, seen as reference in their field, with high seniority, and that could provide high level of critical thinking to the topic.

All the people interviewed were senior leaders in their field of drug development. Their areas ranged from clinical development and regulatory affairs, access & pricing, industry strategists, executives & investors. They were based in different locations namely US, UK, Belgium, and Switzerland, and all working for global organisations. These organisations were biopharmaceutical companies but also strategic consultancy agencies and clinical universities. In total 8 people were interviewed. I did not interview anyone that was directly employed by a regulatory agency at the time of this project.

Materials

The interviewees were approached through LinkedIn or by internal company contact. The participant information leaflet shared in advance with the interviewees, as well as participant consent form, that was further collected signed by each participant before the interview. The names of participants were categorised and anonymised following ethics and compliance form.

All subjects were interviewed through 30-45min MS Teams video call that was being audio recorded and automatically transcribed by MS Teams.

Data Analysis

The analysis was a mix of relying on the theoretical propositions to focus attention on certain data and ignore less relevant aspects, plus the use of Gioia methodology of grouping common themes that are supported by observation and packing key priorities for further new analysis and recommendations.

4. Findings

4.1 Quantitative data on Oncology

Quantitative data was collected from drug Accelerated Approvals (AA) and respective conversion to Full Approval (FA) in US market, as well as related pricing and market response at the two events (see details in methodology section).

This data was gathered with aim to provide further insight on the establishment of AA in Oncology, namely, to better understand the impact of this pathway on companies' shareholders and how these learnings could later be translated to inform strategic decision-making of neurodegeneration development programs. This data also allow to test some of the hypothesis found on the literature review.

Figures below describes the filters and amount of data collected:

Fig 48 - Visual representation of filters applied and amount of Quantative data collected in this project

According to FDA list (consulted as of September 2022) there were 166 drugs with indications in Oncology approved through Accelerated Approval between 1995 and 2022. From these, 60 had already been converted to Full Approval and 23 withdrawn.

Fig 49 - Status of Oncology Accelerated Approval applications extracted from FDA database (as of Sep 2022)

Timelines on conversion from AA to Full Approval

This review is focused on the drugs that were already converted (N=60).

Data collected shows that:

- Takes on average 7 months to receive an Accelerated Approval from the time of FDA application received.
- Once the drug received the accelerated approval, takes on average 47 months, or approximately 4 years, to be converted to full approval.

Fig 50 - Graph Overview of all cases (N=60) with the time it took to get accelerated approval (blue) and then until conversion into full approval (red)

The 4 years of distance between AA and FA represents the typical time that patients could already have had earlier access to the drug based on controlled risks, while industry starts generating clinical evidence of the drug behavior in the real world and initial revenues.

Data seems to show a trend of conversion from AA to Full approval to have become slightly faster over time.

Drug prices at the time of AA vs FA

The focus for the price observations were the 60 cases of conversion from AA to Full Approval and how prices changed from one to the other. As described in the methodology section, the *WAC unit price* for each drug in US Market was collected at *AnalySource* at the two time points, and the increase that is due to inflation was subtracted.

Overall,

- 50 out of 60 cases observed, more than 83%, show an increase of price from accelerated to full approval.
- On average the **prices at the time of FA augmented 26% more than initial AA price**, an average of **\$102 more** (per WAC unit price).

Fig 51 - Percentage of price variation (N=60): from initial price at the time of accelerated approval to the price when it was converted to full approval (inflation contribution excluded). Used WAC unit price. Blue dots: price increase. Orange dots: price maintained or slightly decrease.

Fig 52 - Amount of variation in US dollars \$ (N=60): from initial price at the time of accelerated approval to the price when it was converted to full approval (inflation contribution excluded). Used WAC unit price. Orange dots: price maintained or slightly decrease.

No significant correlation was observed between the price and type of surrogate endpoint used. However, data seems to show a slight trend to reduce the % of price increase over time, with few cases of price reduction in the last decade.

Companies' stocks response to AA vs FA announcements

There is literature showing regulatory Agencies approvals heavily affect companies stock prices, especially for smaller companies (De Schrijver, J.,2013). However, there is a Gap in the published literature as no papers were found that compare how the market responded to AA versus FA approval communications. To investigate this, among the 60 cases of AA converted to FA from FDA list, 40 that had their company publicly listed on the stock market were used (See methodology sections for details on CARs calculation).

Fig 53 - Overview of data from companies' CARs (N=40) on the day of announcement of Accelerated Approvals (blue) vs day of announcement of conversion to Full Approval (red) for a same given drug (each two dots for the same drug on the same vertical line)

Overall data seems quite disperse on the way the market reacts to communications of drugs accelerated approval versus its conversion to full approval. However, if looked more in depth:

- Data shows a trend of market reacting more positively to the Accelerated Approvals than to its later conversion to Full Approvals, with a total avg of CARs for AA of 0.4 and avg CARs for FA of -0.1.
- It was not observed a significant change on how the market reacted to announcements when using Forbes 500 as distinction criteria (assuming this criterion would be a proxy for company size). However, both smaller and bigger companies clearly react more positively to AA announcements.

Averages	F500 yes		F500 no	
	CARs AA	CARs FA	CARs AA	CARs FA
	0,38	-0,12	0,30	0,11

- Few variations noticed on Market CARs on the day of AA depending on endpoint used. Average CARs slightly higher for AA where primary endpoint was PFS (0.6) compared to Tumor response rate (0.37). Only one AA had already OS data on its AA (which is very uncommon) and interestingly its CARs was of -0,15. Even though these amounts of data do not allow to take statistically significant conclusions, still raise interesting reflections/hypothesis.

		AA CARs
28 average	RR	0,37
11 average	PFS	0,57
Only one	OS	-0,15

Stocks of companies listed in NASDAQ seem to react more to FDA approvals than the ones listed in NYSE (De Schrijver, J.,2013). This being explained by the fact that companies listed in NYSE

are often larger and with more products already in the market and new announcements affecting less their profits

The data collected in this project seems to confirm the literature work from De Schrijver (2013), showing that NASDAQ companies seem to respond more to the announcements, specially more positively to the accelerated approval announcements, than the ones in NYSE. In some way, this also confirms the hypothesis that smaller companies react more to Agencies announcements, as NYSE companies are often larger.

Fig 54 - Overview of data from companies' CARs split per companies listed in NASDAQ versus NYSE.

Overall Companies (NASDAQ + NYSE)
 Avg CARs AA: 0.34 / Avg CARs FA: -0.04

NASDAQ Companies
 Avg CARs AA: **0.70** / Avg CARs FA: 0.11

NYSE Companies
 Avg CARs AA: **0.21** / Avg CARs FA: -0.10

4.2 Alzheimer’s Case studies

Case study overview

Aducanumab is an anti-beta amyloid antibody drug from Biogen, also known by the commercial name Aduhelm. It was the first Disease Modifying Therapy (DMTs) approved under the FDA accelerated approval pathway in June 2021 for Alzheimer’s Disease (AD).

Fig 55 - Self-created timeline overview of key chronological events related to the approvals of the first disease modifying therapies in Alzheimer’s disease

Biogen initially went for a “full traditional development” strategy, aiming for a full approval with two Phase 3 studies, called ENGAGE and EMERGE, which had conflicting results. EMERGE met its primary endpoint, while ENGAGE did not present statistically significant change in clinical scales.

By 6th November 2020 FDA had a meeting with external advisory committee to discuss ongoing data of the different clinical studies, where the committee (info from public company statements):

Questions at FDA table	Votes from FDA external Advisory Committee
“Does the study EMERGE viewed independently of ENGAGE provide strong evidence that supports effectiveness of aducanumab for treatment of AD?”	1 yes, 8 no and 2 uncertain
“Does Study 103 (PRIME) provide supportive evidence of the effectiveness of aducanumab for the treatment of Alzheimer’s disease?”	0 yes, 7 no and 4 uncertain
“Has the Applicant presented strong evidence of a pharmacodynamic effect of aducanumab on Alzheimer’s disease pathophysiology?”	5 yes, 0 no and 6 uncertain
“In light of the understanding provided by the exploratory analyses of Study EMERGE (Ph3) and Study ENGAGE (Ph3), along with the results of PRIME study (Ph1b) and evidence of a pharmacodynamic effect on Alzheimer’s disease pathophysiology, it is reasonable to consider EMERGE study as primary evidence of effectiveness of aducanumab for the treatment of Alzheimer’s disease?”	0 yes, 10 no and 1 uncertain

Even if the external Advisory Committees provides FDA with non-binding recommendations, with the opinions expressed being so negative, most thought the chances of Biogen getting an approval were quite low. Despite the odds, Biogen went back to analyse the data of its two Ph3 studies together with its previous phase 1b study, PRIME. According to their new analysis considering subpopulations and different dosing, the drug was later granted accelerated approval in June 2021, instead of the full approval the company was initially strategizing for.

Criticality: Could the strategy have been different? For example, planning early by design for an accelerated approval with Ph2 studies, while having by that time Phase 3 trials ongoing - strengthening the surrogate/clinical outcomes link. And incorporate the feedback received from authorities from AA in Ph3 for traditional approval while the product was already marketed under AA.

This was the case for Lecanemab, that will be later analysed. This is also a development strategy that is often seen in Oncology.

This was the first FDA accelerated approval in this field based on a combination of Ph1 and Ph3 data and using a biomarker, reduction of beta amyloid plaques, as reasonably likely surrogate endpoint for the traditional scales assessing clinical decline. This historical approval brought for the first time a surrogate endpoint in Neurodegeneration to the FDA list of potential use for Accelerated Approval pathways. This supported the mechanistic hypothesis of the progress of Alzheimer's Disease being directly linked with the accumulation of beta amyloid plaques in the brain.

Fig 56 - Effect of anti-amyloid antibodies, illustration of hypothetical relationship between amyloid removal and consequent amelioration of cognitive decline, the basis for using removal of amyloid plaques as a surrogate endpoint. Source: E., Karren (2022)

This approval saw conflicting stakeholders with different positions, like no other. On a scientific side, we see pioneer approach in the field of basing an approval on surrogate biomarkers, and a questionable risk benefit assessment. This, of course, divided the scientific community.

But the complexity of stakeholders involved in such type of decisions, goes much broader than scientific community, with the policy makers, the payors, the industry, the patients' organisations,

the media, and the society in general. Coronavirus 2019 pandemic already showed us that scientific disputes are often viewed through ideological lens and as pointed out by Gusmano, K. (2022) “the calls for lowering evidentiary standards when allowing new health innovations on the market and using public money to purchase them, may have greater resonance when emphasize the contribution of this innovation to economic growth”.

Unprecedented regulatory scene

Choices surrounding the approval of new drugs like Aduhelm, will never be a purely scientific matter, as they touch on very sensible points of society goals and what it is considered as being fair. These decisions set the tone of how values and interests shape the way evidence is treated. They expose fine tensions between those values and the type of innovation and societal issues prioritised, a lot of what politics is about (Gusmano, K.,2022).

Some stakeholders and experts in the environment saw Aduhelm as a positive controversy in the field, as breakthrough boosting the interest of investors in the field and the hopes for the people suffering from the condition. FDA as a key agent kicking doors and fostering innovation in the area, seen by increased abundance of research and development work in neurodegenerative diseases. As stated by Sabbagh MN (2019) on a peer commentary on the aducanumab trials results:

“Approval of aducanumab would represent the beginning of the modern treatment era for AD similarly stimulating the field as was seen with statins, HIV treatments AND Oncology”

“This is not a cure but the first incremental step in transforming the disease from an untreatable terminal illness to a manageable chronic disease. Advancing aducanumab forward toward approval could pave the way for other monoclonal antibodies and therapeutic interventions. We believe the data are sufficient to warrant approval with Phase 4 surveillance.”

One could argue that FDA accelerated approval is just being here to its fullest potential of allowing more shared risk among the different stakeholders in the ecosystem, trying to provide earlier access in potential valuable therapies where despite the uncertain benefit there is some expectation of clinical benefit.

FDA assumptions relationale for Aduhelm Accelerated Approval (AA)	
<p>Pathophysiological Hypothesis: Amyloid plaque accumulation is directly linked with progression of Alzheimer’s Disease</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Amyloid plaque is an underlying, fundamental, and defining pathophysiological feature of the disease ▪ Presence of amyloid plaques is a primary and essential finding in AD
<p>Risk-benefit based on available evidence and environmental context: Severity of disease, unmet need, and available data, makes its reasonable to accept accelerated approval based on a biomarker likely thought to be a surrogate of clinical progress of disease</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It is reasonable to conduct that treatment that is targeted at reducing amyloid plaque, and that successfully accomplishes that reduction, has the potential to convey clinical benefit ▪ Data of Ph1b study together with other two Ph3 provide convincing evidence for treatment-related reduction in brain amyloid beta plaque as measured by PET imaging ▪ Overall finding supports reasonable likelihood that reduction in Anti Beta plaques by aducanumab predicts clinical benefit ▪ Sub-analysis also considered multi compounds data targeting amyloid plaque and its relationship with clinical outcomes as cumulated evidence. ▪ FDA was also using the clin pharm modelling to make the link between beta plaques reductions and Clinical scales – using data from other assets, so from an asset agnostic perspective!

Biogen recognised Aduhelm dataset was complex and did not follow a conventional path, as the road to innovation is rarely straightforward”.

What added controversy on the regulatory side was the fact that most of the external advisory committee members of FDA voted “No” to approve the drug, considering the surrogate endpoint not to be fully linked with clinical endpoints. Nevertheless, FDA used the reasonable likelihood assumption to approve the drug.

The only member of the external advisory committee that found that the single study’s evidence was convincing was the committee chairman, Dr. Nathan Fountain, a professor of neurology at the University of Virginia. *“I think there are lots of small issues with it, but the trends, I think, are all in the right direction,”* he said. However, to mark their disagreement, three members of the external advisory committee quit their functions after the drug was approved. This made the media put additional fire to the already controversial approval.

Factors related to the regulatory approval that escalated criticism	Critical perspective / contra-arguments
The fact that the biomarker used (PET tracer) was not approved for measuring treatment outcomes in clinical setting.	Given that this was a first ever approval, based on “reasonable likely” validated surrogates, and that for full validation it would require epidemiological real-world data; expecting this biomarker to already be fully validated would seem contradictory to the primary goal of AAs.
The “disregard” of one of the Phase 3 trials that showed no clinical efficacy on clinical scales.	Was deemed data was initially not enough for full approval. Hence Biogen went back to re-analyse phase 1b data together with the full metadata perspective and came with a different patients stratification strategy. Showing a potential signal that could suffice for accelerated approval but would need further post-marketing commitments in order to allow a full approval. Had this strategy been thought by design since the beginning
<p>Approval with very broad label</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Labelling miss-match issue: The FDA approved the drug for all Alzheimer's patients totalling more than 6 million people in the U.S., even though the drug was only studied in patients with early disease. ▪ Treatment duration: The agency also didn't place a limit on treatment duration, suggesting patients could stay on Aduhelm <i>“until either all plaque is removed, or the patient progresses.</i> Under that label, the Aduhelm monthly IV infusion has millions of patients to target, and they could all take the drug indefinitely. 	<p>This seem to have been one of the biggest problems (together with pricing strategy).</p> <p>It was later corrected, and label was restricted afterwards, but would this have been done since the begging, certainly the situation would have been less controversial.</p> <p>Here the problem is not coming from Biogen, but from FDA.</p> <p>This is probably a result of “growth pains” from an agency that is trying to innovate, applying for the first time a pathway that was up until then used in smaller sized populations in cancer and rare diseases.</p>
Management of safety concerns	Biogen did not engage as much with medical and scientific community on the risk of drug potential side effects and how to control them.

EU confirmed its track of being more stringent in their risk-taking as identified in the literature review. Biogen scrapped the filling of Aduhelm in the Europe after discussions with European

regulators made it clear that the same data that conceded AA in the US, would not be accepted for conditional approval in EU.

Biogen has stated *“Alzheimer’s is a highly complex disease, and we have learned from the development and launch of Aduhelm.”*

This mediatisation of this case also spurred discussions around reforms to FDA accelerated approval, calling for higher scrutiny for approval to be automatically withdrawn when post-marketing trial is negative or the potential use of price caps for drugs approved through this pathway until it is converted to full approval. Aaron Kesselheim, Professor at Harvard Medical School, pointed that *“for the public and physicians to fully trust the pathway and the clinical value of drugs with accelerated approval, reforms as well as the timely completion of post approval trials are needed”*.

Force of patient associations & media speculation

Alzheimer’s Association was an outspoken supporter of Aduhelm’s approval, writing a letter to the panel *“While the trial data has led to some uncertainty among the scientific community, this must be weighed against the certainty of what this disease will do to millions of Americans absent a treatment”*. The Association is the largest noncorporate sponsor of Alzheimer’s disease research, and their efforts in encouraging this drug are in line with their recent efforts to promote biomedical research. (Caspi, 2019; Cummings et al., 2018).

While well received and supported by patients’ associations, the decision from FDA progressively gained more criticism from media and medical journals. As the controversy rose in the public sphere, national public interest groups called for investigation on the decision and two hospital systems announced they would not administer the drug. Image from Twitter post below shows message from Neurology centre saying that *“in response to growing controversy over new BIOGEN medication Aduhelm, Biogen pharmaceutical representatives are no longer welcome in the office, and should not enter or engage with staff, physicians or patients”*. It is clearly seen here the impact of not managing well the communications and all involved societal stakeholders when going for approval of such drug.

The close interactions between the company and FDA during the development process, that are often commended in the case of Covid-19 vaccine, in the case of Aduhelm were described as “an inappropriately close collaboration” (Public Citizen, 2021), that ended by being investigated by the Office of the Inspector General (Sullivan, 2021).

Access controversies

Access of Aduhelm to the market is conditioned by its price and reimbursement. This was also a key variable impacting all the controversy around the arrival of this drug to the market. Analysts initially projected that *“Biogen is now set up for one of the biggest drug launches in biopharma history”*, that *“has the potential to generate at least \$10 billion in peak sales and completely change the profile of the company”* (Reuters reports).

Biogen shocked the world with its aggressive pricing strategy. It set Aduhelm list price at \$4,312 per infusion for a patient of average weight, or \$56,000 per year. Well above the recommendations from the Institute for Clinical and Economic Review (ICER), which said the drug should cost \$8,300 per year given the “insufficient” evidence supporting its benefits (Higgins-Dunn, N., 2021).

Patients taking this drug would require multiple brain scans for diagnosis and during treatment to monitor potential side effects, and the cost of these brain scans would also be part of the additional costs to be reimbursed. An article from the New York times sorts out with a title criticizing “*New Alzheimer’s Drug could cost the Government as much as it spends on NASA*” with analysts saying that Medicare, who would pay a share of the prescription costs, would spend \$5.8 billion to \$29 billion on the drug in a single year, which would be an overwhelming impact on government budgets.

Fig 57- Projected spending for US government (Medicare) on Aduhelm based on first label approval and initial pricing, compared to budget government spends on NASA. Source: Katz, J. et al, New York Times, (2021)

It is a fact that there are plenty of other drugs that cost more than Aduhelm, specially in Oncology and rare disease space. What makes a special difference here is the size of the potential “customers” in scope of the label of this drug. Its first approved label included a super broad group of patients that could remain in treatment for several years.

Fig 58 - Self-constructed visualization showing the drivers of drug impact on government spends. The equation is much more complex than simply the drug price.

Should the initial pricing strategy be closer to ICER recommendations, most would say that this could have minimized the controversy. Still, Biogen Head of Global Product Strategy & Commercialization initial statements seems to show confidence on its pricing strategy:

“There is no perfect analog in this space... we have priced Aduhelm at roughly a third the level of cancer immunotherapies and roughly 25% below the average level of psoriasis biologics. We consider this to be a really responsible price and we consider this to be a price sustainable to the system”

Meanwhile, Biogen seemed to soften their initial aggressive strategy, and in January 2022 the CEO communicates that:

“Over the past several months, we have listened to the feedback of our stakeholders, and we are now taking important actions to improve patient access to ADUHELM”

Later announcing a price reduction of 50% with a label narrowed to patients with early Alzheimer’s Disease. As a critic, one could point that this pricing strategies should have been better thought since the beginning using value-based innovative pricing models.

One could also speculate that Eisai stepping out in March 2022 and Biogen taking over as “sole decision making and commercialisation rights” on Aduhelm, shows some signals of internal misalignment between the two companies that were initially co-developing the drug.

To add to the already bumpy road, the Centres for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS) released in April 2022 a national policy for coverage of Aduhelm and any future monoclonal antibodies directed against amyloid approved by the FDA with an indication for use in treating Alzheimer’s disease (CMS.gov). This policy determines that Medicare, the US government health plan for people older than 65, would cover these drugs under Coverage with Evidence Development (CED). Meaning it would only pay for Aduhelm for patients enrolled in a clinical trial.

This raised strong disagreement among some stakeholders, including patients and industry, with Biogen CEO stating on a call with investors that the CMS cover decision *“denies nearly all Medicare beneficiaries the right to access Aduhelm”* arguing that it promotes inequalities specially for patients living in remote areas that cannot dislocate to specific site locations to participate in ongoing randomized clinical trials. He goes further, reinforcing the move could hamstring appetite for future Alzheimer’s innovation, as the policy applies for all drugs within same category.

With all hurdles on Aduhelm access, sales prospects started to look increasingly negative, and that lead to ultimately considering ceasing its commercialization, and doing serious company restructuring where resources were initially allocated for the launch of this drug.

Follow-on drugs benefiting from the silver lining

Eisai and Biogen have a subsequent opportunity to learn from the storm of Aduhelm, with a second anti-beta-amyloid antibody, lecanemab. But on this case, it is the Japanese company that is leading the development and commercialization of the drug, with different company cultural dimensions in driving strategic decision making.

In fact, there were three additional anti-beta-amyloid drugs following the controversial Aduhelm drug from Biogen:

Anti-beta-amyloid drugs under development following Aduhelm	
Lecanemab	Drug from Eisai (Japanese company) in partnership with Biogen (American company) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good clinical and biomarker topline data on Ph3 study announced by Q4 2022 • Granted AA approval in January 2023 and is working to submit a conversion for full approval.
Donanemab	Drug from Lilly (American company) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topline Ph3 data vs Aduhelm Q4 2022 • AA first declined in January 2023 as not enough trial data from patients who were treated for at least a year.
Gantenerumab	Drug from Roche (Swiss company) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failed results on biomarker and clinical outcomes Q4 2022, somehow also confirming the correlation that exists between the two. • Results from Ph2 were already not strong, hence waited for full Ph3 and did not apply for AA.

After more than 20 years of promising but disappointing drug development in the field, all the helixes were starting to align with different compounds progressing the development gates showing consistent link of amyloid lowering with cognitive signal. From the three candidates on the fight, Lecanemab from Eisai seems to be well positioned showing clear evidence with two trials on consistent lowering of amyloid levels leading to slow of cognitive decline according to Clinical dementia rating (CDR). Most importantly these findings seem to be consistent across a multiple number of trials from different drugs. Even if there are still some works to be done to establish the clear link between lowering amyloid and tau levels and stopping the cognitive decline, the holistic analysis of all the evidence from different drugs suggests that the amount of amyloid depletion, rate of lowering and time spent at low levels matters to slow decline in CDR.

Trial	Antibody / Company	Duration (years)	Baseline amyloid (centiloids)	Residual amyloids (centiloids)	Clinical Dementia rating (How much it slows Progression of disease?) (▲ vs placebo)
POSITIVE					
EMERGE (Ph3)	Aducanumab (Aduhelm) Biogen	1.5	85	25	-22%
CLARITY AD (Ph3)	Lecanemab Eisai	1.5	78	23	-27%
Study 201 (Ph2)	Lecanemab Eisai	1.5	75	6	-26%
TRAILBLAZER-ALZ (Ph2)	Donanemab Lilly	1.5	108	23	-23%
NEGATIVE					
ENGAGE (Ph3)	Aducanumab (Aduhelm) Biogen	1.5	91	37	2%
GRADUATE I (Ph3)	Gantenerumab Roche	2.25	92	34	-8%
GRADUATE II (Ph3)	Gantenerumab Roche	2.25	98	51	-6%

Fig 59 - The sum of boxes from the clinical dementia rating (CDR) scale is applied to interventional trials for tracing the progression of Cognitive Impairment (CI) in the early stages of Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Range of positive data on different assets seen from -22% to -27% slowed decline at 18 months. There is positive correlation between the amount amyloid plaques reduction (Baseline-Residual) and CDR. Source: Adapted from Nitsch 2022

Efficacy results on % of slowing decline are becoming interesting (see appendix 4 with details of Lecanemab Ph3 results). As said by Dr Jeff Cummings, director of the Chambers-Grundy Center for Transformative Neuroscience at the University of Nevada Las Vegas, *"If you can slow a disease by almost 30% that's fantastic"*.

Lecanemab, Eisai

After the gates being opened by Aduhelm, Eisai also applied for Accelerated approval with Lecanemab in September 2021. However, Eisai leveraged the learnings from its predecessor and explicitly filled for accelerated approval from the beginning using Phase 2 published data (where robust plaque removal correlated with modest slowing of cognitive decline) while it's Phase 3 trial was ongoing. It was *"rolling submission"* process delivering portions of the application to the agency as they complete them and agreeing Phase 3 trial would be the confirmatory trial to show clinical benefit.

FDA later approved Leqembi (brand name of Lecanemab) under Accelerated Approval pathway in January 2023 based on the Ph2 data, and Eisai is working to file for a conversion to full approval with the also positive Ph3 data (Eisai website, Jan 2023).

Eisai applied smarter strategies compared to Biogen with regards to engagement of the medical communities on education and management of potential safety issues from its drug. *"We want to be proactive and will launch a program called 'Understanding ARIA'"* which continuous educational modules for healthcare professionals on how to manage the risk of the adverse reactions with lecanemab (Eisai website).

Eisai also profited from learnings from Biogen with regards to drug Access and planned to price it at \$26,500 per year. Even CMC said was looking at available information and "may reconsider its current coverage based on this review." Saying the conversion to Traditional approval could lead to broader coverage versus its initial limiting coverage policy applied to all beta-amyloid antibodies.

Ivan Cheung, Eisai CEO of the Americas Region commented:

"This initial phase, our goal at Eisai is not generating demand or generating sales. It's really getting the ecosystem ready,"

Assuming the true launch will come afterwards by the time of conversion to full approval, showing a completely different strategic approach than its Biogen contra part took with Aduhelm.

Nevertheless, several advocacy groups including Alzheimer's Association and several medical professionals, were actively advocating for CMS to reconsider its restrictive reimbursement policy for anti-amyloid monoclonal antibodies for Alzheimer's currently exclusive to patients enrolled in randomized controlled trials (Schloesser, P. 2022, Endpoints news).

In big contrast to the Aduhelm case, Eisai made a press release in January 2023 when it was granted the FDA Accelerated Approval, with an eight pages detailed document, entitled:

“Eisai’s approach to US pricing for leqembi (lecanemab), a treatment for Early Alzheimer’s Disease, sets forth our concept of “societal value of medicine” in relation to “price of medicine” maximizing value for all stakeholders while giving back value to society”

This document had a thorough and transparent analysis, describing among other things:

- ✓ Social impact of AD in US;
- ✓ Value of Lecanemab adoption to US Society;
- ✓ The detailed formula of how Eisai calculated the Annual per patient value of the drug at \$37,600 per year in the US by AD ACE Model;
- ✓ How they decided to price lecanemab at \$26,500, \$11,100 below their estimated calculated patient value;
- ✓ How they plan to focus on patient affordability and committed to patients access, once insurances cover for 90% with minimal out of pocket costs for patients;
- ✓ Their focus on health systems sustainability with their pricing approach and given value back to US Society;

This press release can be praised as masterclass of innovate best practices of how to approach a pricing and stakeholders management strategy when preparing to launch these types of innovative drugs in the field. It certainly learned from Aduhelm controversy and focus on the problematic of the innovation system affordability.

Brian Reid, expert in drug pricing and access comment on his social media:

“The press release from Eisai on how they priced their new Alzheimer's drug is incredible, and it sets a best practice for how companies must think about launch pricing. I didn't work on this, but it's one where I wish I did.”

He goes further to that the key four steps that set Eisai away for success are around its transparency they:

1. Showed their math
2. Leaned into the context
3. Didn't play games with the price
4. Showed they understood the patient experience

Gantenerumab, Roche

Gantenerumab drug from Roche had challenges on its Ph2 data, where it reported no efficacy on primary and secondary endpoints, but a trend in the fasted progressors based on post hoc analysis (AA international conference 2015). This would be a very weak data to try for Accelerated Approval, yet Roche decided to progress with a strategy of two full Ph3 trials trying to aim for a full approval, but ultimately by end 2022 communicated their two trials did not show either significant decline on their amyloid plaques removal nor in its clinical scales of slowing cognitive decline.

So, even if this trial failed to meet its primary goal, somehow also supported the hypothesis that the unsuccessful removal of beta-amyloid plaques correlates with no improvement on cognitive decline.

Donanemab, Lilly

Lilly has been taking innovating development strategies on its Donanemab asset thanks to the doors open and learnings from pains suffered by Biogen. Lilly had to remind investors to wait for confirmatory phase 3 readouts after the expectations set by Biogen, but still planned for accelerated approval pathway, even if their Head of Neurosciences, Anne White confessed disappointed with CMS reimbursement position *“because it negates any benefits patients can gain from the FDA’s accelerated approval pathway”*.

It is interesting to note that White moved over from leading the company's oncology commercial division to neuroscience in August 2021, so she is well equipped to attempt to translate fungible innovative strategies from the oncology ecosystem to this field.

Their strategy is heavily leveraged by the "opened doors" of their predecessor:

"We won't be discouraged if others miss their primary endpoints and so we'll be following that closely, obviously" adding that "In Alzheimer's disease, there have been many well documented failures, but with each failure we have learnt so much more about this devastating disease. When I think about what we now know about how to design a clinical trial and how to choose a population of patients to test a given therapy, it's clear that our understanding has deepened with each trial, even from those that weren't successful".

Lilly come with a better tailored and focused approach than Biogen. Having different approaches for prevention, early stages and late stages of the disease, through patient stratification and focus on diagnostics, that investors believe to be a key differentiation against previous players.

In their Ph3 trial patients have been stratified according to their levels of tau protein, based on the learnings from their Ph2 trial where patients with low levels of tau showed higher clinical improvement. This stratification strategy is not being pursued in the trials of Biogen/Eisai or Roche, and Lilly is convinced that this biomarker will help pinpoint the patients who will benefit most.

White defends,

"The uniformity of patient population is an essential factor for trials' success. The imbalanced rate of rapid progressors and the associated heterogeneity in individual dosing were, indeed, among the main contributing factors to the divergent results between EMERGE and ENGAGE trials for Aduhelm."

Adding that,

"The diagnostic will play a vital role not just in clinical trials, but in expanding and accelerating diagnosis of patients and identifying those who can benefit from drug therapy".

Donanemab Ph3 trial is also the first one in the field to have a head-to-head arm comparator with Aduhelm. Having this type of trial design is just possible because Biogen open the doors in this space. Lilly did not provide many details with regards to its pricing and Market access strategy, however White suggested their treatment may only need to last up to six months and they would maximise the use of innovative value-based agreements to gain market uptake. They seem to have a strategy focused on the long-term opportunity, acknowledging the patients access is very limited under accelerated approval CMS policy. Yet, Lilly also planned to make donanemab available to the small pool of available patients within the CMS guidance as quickly as possible through the accelerated approval, *"using that time to build out the diagnostic ecosystem to help physicians with the referral process and infusion systems"* White said.

Overall impact of approval of Aduhelm as a silver lining for innovation

While the approval of Aduhelm was controversial, it is seen with the examples of the three drugs above, how FDA taking that step have holistically shaped and kicked the doors for further investment and similar drugs to innovate their path in this area. This is seen for the abundance of research and approval boost in Neurodegeneration, also in related diseases to Alzheimer's such as Parkinson's or Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (Thomson, L.2021).

Dr Rudi Tanzi, professor at Harvard Medical School specialised in Alzheimer's Disease reinforced that,

"This approval (Aduhelm) allows us to come with other similar drugs to FDA that are cheaper and safer. As controversial as this approval was, it opened the door to find repurposed drugs that can do the job!"

Stressing that one of the main issues of such controversy was that,

"(..) press can blow things up and create much fear when not needed"

The approval was painted as a "Silver lining", as imperfect as the drug was, allowing the players in the innovation ecosystem to come with faster, cheaper, safer drugs with better efficacy with real world data. Marking the entrance of Alzheimer's treatments into a new era, similar to what happened to Oncology in the 90's.

Fig 60 - Self-created illustration representing the hypothesis that, as painful and controversial as it might have been, Aduhelm case was a sort of a silver lining propelling breakthrough learnings for lecanemab and other innovative drugs that followed.

STAT scientific magazine reporter Damien Garde described *"the legacy of Aduhelm as opening the floodgates, that Biogen itself didn't manage to actually profit from and will actually kind of be punished for this work they've done"*.

Share price roller-coaster

BIIB 269.44 | LLY 206.14 × | ROG.SW 318.45 × | ESALY ×

<p>November 2020</p> <p>FDA external advisory committee meeting on Aduhelm (Aducanumab)</p> <p>↑ ↓</p>	<p>October 30th – EMA accepted Biogen Aducanumab Marketing Authorization Application, which started raising the stock price until a peak max on Nov 4th with positive speculation just two days before the meeting with FDA external advisory committee on Nov 6th.</p> <p>As the panel voted on Friday 6th a negative appreciation on the level of evidence of the data to allow for a full approval, not only Biogen, but all the stocks of key players with beta amyloid antibodies in the pipeline slumped about 30% the next Monday Nov 9th.</p>	
<p>Jan - March 2021</p> <p>Results Eli Lilly Donanemab Phase 2</p> <p>↑ ↓</p>	<p>In January 2021 Eli Lilly Donanemab initially announced auspicious results slowing cognitive decline in results from their Phase 2 study. Eli Lilly stock surged nearly 12% in January, with also positive on Biogen stocks and other players.</p> <p>But stocks later fell more than 9% on March 13 when the results were murkier for a specific measure of cognition, this time with less negative impact on the stocks of competitors.</p>	

<p>June 2021</p> <p>Aduhelm (Biogen) receives FDA Accelerated Approval</p>		
<p>June - July 2021</p> <p>Controversy starts to rise with three FDA advisors of external committee resigning</p>		
<p>January 2022</p> <p>CMS issues a draft proposal to restrict Aduhelm (& similar drugs) coverage to patients in approved hospital-sponsored clinical trials</p>		

<p>Feb - July 2022</p> <p>Biogen strikes back at investor lawsuit on Aduhelm launch flop</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↓ ↓</p>	<p>All the first half of the year 2022 has been of continuous decline for both Biogen and its partner Eisai.</p> <p>Biogen shareholders have shown high discontentment and filed a lawsuit against the Big Biotech in February 2022 claiming it misled investors on the assumed success of Aduhelm.</p> <p>Biogen replied by filling a motion in court later in July 2022 to dismiss the claim, where it stated that <i>“the drug’s approval was a source of enormous hope for Biogen on behalf of patients and the company (...) while its flop of out the gate was a source of great disappointment, the company never promised the drug would become a commercial success”</i> (Fiercepharma News, July 2022).</p>	
<p>Sep 2022</p> <p>Eisai communicates first topline positive data on Lecanemab Phase 3 study</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑ ↑</p>	<p>On September 27th Eisai shares positive first topline data on Phase 3 clarity study meeting its primary endpoint, communicating they will also apply for full approval based on this data in addition to the accelerated approval request that was already done based on Phase 2 biomarkers data.</p> <p>This has catapulted the shares of Eisai and its partner Biogen, to levels not seen more than one year before, and starts projecting new hopes after the disbeliefs seen in stock markets due to Aduhelm’s controversies. Biogen shares climbed nearly 40% adding over \$ 10 billion to its market cap, putting it on track to erase the losses of previous year; also, with positive ripple effects felt across the industry, with shares from Lilly and Roche also benefiting from market increases.</p> <p>A general optimistic momentum for neurodegenerative drugs amongst investors is again created.</p>	
<p>Nov 2022 - Jan 2023</p> <p>Accelerated Approval Lecanemab Jan 2023 – watch how Market reacted to the approval of Lecanemab in AA</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑ ↑</p>	<p>The market maintains considerable high values throughout end of 2022 and beginning of 2023 when both Eisai and Lilly presented in the full positive Ph3 results of their anti-beta amyloid antibodies at AD conferences, Lecanemab and Donanemab, respectively.</p> <p>On January 6th, 2023, FDA approves Lecanemab under the Accelerated Approval pathways (based on previous submitted Ph2 data) which give an additional boost to keep the market on the high end. The company also communicates it is planning to resubmit the full Ph3 data to try to convert to a full approval, and hopefully overcome CMS coverage limitations of the AA as soon as possible.</p>	

The role of company culture & Executive leadership?

Biogen and Eisai were partners on the development and commercialization of both Aduhelm and Lecanemab drugs. Biogen took the strategic lead on the first (and ultimately led it alone as Eisai exit the partnership once controversies arose), and Eisai controlled the strategy for the second.

At this point in time, it is evident that Lecanemab has been more successful than Aduhelm on its development and commercialization strategy. This certainly has a multifactorial reason behind, starting from the differences in clinical data, but also to the learnings the follow-on program got from the first one, and perhaps most importantly, the different strategic decisions taken by the leadership of each company. On this last point, some questions emerge:

- What was the influence the different cultures of the two companies and their executives had shaping the different strategic paths both companies took?
- How much the CEO characteristics such as their professional and cultural background, etc. influenced decision making and appetite for risk taking?
- Were there some strategic leadership errors from Aduhelm that could have been mitigated?
- How much of the success from Lecanemab was thanks to the efforts of Aduhelm paving the way and allowing the followers to learn of this setback? Could a more holistic portfolio strategic approach shape their development strategies through different paths?

Biogen could be pictured by its American culture, traditionally more individualistic, capitalist, commercially aggressive, or even risk prone. On the other hand, Eisai is influence by its Japanese heritage, that is more collective, risk adverse, seeking consensus and adverse to confrontation of controversies. The Biogen CEO who drove the boat during the Aduhelm storms, Michel Vounatsos, ascended in the organisation from a commercial line, from his prior post as Chief Commercial Officer. In contrast, Eisai CEO, Haruo Naito, raised to the ranks from a role of Chief Director of Research & Development (Kansteiner, F. ,2022 & Wallmine).

Biogen Leadership

Vounatsos showed a tenacity to “fight” different stakeholders in forcing his vision forward in different settings. Including in open call with investors, Vounatsos strongly verbalised its “*strong disagreement*” with CMS coverage decision and “*encouraged other to make their voice heard in fighting this decision*” that limited access of innovative drug to patients, as wrote by Fiercepharma reporter (Kansteiner, F. ,2022). The covered limitations were applicable to other amyloid-target drugs approved through AA, and Vounatsos was very vocal voicing concerns that the decision could “*discourage investment*” and produce a “*chilling effect*” on future Alzheimer’s development.

In theory the questioning raised by Biogen CEO “*Why should Alzheimer’s disease patients be treated differently than those suffering from cancer, HIV, or other illnesses?*” could be seen as a valid one. He had a good point in terms of fostering innovation by trying not to close doors to follow-on drugs, and indeed there are appropriate pathways and value-based access strategies that could be leveraged from Oncology to AD. However, he did not leverage those. Should he done that, he would have made best use of value-based pricing and coverage with evidence development for innovative drugs with less strong clinical evidence, instead of aggressively aiming since bigging for big price and full coverage on a very broad label.

Literature review also indicates he might have failed on stakeholder management and fall into some decision-making biases. In other words, he had a valid *“Why”*, a fair vision. The problem seems to be on the *“How”* and the execution of different strategic decisions, often too bold at once, confrontational and without proper due diligences and concessions made across major stakeholders in the ecosystem. It is true that the unprecedented environment of Aduhelm was complex, fast, and highly knowledge intense. All the ingredients Jarzabkowski and Wilson (2006) would defend that ask for an emergent type of strategy, whereas the later Lecanemab drug from Eisai had more liberty for a better deliberately formatted type of strategy. Both Biogen and FDA contradicted the theory of Mante-Meijer & Loos (2008) that *“if the perceived risks are too great, people abstain from making a decision and keep things as they are”* yet reinforcing the theory of Douglas & Wildavsky (2004) showing that their individualist culture translated in being bolder towards potential gains, rather than focusing on risks.

With emergent strategies inevitably also comes the risk for emerging errors. According to framework from Merckler, M. (2020) it does not seem that the major problem from Vounatsos was a Vision error, as he was pursuing the right problems. Perhaps it was correlation error, in the sense that the societal forces expressed through media, as well as the medical community, were misplayed, and their price sensitivity wrongly correlated. Could also be argued to have been an Innovation error, when poorly choosing the appropriate price/label trade-off.

For a company that had a pipeline with more than one anti-amyloid drug for the same disease, a broader strategic portfolio consideration could have been thought. That could mean not being so bold on the first drug by trying to maximise price (which could have saved reputational damages and coverage blockages) but focus instead in preparing the AD ecosystem for the new class of drugs and explore the best value-based tools. A broader portfolio strategy would also mean leveraging economies of scales for their commercial operations of the different drugs. But the launch infrastructure that was initially prepared for Aduhelm was all dismantled once the drug was deemed as a commercial failure, and without a smooth continuous work with the ecosystem to prepare the arrival of their second partnered drug, Lecanemab.

Many tensions seem to have emerged internally at Biogen Leadership and certainly across the alliance among the two companies, that ultimately led to Eisai withdrawing from the partnership on Aduhelm commercialization. As described by Mullins, L., (2021) with all *“negative press, criticism on pricing and disappointing financial returns”* and *“just as Aduhelm proved to be a breaking point of public perception of Biogen, it ended up straining the relationships inside the company”*. Reporter from WBUR described this led to a game of musical chairs of who to blame for the failed strategic decisions, and that ended with the Executive VP of R&D being pushed out of the company. Ultimately, the company overhaul also reached the CEO, and Vounatsos steps down in 2022. On interview to Fiercepharma Vounatsos classified his reign as a *“good term”* and that his transition was a *“natural event that would be good for everyone involved”* (Liu Angus, 2022), tough one could imagine that the tension among Board of Directors and shareholders dictated the exit.

Eisai Leadership

With more than one year apart, Eisai approach with Lecanemab was different. Obviously, they benefited greatly from the learnings of their partner Biogen with Aduhelm. Still, there were clear signals of differences in both companies' leadership styles.

On public declarations, Haruo Naito, Eisai CEO, always transpired his vision to push for innovative approaches in the field however balanced with his acknowledgement of the inherent drug development challenges. On an interview to Bloomberg, Naito described "*drug development like a 4 R's puzzle game*" that need to be well balanced all the pieces right to successfully bring a drug to market:

- Right Hypothesis
- Right Dosing
- Right Population
- Right Endpoints

This is an example of how he used these opportunities to raise his credibility and back the solidity of Lecanemab development that was underway. When asked about Aduhelm price, he reinforces that his main priority is value-based drug affordability.

The background of the Leadership team and company culture certainly played a key influence driving these different strategic choices. Yet, it is important to reinforce that the external environment was not the same for the two companies that were moving in different places of the run to the market, so it is difficult to distinguish how much of the decisions were made by design in advance by Eisai leadership, versus how much was taken from the learnings from Biogen that was ahead breaking ice. In any case, some of the credit shall lie in the doors that were broken thanks to Biogen executive

leadership. Ultimately one could think that for innovation to foster in this ecosystem we need a combination of these two types of leaderships, as Eisai alone probably would not be as bold to breakthrough unpaved pathways and access the learnings these "failures" provide. In fact, these benefits have proved to go beyond Eisai. For example, Lilly has benefited from huge stock price increases with the Approval of Aduhelm, because of increased regulatory flexibility in the field and strength of the amyloid mechanism of action in AD. As wrote by Mullins, L., (2021) "*Aduhelm did the unblocking and tackling. (...) the industry might march on and make a great deal of money, based in large part on Biogen's pioneering research and breaking efforts*".

4.3 Summary of initial Hypothesis and Theories

Summary visualization of key knowledge gathered from the analysis of the **literature review, oncology quantitative data & AD case studies** before being contrasted against learnings from qualitative stakeholders interviews.

Source	Topic	Hypothesis / Theories
Main overarching hypothesis of the research project		The correct use of accelerated regulatory pathways in oncology over the past years has contributed to stimulate different investment and sponsored innovation by progressively bring better drugs to oncology patients. And with the right approach from concerned stakeholders, similar strategies could also create similar catapult effect and help foster innovation in the neurodegeneration space.
Literature Review: Ranga and Etkowitz (2013)	Innovation Intermediaries	Well integrated interaction between Science, Business and Government is the key to successful innovation and economic growth
Literature Review: "Government as Entrepreneur" by Albert N. (2009)	Innovation Intermediaries	Based on economic principle of market failure, government involvement in market activity to remove the innovation barriers is warranted. The marginal social benefit of involvement is greater than the marginal social costs, assuming of course that government involvement is efficient
Literature Review: Grace, C. (2009)	Push & Pull Strategies	"Push" and "Pull" incentives tech development across sectors work best together synergistically, push used to attract partners to engage work during development, and pull used to add credibility to market incentives
Literature review: The domestication approach (Haddon 2004)	Push & Pull Strategies	Push may start the acquisition, but pull is the determinant factor in the final adoption.
Literature Review: Loos & Mante-Meijer (2007) and Mante-Meijer & Loos (2008)	Decision Making & risk taking	If the perceived risks are too great, people abstain from deciding and keep things as they are. However, some people accept higher risks than others. Douglas & Wildavsky (2004) speak of different cultures of risk taking: in individualistic cultures, people look only at personal risk and gain, while in regulated cultures people do not intend to do something that might break the rules. These rules may be the structural rules of society as a whole, or the rules of their own social group.
Literature Review: Tafuri, G. et al (2014)	Risk taking FDA vs EMA	Tafuri concluded that two agencies manage uncertainty in a different way – FDA has a predominant attitude to take risks in order to guarantee quicker access to new treatments, unlike EMA. And that although the regulatory decisions should mainly be driven by formal factors, the informal aspects, like cultural tendency to manage risk, also play an important role in the regulatory process.
Literature review: Jarzabkowski and Wilson (2006)	Strategy formulation	In such Environments with high-speed velocity and high knowledge intensity (such as biopharma) the company strategy and decisions need to be done on the fly and is more of an "Emergent Strategy" than "deliberate Strategy "
Literature review: Trubel, H. (2022)	Decision making and biases	Top biases on R&D executive decision making: Confirmation bias, Champion bias and over-reliance.
Literature review: Huber (2019)	Innovation in Oncology	The three factors responsible for positive innovation seen in oncology drug development are: Investment that brought molecular understanding of disease Alignment on societal necessity to speed access to oncology drugs Adaptability of Regulators, especially FDA, to support clinical innovation
Literature review: Schwaederle, M., 2015	Innovation in Oncology	Use of precision medicines strategy, i.e., clinical trials and regulatory approvals focused on targeted sub-population based on expression of predictive biomarkers, allowed increased success in the field.
Literature review: Theoret, M. 2015	Innovation in Oncology	Use of expansion cohorts and adaptive clinical trial designs was a key factor that prompt agile clinical development innovation and fit into FDA expedited regulatory pathways.
Literature Review: Dagenais, S. (2021)	Innovation in Oncology	Use of real-world data on surrogate markers of progression has been a key strategic support to develop models of disease progression in cancer. This allowed to design leaner and faster clinical trials and identify patient subgroups with greatest unmet need.
Literature Review: Scher, J. et al (2021)	Innovation Intermediaries in drug development	Need to reconsider the partnership between investigators and industry. Such interactions need to go far beyond opinion-based spreading of information, as is often mediated by the current Key Opinion Leaders driven model. A truly scientific dialogue between academic scientists and industry needs to be rebalanced towards innovation-driven and data-driven science. 'Innovation and Knowledge Leader' (IKL), rather than a KOL, would be best suited for these interactions
Literature Review: Michel Foucault, 1966	Evolution of what is accepted in the industry	Each historical period (e.g., 90s versus the 2020s) contains certain underlying epistemological assumptions that determine what is acceptable as scientific discourse.
Literature Review: Beaver, J. et al. (2018) Huber, M., (2019) Subbiah, V. (2022)	Positive impact of AA in Oncology	Beaver showed the use of AA has increased over time and that the clinical benefit was not verified only in 5% of indications. Thus, defending that AA in oncology has been a successful strategy of balancing risk uncertainty while allowing enough regulatory flexibility to make safe & effective drugs available sooner to patients. Huber defends this earlier access to promising new drugs especially relevant and helpful for deadly diseases that progress slow, hence admitting they shift part of the evidence generation and safety risk from the pre-approval to the post approval period.
Literature Review: Richey, E. et al (2009) Dhingra, K. (2015)	Challenge of AA in Oncology	Dhingra challenges AA have been used by some companies as 'intellectual creativity exercise' to define narrow patient population to gain early regulatory approval of 'failed standard therapy' followed by attempts to get drug widely used before confirmatory trials completed.

Kunnumakkara, A. et al (2019)		Nachi shows concerns with limitations of companies in fulfilling post-marketing commitment studies. Kunnumakkara defends there is much uncertainty in bringing drugs to market for which correlation with overall survival is not well established, thus risk for patients of getting ineffective drug.
Literature Review: Hoekman, J. (2015)	Flexible Regulatory Pathways: FDA vs EMA	Hoekman showed CMA pathway from EMA hasn't been used its full potential liked some risk aversion. Instead of proactively being planned to use with Ph2 data as a pathway to obtain early access, it is just used as a "rescue option" when final Ph3 data not strong enough to justify full marketing authorization.
Literature Review: Dhingra,K. (2015)	"Limited Approval" paradigm	Central philosophy behind this concept is that we need to move drug development from a series of linear, landmark events to a flexible and iterative process. 'Limited Approval' is proposed based on limited initial clinical investigation on small, targeted population. This approval shall not be the end, and the research work would continue to add the survival data and identify better biomarkers.
Literature Review: EMA Pilot (2015)	Adaptive Pathways	EMA explored similar concepts of innovative regulatory paradigms of the "limited approval" approach from Dhingra,K., that was renamed to "adaptive pathways". The Pilot of adaptive pathways concept was tried by EMA as a response to the access-versus-evidence conundrum.
Literature Review: Moreno,S. (2019)	Value-based pricing in Oncology	VBP lies on the principle that prices should on the one hand reflect the added drug's benefit to patients, healthcare systems and, in some cases, broader society, and on the other hand reward successful innovation and create incentives for further R&D. To ensure that the industry develops valuable innovations, it is fundamental to remove any ambiguity around the 'value framework' used by payers to appraise the value of pharmaceutical products and then set value-based prices. Clarification is important because value frameworks signal the type of innovation preferred and so it encourages the generation of socially valuable innovations as opposed to just innovation per se
Literature Review: MacEwan, J. (2019)	Different Oncology endpoint preference among different stakeholders	Researchers and clinicians often presume that the value of surrogate endpoints like stable disease/PFS only have value if they increase OS. In contrast, MacEwan results suggest that patients demonstrated a strong preference for longer periods of stable disease, even when OS was held fixed
Literature Review: Huber,H. (2019)	Benefits of Pay for Performance models used in Oncology	In the simplest terms of P4P, payers only pay for the drug if a prospectively agreed patient benefit is realized. P4P greatly incentivizes drug makers to: 1.Focus on medical value not volume; 2. Invest in identification of prognostic indicators to prospectively help identify responders and non-responders; 3. Extend effort to ensure the health care professionals are using drug in the right patient population E.g., The pharmaceutical company essential proposed to charge only when the drug was effective and to refund the drug costs if it was not clinically effective.
Literature Review: Cherla,A. (2021)	Coverage of oncology drugs in EU that got FDA AA	This study found that many cancer drug indications that received accelerated approval from the FDA were either not reviewed or denied authorization or coverage by European regulators because of insufficient safety, clinical efficacy, or cost-effectiveness, which was likely owing to the use of uncertain evidence derived from unvalidated surrogate measures, which provided the basis for US regulatory approval
Literature Review: Gusmano,M et al (2022)	Regulatory Approval vs Payers Coverage	While the reluctance of public and private payers to pay for new drugs and devices for which there is limited evidence may protect against instances in which the FDA approval process moved too fast, there is a concern that the reliance on payers to call for additional evidence makes it easier for the FDA to issue approvals on the basis of limited evidence.
Literature Review & AD drugs case studies Lin, P. (2020)	Pricing & Access strategies for AD drugs	Whether aducanumab succeeds, other disease-modifying therapies for AD will follow, and the health-care system is unprepared for the reimbursement and access challenges. First, we urge the use of cost-effectiveness of new Alzheimer's treatments as a starting point for setting value-based prices. Second, payments for new AD therapies should ideally incorporate a performance warranty, which helps apportion risk associated with initial therapy value estimates between drug manufacturers and payers. Third, we urge consideration of "subscription" payment agreements to address system affordability issues.
Literature Review Budish E (2015)	Positive effect of surrogate endpoints in Oncology	Budish document developed a theoretical model that shows that surrogate endpoints appear to increase R&D investments on innovations that would otherwise have long commercialization lags. We also use this surrogate endpoint variation to estimate counterfactual improvements in cancer survival rates that would have been observed if commercialization lags were reduced Both our empirical evidence on the effects of surrogate endpoints for hematologic cancers and this historical case study for heart disease suggest that research investments aimed at establishing and validating surrogate endpoints may have a large social return
Literature Review: Tulum, O. et al (2019)	Investment & Shareholder value: Tension between innovation and financialization	The strategic underling goal of the company is profits, not products, and the purpose of the profits is to boost the company's stock price. If the goal of public policy is to generate effective medicines at affordable costs for a wide range of diseases, our findings for the U.S. pharmaceutical industry call for inquiry into the deleterious impacts of the prevailing ideology that companies should be run to "maximize shareholder value."
Literature Review: Mahlich, J. (2021)	Investment & Shareholder value: Company size linked to agency problems	The size of the company plays a key role on how the company approaches strategic decision to move forward its development programs. single-project firms were more likely to move their products from Phase 1 to Phase 2 trials within a two-year period than were mature firms. However, their products were also less likely to demonstrate good results in Phase 2 trials, and less likely to move into Phase 3 trials within a three-year period. The authors interpret these findings as suggesting an agency problem between investors and managers for smaller, single-project firms that often leads to overinvestment in research. Larger, multiproduct firms were therefore more efficient.

Literature Review: Budish, E. et al (2015)	Investment & Shareholder value: Invested limited to early-stage diseases	Private firms invest more in late-stage cancer drugs and little in early-stage and cancer preventive drugs that require longer time to bring to market. "Short-termism" and "fixed patent term" were two of the potential causes identified as drivers for private companies to move away from long-term research investment.
Literature Review: De Schrijver, J., (2013); Mahlich, J. et al, (2021).	Investment & Shareholder value: Share price reaction to drug approvals	The share price of biopharma firms fluctuates based on the expected profitability of its pipeline, hence seen as a proxy of the company's innovation potential. Biopharma Investors seem especially sensible to negative news linked to refusal of approvals of new products. Stocks of companies listed in NASDAQ seems to react more than the ones listed in NYSE. The impact of drug approvals also seem larger in stocks of smaller companies.
Literature Review: J. Donavon (2018)	Investment & Shareholder value: Disease area vs novelty	The type of disease (for example if cancer or neurology) has little impact level of market returns in an event of a successful new approval. However, the fact that is a more novel application type, i.e., completely new molecule, completely new MoA, etc. have a positive effect on returns.
Oncology Quantitative data	Timelines conversion from AA to FA	Takes on average 7 months to receive an Accelerated Approval from the time of filing. Once the drug received the accelerated approval, takes on average more 47 months, approximately 4 years, to be converted to full approval.
Oncology Quantitative data	Pricing conversion AA to FA	Overall, from 50 from the 60 cases observed (more than 83%) show that an increase of price from accelerated to full approval. This increase is on average of plus 26%.
Oncology Quantitative data	CARs conversion AA to FA	Slight trend of market reacting more positively to the Accelerated Approvals than to its later conversion to Full Approvals. Average CARs slightly higher for AA where primary endpoint was PFS (0,6) compared to Tumour response rate (0,37). Only one AA had already OS data on its AA (strange!) and interestingly its CARs was of -0,15. Verified NASDAQ companies seem to respond more to the announcements, specially more positively to the accelerated approval announcements.
AD case studies	Aduhelm as catapult for opening regulatory doors	Historical approval brought for the first time a surrogate endpoint in Neurodegeneration to the FDA list of potential use for Accelerated Approval pathways. This opened the innovation doors for its following drugs.
AD case studies	Perception on Interactions between firm-government interactions	Close interactions between the company and FDA during the development process, that are often commended in the case of Covid-19 vaccine, in the case of Aduhelm were described as "an inappropriately close collaboration", showing the importance of environmental context.
AD case studies	Aduhelm label-pricing strategy seen as the biggest source for controversy in the case	There are plenty of other drugs that cost more than Aduhelm, specially in Oncology and rare disease space. What makes a special difference in Aduhelm pricing is the size of the potential "customers" in scope of the label of this drug. Its first approved label included a super broad group of patients that could remain in treatment for several years which would represent a huge some for reimbursement. Should the initial pricing strategy be closer to ICER recommendations, most would say that this could have minimized the product controversy. Label-pricing strategy seen as the biggest contribution for Aduhelm commercial failure.
AD case studies	Aduhelm as Silver lining Effect	The approval Aduhelm could be seen as a "Silver lining", as imperfect as the drug was, allowing the players in the innovation ecosystem to come with faster, cheaper, safer drugs with better efficacy with real world data. Marking the entrance of Alzheimer's treatments into a new era, similar to what happened to Oncology in the 90's.
AD case studies	Lecanemab successful innovation following Aduhelm Silver Lining	Strategy of Lecanemab, and specially the way the company engaged with stakeholders as in the press release describing their value-based calculation is seen as masterclass of innovate best practices of how to approach a pricing and stakeholders management strategy when preparing to launch these types of innovative drugs in the field. It might well had got the learnings from Aduhelm controversy and focus on the problematic of the innovation system affordability.
AD case studies	Market response to regulatory events	As described in literature, the regulatory decisions are more difficult to correctly speculate, as Biogen stocks started raising the stock price until two days before Advisory Committee meeting, that had then had a negative outcome. However, it confirmed the big reactions to negative regulatory news for NASDAQ listed companies (as Biogen) seen after the meeting.
AD case studies	Companies cultures and strategic decision making	Biogen is pictured by its American culture, traditionally more individualistic, capitalist, commercially aggressive, or even risk prone. On the other hand, Eisai is influence by its Japanese heritage, that is more collective, risk adverse, seeking consensus and adverse to confrontation of controversies. It does not seem that the major problem from Vouatsos (Biogen CEO) was a Vision error, as he was pursuing the right problems. Perhaps it was correlation error, in the sense that the societal forces expressed through media, as well as the medical community, were misplayed, and their price sensitivity wrongly correlated. Could also be argued to have been an Innovation error, when poorly choosing the appropriate price/label trade-off.
AD case studies	Combination of different leadership styles in ecosystem leading to field innovation	Aduhelm more "aggressive" and risk-prone leadership, seen as benefiting the in some ways the class. Assumed that for innovation to foster in this ecosystem we need a combination of these two types of leaderships, as Eisai alone probably would not be as bold to breakthrough unpaved pathways and access the learnings these "failures" provide. Lilly has also benefited from huge stock price increases with the Approval of Aduhelm, because of increased regulatory flexibility in the field and strength of the amyloid mechanism of action in AD. As wrote by Mullins, L., (2021) " <i>Aduhelm did the blocking and tackling. (...) the industry might march on and make a great deal of money, based in large part on Biogen's pioneering research and breaking efforts</i> ".

4.4 Qualitative data from Interviews

Following the project methodology, raw data from qualitative interviews was clustered in seven dimensions. The table below provides a summary of key takeaways of collected data that can be found on Appendix 1 and that will be deeply analysed on the discussion section.

<p>DIMENSION 1</p> <p>Value Perception in Oncology vs Neurodegeneration: Policies & Regulations</p>	<p>Interviewees described that Oncology ecosystem has benefited from the “<i>perfect storm factors for drug development innovation with societal alignment on the need, sense of hopelessness of its fatality and high Salience.</i>” And reiterated an overall positive effect of FDA AA fostering continuous investment and innovation in the field (EU referred as more closed when supporting riskier Innovation). Most described that FDA is just starting to open doors in ND ecosystem, but there is still reluctance of sharing risks with earlier access at the same level as Oncology. Pointing an opportunity for innovation if more adaptive and “limited approval” approaches were followed together with increased control from Agencies, right payor mechanisms, and real-world clinical practise.</p> <p>Participants describe as one of the highest hurdles in Neurodegeneration (ND) how to define value and align stakeholders around it, describing it as cause for policy controversies and affordability challenges.</p>
<p>DIMENSION 2</p> <p>Scientific hurdles on clinical development Innovation in Neurodegeneration space</p>	<p>Respondents pointed to the issue of low investment, early exploration, and development of biomarkers in ND. Old scales of measures seen as main responsible for parading of long and expensive trials, that also limit the use of innovative trial designs such as basket and umbrella designs seen in Oncology.</p> <p>Individuals linked the lack of biomarkers exploration for AD with current lack of knowledge to connect disease molecular signature with clinical benefit, as it was developed in Oncology</p> <p>Reporting this ultimately contributes to misalignment among stakeholders of what is a “relevant meaningful change” in ND, something needed for a drug to be well accepted.</p>
<p>DIMENSION 3</p> <p>Pricing & Market Access Models of innovation</p>	<p>Positive value-based innovative pricing schemes were given as examples that should be leveraged from Oncology to ND, such as the collaboration between <i>AIG Insurance</i> and Pfizer on the use of insurance policy to pay back patients and payors based on real-world drug performance. Something not seen in ND.</p> <p>Described the hypothesis of “<i>the inverted U curve</i>” as potentially explaining some of the behaviour seen in drug affordability controversies:</p> <p><i>“(…) describes the degree to which someone want a treatment or feels they need it versus their willingness to pay starts with low demand for a treatment in the beginning because it is not lifesaving, or they don't think there's a likely chance they're going to have the disease. They're willingness to pay is low. And as they're worry about the disease, their sense of it as a threat goes up, the willingness to pay goes up. But then something happens when that seriousness is red lined all the way, and now it's a lifesaving treatment and it's the only option available. Their willingness to pay goes to 0. Because all of a sudden, I'm entitled to it. It's not a payment issue.”</i></p> <p>Concerns were raised on ND limited infrastructures that are needed to shift the real-world evidence paradigm after launch when supporting dynamic pricing models. Current system in Europe with prices mostly adjusted down seen as a big limitation. If they would be adjusted up, this would bring pull incentives to continuous evidence degeneration and decrease the pressure to maximize price as much as possible from the first launch.</p> <p>Participants also described a lack of well-accepted quality adjusted target ambition in the ND field, that has made it difficult to compare and judge drug pricing and reimbursement mechanisms and compare products against competitors, with clear tensions among regulators and payors.</p>

	Proposed opportunity to embrace more often the benefits of having joint engagements with Payors and Regulators early on the drug development journey.
DIMENSION 4 Cross Helix collaboration & Innovation strategies	<p>Described that innovation in Oncology has come from “<i>necessity pressure</i>”. Discussed a theoretical illustration describing innovation pressure seen in Oncology ecosystem as a “<i>box with four outlet valves</i>” where the pressure needs to come out at least from one of them: 1) unmet need recognition, 2) ethical issue of early access, 3) justification of high price, or 4) Innovation. In Oncology all 3 first valves were assured, so the pressure has been directed to the innovation valve.</p> <p>Pointed that in ND there is gap on the effort that is put in multiple helix collabs, “<i>e.g., with NHS Foundation, National Institute on Aging Accelerated Medicines Partnerships, etc.</i>” that are not yet leveraged for sponsoring and generating RWE, explore and develop biomarkers, including digital tools. “<i>In oncology a lot of these sponsoring allowed the needed brokering of innovation in the field.</i>”</p> <p>Yet interviewees recognised some recent triggers in ND that seem like a “<i>catapult on the whole sector into higher levels of efficiency, and investment productivity is about to happen.</i>”</p>
DIMENSION 5 Strategic learnings from Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloids case studies	<p>Interviews agreed that the key concerning controversy on Aduhelm was the recipe of clinical efficacy uncertainty inherent to AA pathway, joint with broad label/high price. During interviews critics were raised on potential pressure FDA might have felt to approve the drug. Yet all agreed the AA has catapulted the market, as it is seen with increased investment and success of following drugs in the field.</p> <p>Interviewees showed appreciation to strong and close collaboration between Biogen and FDA, similar to what was seen with Pfizer in Covid-19 vaccine.</p> <p>All referred Eisai strategy with lecanemab as best practises.</p>
DIMENSION 6 Executive Leadership and strategic decision making	<p>Most interviewees referred the art of recognising the environmental context as key factor for efficient decision-making when doubting between going for a faster accelerated approval access <i>versus</i> sticking to a traditional pathway. Apart from clear mistakes in commercial pricing strategy, not all Aduhelm development was seen as a strategic mistake per se.</p> <p>The notion of two types of leadership in the industry was debated between “<i>the disrupter cavaliers</i>” & the “<i>conservative collaborators</i>”. Participants agree good innovation ecosystem needs both, with strong situational leadership skill to know when to shift from one to the other. One of the Executives interviewed referred the example of Roche amyloid development program where they followed a “<i>conservative collaboration approach</i>”, but had they been on Biogen feet (potential for first in market), they might as well have gone for “<i>the disrupter cavalier</i>” approach.</p> <p>Executives interviewed reiterated the importance to foster the right leadership culture in order to make the best strategic trade-off on drug development decisions, that are often based on tacit knowledge of the external environment</p>

<p>DIMENSION 7</p> <p>Investment in Neurodegeneration business</p>	<p>Perception of Executives and Investors interviewed is that Return on Investment (RoI) in the field is still seen as lower and with greater uncertainty compared to other fields. Emerging amyloids antibodies are starting to break the old and slow innovation cycle, yet up to now Aduhelm also brought to attention the paradox that a big size disease population with big unmet need (thus huge demand) makes the access to market even more challenging. Hence from purely investor/shareholder side, a lot of them are still on the “wait and watch mode”.</p> <p>There is agreement among participants that a strong alignment between innovation regulators/payors/HCP etc. is needed, namely on severity of unmet need and acceptability of risk, otherwise the field would get stuck in the old cycle of long development and uncertain RoI. Consequently, decreasing investment on riskier innovation, where only bigger corporations would have the luxury to play, as smaller and dynamic biotech won't have the investment founding to venture in the field. Specially if aiming to invest in trials that intervene in very earlier stages of disease (including prevention).</p> <p>Agreed the opportunity is there, but needs the right leadership flexibility, the right touchpoints across innovation helix, and the right policies incentives with a mix of push & pull approaches.</p>
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5. Discussion

5.1 Accelerated pathways in Oncology ecosystem

REGULATORY EFFICENCY

Research data of this project shows that Oncology ecosystem have benefited from perfect interphase collaboration among the different helixes systems of innovation with clear shared value proposition. The interviewees described the cause for this to be linked with:

“The perfect storm factors for drug development innovation with societal alignment on the need, sense of hopelessness of its fatality and high salience”.

Together with the appropriate level of flexibility from FDA and Payors acceptance for higher levels of risk sharing, this was described by participants as the motor for continuous investment that brought scientific innovation in the field. Namely being responsible for the leap in paradigm with earlier investment in biomarkers exploration and real-world data generation.

This data confirmed the hypothesis suggested by Huber, M., (2019) and Subbiah, V. (2022) that defended that accelerated regulatory approval benefits in Oncology have clearly outweigh its risks, allowing it to move away from traditional slow phased sequential development to more agile pathways of development. Participants also confirmed that this shift has moved with less extend in Europe:

“(…) It's still a little bit different in the US and Europe as well. Regularly in the US I've seen being more interested in actually having the dialogue with industry to try and find solutions; in Europe is still very much not the case where industry and the regulators are still seen as kind of being on opposite sides.”

Fig 61 - Overview of project quantitative findings related to US Oncology accelerated *versus* full approvals. Raw data analysed from 1995 to 2022. Shows clear benefit from accelerated approvals in terms of providing earlier access to market and earlier capitalisation yet leaving a potential for further price increase once confirmatory efficacy data available at the moment of conversion to full approval.

The average four years gap between AA and FA demonstrated by the collected regulatory data in Oncology is considerably high and prompts that the overall stakeholders in this ecosystem (profiting from earlier treatment for patients, earlier real-world evidence for health systems, earlier revenues for industries, etc.) would benefit less from its value if they had to wait more four years to access these drugs. With the condition that these flexible paradigms are accompanied by high control and scrutiny from Agencies, with measures to make sure post-marketing are well fulfilled, off-label is controlled, and with celerity withdrawing products of the market when needed.

PRICE & ACCESS

Value-based access mechanisms balancing the right level of pricing incentives to innovation and sustainability of healthcare systems, are well adopted in the context of accelerated approvals in oncology:

"(...) healthcare system budget is no longer kind of exclusively used to fund provision of care for patients, but it's also used as a means to explicitly stimulate scientific innovation. It's a massive shift, I think."

Oncology ecosystem shares the risk of drug underperformance in situations of accelerated approvals through pay for performance mechanisms:

"they had AIG develop an insurance policy that protected the patient from financial exposure in case of clinical failure or in case of catastrophic cost.(...) it's an example of the innovation that spurred by the pressure that oncology creates."

New findings from this project on quantitative US price data collected shows that on average more than 80% of drugs have their price increased once they convert to full approval. Overall data shows an average of price increase 26% at the time of full approval compared to the initial accelerated approval price (already excluding inflation contribution).

Even if literature describes a lower push for value-based pricing in US than in EU, the new learnings from this project somehow lead us to the premise that when the additional evidence data is provided to allow for a conversion to full approval, this is recognised within US market mechanisms with a price increase. This could also be argued as sort of an organic value-based principle. It could be interesting to translate this in the Neurodegeneration sphere. These types of strategies force some changes on the trade-off between earlier access and price potential along the drug life cycle.

Quantitative data also hints that the level of price increase between AA and FA tended to be lower over last decade, even with few cases of price decrease. One reason could be the growing quality of accumulated evidence that is being provided early in AA, with adoption of a higher price since the start. Or cases where additional post-marketing commitment of Ph3 data is actually comparatively decreasing the value of the asset in the market. These are just speculations, because normally the market in the US does not strictly follows a value-based control.

Important to add that these dynamic mechanisms also brought a positive shift in development of powerful real-world infrastructures, that iteratively feed in real clinical setting data for value definition. On the slip side, the data show no correlation between price level and type of surrogate endpoint used, which would have been a deeper signal of value-based pricing.

CAPITALISATION & INVESTMENT

Even if literature showed that the initial bigger investment were in trials that intervene at later stage of progression of disease, this has been progressively shifted with the use of surrogate endpoints and support of public entrepreneurship. This allowed a shift of R&D investment to earlier stages of disease, and even prevention.

New Oncology quantitative data of market returns at the time of AA vs FA generated in this project responded to existent gap in literature. This research has contributed with the new knowledge for the field by suggesting that the market responds more positively with higher levels of capitalization to AA strategies, when compared to the moment of drug conversion to full approval. One potential explanation would be that AA is inherently associated with more novelty and with potential for earlier revenue. These earlier abnormal returns are especially important for smaller oncology companies that are hungry for investment to venture in risky development paths. In fact, the new findings also confirmed work from De Schrijver (2013) with market reacting more to NASDAQ than to NYSE listed companies, that are often smaller and more innovative and in need of this earlier financial push.

Once the drug hits the market through Full Approval the returns seem to be lower. Some companies had even negative CARs, this is specially seen in NYSE companies that have bigger portfolios so one reason that can contribute to that could be the interference of the various micro events that are happening at the company pipeline.

ACCELERATED PATHWAYS AS A SOURCE OF CATAPULT INNOVATION

Findings from this project on the observed innovation forces on oncology ecosystem could be visually represented as a group of “*effort forces*” accumulated through “*load force*” that at some point catapulted innovation of oncology drug development.

Fig 62 - Confirmed the hypothesis that the correct use of accelerated regulatory pathways coupled with other cross-functional effort forces led to a catapult of innovation in oncology ecosystem

The pressure from society, and the aligned recognition among different stakeholders on the severity of disease & unmet need, led to the acceptance that the risk of developing an innovative medicine should not be taken only by industry. But it needs to be taken across all the intermediaries along the value chain as the main goal is to develop a therapy with maximised value for all stakeholders, and not only for shareholders. All of this “forced” the flexibility from Agencies to progressively use accelerated approval pathways that have reduced development cycles and uncertainty of investment in riskier innovation.

By speeding the innovation cycle and reducing uncertainty, findings showed “loaded increasing forces” of interest through increased capitalisation, venture funding, deals activity, etc.; and this has resulted in an increased number of new Oncology solutions hitting the Market. The intensity of competition to play in this attractive field pulled for further drugs with increased differentiation that resulted in drop of cancer mortality in the last decades.

So, with these findings, the first part of the main hypothesis of this research project, that the correct use of accelerated pathways in oncology has contributed to stimulate different investment and sponsored innovation by progressively bringing better drugs to oncology patients, is confirmed.

5.2 Translation to Neurodegeneration ecosystem

The second part of the main hypothesis of this research work, assumes that if similar strategies as used in oncology ecosystem are translated to neurodegeneration, with the right collaboration among different stakeholders, similar catapult effect could be experienced in the long run-in neurodegeneration.

Findings were then also used to better understand the barriers and opportunities related to the translation of oncology pathways to the neurodegeneration ecosystem. And how the leadership from these biopharmaceutical companies can take better strategic decisions to effectively apply these accelerated paths.

5.2.1 Barriers to overcome

The analysis of the case studies of amyloid antibodies in Alzheimer's Disease shows that the Stakeholders in Neurodegeneration ecosystem perceived the same level of flexibility that is used in Oncology differently. Showing the field is not aligned when it comes to take similar level of risk as in Oncology.

Fig 63 - Illustration of supportive & resistant forces from different stakeholders in the controversial case of Aduhelm, first Alzheimer's drug ever approved under an FDA accelerated approval pathway.

Societal helix showed key resistance translated through the Media controversies, even if patients associations exerted strong willingness to adjust risk levels and pilot early drug access. Resistance from Medical community also played a key role, showing lack from Biogen to bring them onboard during the early development journey, communicating the drug value in the context of the broader ecosystem and managing expectation for side effects treatment.

Compared to Oncology, one of the highest hurdles identified in the Neurodegeneration field, is how to properly define, measure, and align stakeholders on the therapeutic value. This is pointed as the basis for policy controversies and access challenges, as described in table below:

Barrier	Exerts from panel interviews	Comments
Properly define and measure value	"In oncology (...) hope is provided by the tail end of the distribution, so it gives people a lot of hope even if the median survival time is 6 extra months. But one out of 100 has six extra years. The science started to unlock oncology and it made a shift from it being such that you have to have a fatalistic attitude with no hope and reason to believe. I think Neurodegeneration is on the same journey. There is a hypothesis that aging is the next crisis, we need to shift the fatalistic attitude towards aging as an inevitable thing , we should start to unlock it as a disease as we did for oncology."	Work needed to shape the societal perspective of the fatalistic attitude towards neurodegenerative diseases associated with aging. Work needed with government policy makers, innovation brokers, patient associations, medical community, and general media
	"Healthcare systems, the understanding of what these drugs (Alzheimer's) contribute in terms of value is not there and that's something actually we are working on to try and bring more data that can then help inform those types of conversations."	More real-life data needed on the use of the new drugs and diagnostics in clinical practise where there is very little data in this field, if these are to allow accelerated pathways the paradigm is blocked for investment, this data is never generated, and the field never catapulted
	"I think value-based pricing is certainly one of the more sustainable ways to go. The challenge with that is really the demonstration of value, is the conceptualization and demonstration of value. It's harder in in some areas than others "	
	"It's easier if there's a cost per quality that we're going to stick to, the only question is what quality adjusted life here means on the drug"	Important to define, align and communicate on the unmet need and the targets in terms of the disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) target, how much its perceived by all and get commitment on sharing risks Then make the value-based calculation clear to the world (example of lecanemab)

Using the figurative analogy discussed during qualitative interviews of the “pressure box with four outlet valves”, it seems as in the case of Neurodegeneration there is still no alignment on how to close some of the “valves”. These are unanimously closed in Oncology field, thus putting all the pressure into drug development innovation (Fig 64):

Fig 64 - Illustration of the concept of the “Pressure box with four outlet valves” found during qualitative interviews. It assumes that in the case of Oncology all the pressure has been directed into “drug development innovation valve” because all other topics on the other valves are fully aligned across all stakeholders, thus valves are closed. Whereas in Neurodegeneration the pressure is still disperse across all the four valves, hence there has been less pressure for innovation in this field up to now.

Findings from this project confirmed that the lack of stakeholders alignment around the definition of value in neurodegeneration is a major responsible for the inhibition of risker scientific investment in biomarkers exploration over the last decades. This led to clinical development of disease modifying therapies historically relying in old clinical scales with no means of sub-population stratification, and the lack of biomarkers data in real world clinical practise:

Barrier	Exerts from panel interviews	Comments
Lack of proactive investment at risk in biomarkers exploration and targeted approaches for clinical development	" (...) I think if you were able to go back 10 years, I think there's more exploratory work that could have been done. The challenge now is people are looking for biomarkers for just pure disease and they won't be able to stratify the response to the amyloid therapies predictive of onset of disease or predictive of your likelihood of getting it."	Early capitalisation linked to accelerated approvals could be an opportunity to reinvest earlier in biomarkers exploration.
	"Amyloid reduction (...) we can measure it pretty well with amyloid PET imaging. But if you look at clinical symptoms, it just takes 2 years to get anything out and it takes a sample size of thousands of patients, so it is not just because of the nature of the disease, but because of the nature of the measurement as well "	An earlier access could provide an incentive for progressive correlations between biomarkers used in technical trials and real-world settings. And these infrastructures for real world exploration could speed the field and unlock the use of agile clinical trial designs (basket, umbrella) as often seen in oncology.
	" the expensive imaging stuff, which you can do in a technical trial which you wouldn't expect people to do in the real world (...) The challenge is there are a lot of interesting biomarkers for Alzheimer's that are blood based or other things. So, I think the thing that could be done differently would be a more exploratory approach to using some of those "	
	"Use of umbrellas or platform trials today (...) they've been the big driver for innovation in the field (oncology)." "The potential to use adaptive and basket trials in Neurodegeneration is dependent on having things that can change relatively quickly and can be very accurately measured , so you can actually adapt the study in an agile way. So, it is all dependent on having strong surrogate biomarkers in the field. "	

Findings highlight the need for closer relationship and collaboration across the “*components*” of Etzkowitz helix systems that are still relatively weak in the Neurodegeneration space. In contrast, Oncology benefited from stronger entrepreneurship ventures from Government, collaborations among public-private brokers, and promotion of platforms for sharing failed trials data. All of these have rose productivity of R&D investment in Oncology:

Barrier	Exerts from panel interviews	Comments
Less support to adopt open innovation non-commercial collaborations and resistance to share data from previous failures	" In Oncology arena there are a lot of non-commercial organizations , such as the National Cancer Institute in the US. NCI is there to collaborate with industry, and act like an honest broker and have platforms that are being run at their kind of sponsoring and then they're brokering with different pharmas to get them to the table alongside (...) "	This barrier could be overcome with proper definition and communication of unmet need, that would activate the pressure for higher public-private entrepreneurship and brokering of knowledge across innovation intermediaries.
	"(...) of course the whole Pharmaceutical industry is built on competition, you know? So, we often compete and don't collaborate with our peers ; compete with them and it's all about proprietary information and it's all about beating them to the market, isn't it? Or that's how the industry is kind of work traditionally. And now we're asking them to come together to collaborate on them. But this could actually make the difference to spark innovation in this field. "	

All these barriers seem to be closely interconnected. One could debate the source for less public-private innovative efforts in Neurodegeneration compared to Oncology is tied with the lack of societal push in an area with perceived lower unmet need and poor mechanisms for value definition.

Despite the huge potential and very recent triggers of catapult with amyloid cases in AD, interviews show that some Investors still perceive the Return on Investment (RoI) in the field as more uncertain compared to Oncology:

Barrier	Exerts from panel interviews	Comments
Perception of high financial risk and lack of pull incentives to reward investment in this market	<i>"There's still investment hesitance. You look around, there's still not as many players (comparing to Oncology) working in this area, right? You can get approval and not get reimbursed and therefore there's no return. (...) Precisely because it's so big, because perhaps if it was not so big and being given so early, they will not worry. I think that's the paradox. They won't get to blockbuster fast. It'll take long time. Not just because of reimbursement and access, but also because diagnosis is not in place, right. So, there's no good funnels for diagnosis."</i>	Call for pull incentives that reduce investment at risk, with leaner paths to market coupled with the appropriate access mechanisms.
	<i>"Actually, I think a lot of the investors are going to be looking at the case of locator map and seeing what happens. I think a lot of people will be kind of spooked. It will say like, OK, maybe, yeah. Maybe investing a billion to get this. I'm not so sure. It'll be a real shame if investment does not grow because it's one of the huge medical needs in society right now, but again the market then dynamics have to reward it."</i>	

Overall, the oncology data over past decades, showed that general private investment in the field through different ventures tends to soar as the market start to exhibit natural pull incentives. Literature suggest (J. Donavon, 2018) that the type of disease has little impact level of market returns in an event of a successful new approval. With Neurodegeneration ecosystem consistently pursuing accelerated pathways, overtime the capitalisation benefits would be expected to be similar to the ones showed by the analysis of Oncology quantitative data, where market shows a very positive response to AA compared to full approvals, especially in NASDAQ listed companies. These findings show that AA provide a chance for earlier capitalisation for shareholders, and eventual earlier revenue stream, that can be deployed in earlier development investment and incentivise competition for innovation and deeper venture in continuous scientific breakthrough.

Literature shows that in general the market tends to react more intensively to negative than positive approval news. Yet, the Alzheimer's case studies highlighted high magnitude of reactions to both positive and negative news, with significative drug class effect across other Neuro companies such as Lilly, Eisai, or Roche. The case studies also confirmed the hypothesis from literature review that those approvals with higher level of social media focus have higher reaction from the market.

5.2.2 Opportunities for fungible strategies

In Oncology ecosystem, unlike in Neurodegeneration, the risks of developing a new therapy seem to be widely shared across different stakeholders. Compared to other fields that are limited by traditional development pathways, in oncology the *"Access versus Evidence conundrum"* is more pushed to the access side of the equation. In traditional settings most of the investment risk in early development is on the shoulders of private firms. With the described consequence that they might prioritise development strategies that primarily provide more value for shareholders (meaning with less risk and certain RoI) instead of venturing in development that maximise value for all stakeholders (patients, caregivers, health systems, etc.).

If the Oncology paradigm is translated to Neurodegeneration there is the potential to catapult the investment in this field, as it happened in Oncology:

Opportunity	Exerts from panel interviews	Comments
<p>Adopt Oncology-like risk-sharing approaches with cycles of limited and accelerated approvals</p>	<p><i>"Many of us would love to see more of a gradual process of approval where you get enough data to get on the market as soon as possible and those should be mainly safety data and some hints of efficacy. And then you keep recertifying your approval by bringing in more data and more data. That would shorten the time to get real world data actually and also then give the regulator much more interesting data because it would actually be data from the real clinical setting and not an artificial clinical trial."</i></p>	<p>There is a drive from interviewed stakeholders to translate oncology's precision medicine & limited approval strategies into the neurodegeneration field.</p>
	<p><i>"(...) I think that concept of more of a process of approval rather than an event in time, more of a continuous research. (...) Because right now the system (referring to Neurodegeneration space) is just too inefficient. Frankly, we also don't always have good enough drugs. But even when we do have good enough drugs, the system is very inefficient. It's very slow."</i></p>	<p>Identified the need of cultural shift, to see drug approvals more as an agile and continuous research process, instead of a single 'magic' moment.</p>
	<p><i>" Instead of doing a big phase three study and having to enrol 1000 patients so that you can see a small effect size changing the slope over two-year study. Maybe you can do a smaller study with an enriched population or you can do a bigger study and just submit a prespecified subpopulation analysis and show that for patients with certain mutation, or risk factors like being an Ashkenazi Jew or and having a loss of sense of smell etc. These things will predict past accelerators and so you can have it approval for them because we're relatively confident there's an effect there (...) But doing it up front and saying this is part of our strategy to get on the market. And then having a clear expansion plan afterwards I think is important."</i></p>	<p>Stratification of patient subpopulations based on biomarkers was a key factor of success in oncology ecosystem. Neurodegeneration field should invest harder on the exploration of similar strategies, defining it early on since the discovery stages of their programs, and committing to those strategies up front.</p>
<p>Using the right phasing on a value-based pricing strategy that matches the limited approval paradigm</p>	<p><i>" (Biogen) if they had a less aggressive pricing strategy, it might not have been an issue, and you'd still probably have some clinicians questioning some data and how meaningful the results were. But certainly not creating the same very hostile environments for them."</i></p>	<p>Findings show that dynamic accelerated approvals are of limited value if not coupled with the appropriate value-based access mechanisms.</p>
	<p><i>" (...) Launch the drug but (...) hold on to that money and their escrow or something until the drug passes a final regulatory hurdle to say it's a fully approved drug."</i></p> <p><i>"This initial phase, our goal at Eisai is not generating demand or generating sales. It's really getting the ecosystem ready"</i></p>	
	<p><i>" (...) So if you're looking at Parkinson's or Alzheimer's, which are massive patient populations. Data collection infrastructure lacks linkages between the different data sets and there is lack of coherence in terms of data governance and all of these things. The reassessment should be after a few years in real world to see, OK, what's now that we have more mature evidence. How does that price? We negotiated stack up towards that."</i></p>	<p>Findings show the need for pull incentives capable of raising the investment towards real-world infrastructures that would allow more evidence generation being shifted after launch in strong support of value-based dynamic pricing models, including pull for price moving up with the additional evidence of real-world drug performance.</p>

A small hint of the potential of these opportunities was already seen with the raise of investment in the neurodegeneration field after the leap of faith of Aduhelm.

Fig 65 – In traditional paradigm price and reimbursement is negotiated only based on randomized clinical trials data and is more or less static after its first market entrance and until its loss of exclusivity. In the proposed new concept of dynamic accelerated approvals, drug pricing evolves from AA to FA based on performance of drug in real world (possible AA P_B evolution into P_A , P_C , or P_D at full approval). Use of adapted value-based mechanism for reimbursement since the start of AA and evolving with real life drug performance.

The shift in this paradigm requires early strategy negotiations with regulatory agencies and build-up of creative access mechanisms with payors that allow for value-based price increases based on demonstration of drug performance in real-life clinical setting. Findings in oncology showed the combination of these factors was at the basis for deeper investment in early R&D including biomarkers exploration.

It can also be an opportunity for earlier revenue stream within the limited period of market exclusivity. During the initial period of limited accelerated approval, the drug could be at a lower price and in a restrictive population with lower demand. However, the overall total cumulated revenue (area under the curve) at the end of Loss of Exclusivity (LoE) would still be higher in a scenario that starts with AA and afterwards is converted to full approval, compared to a scenario where the company waits for a traditional full approval pathway to first enter the market.

Fig 66 - Theoretical illustration of a model of total cumulated revenue along the product Lifecycle (area under the curve) in a scenario GREEN: where the drug first enters the market with an accelerated approval with a lower price that is later increased once converted to full approval (similar to what was observed in Oncology Quantative data) ; RED: drug enter the market later waiting for Ph3 trial confirmation data with a higher drug price. The total cumulated revenue and the Net Product Value for the company would be higher in the GREEN scenario.

Eisai Leadership already translated some of these approaches in their decisions, when planned for a phased commercial strategy with the first limited approval aimed to prepare the ecosystem and establishing trust, leaving the revenue upscaling to the second phase. By focusing on defining and communicating value through press release in the first phase, they promoted the “closure of some of the still open valves” by thoroughly explaining the severity of unmet need and the math behind their proposed price, this promoted stakeholders alignment around the acceptance of this innovative pathways.

Findings from qualitative interviews highlighted the inverted U curve hypothesis that people are willing to accept to pay (out of pocket) as the disease threat rises but only until a red line. After which they feel entitled to have it, based on assumption that should be no price tag for a life sentence. That is where the reimbursement aspect is expected at its fullest.

Fig 67- Illustration of the inverted U curve concept found during the qualitative interviews on the relationship between people’s perception of disease threat and their willingness to pay for a therapy.

Oncology therapies are often on the right side of the red line and fully reimbursed. Aduhelm perception of need was probably not on the right side, considering all the controveerse challenges.

Interviewees agreed that the major fault barriers of Aduhelm was linked with the broad label, visibly disconnected from trial data, coupled with detached pricing strategy. However, this was seen as part of joint “grow pain” shared with the Agency that was venturing for the first time in this pathway in disease with such high prevalence and heterogeneous population. In fact, some panellist could not agree that their strategy went completely wrong:

" (Biogen) I'm not sure they made development mistakes because in the end, they had an asset they thought it was interesting. They tested it; they got no signal. They looked at a subpopulation. They thought they had a signal. They went back to the FDA. Nothing about that sounds stupid to me"

This case was certainly a propulsor of increased controversial debates on health systems resources and policies, namely on how accelerated approvals may or not be lessening of the standards, or how the FDA Neurology office may be less or more approachable than other subdivisions. A better use of innovative pricing models would have eased the situation. Biogen could have strategically planned by design for the Coverage with Evidence Development approach, negotiating it as a mid-term compromise, that would expand to full coverage after post-marketing commitment and full approval is achieved. This would be just one, among different alternative potential value-based access strategies.

But at the end it was also the propulsor that pushed for more risk acceptance in a field for patients that had no options for access to disease modification therapies. It has catapulted some positive change reflections, namely spreading the focus on the development of surrogate endpoints in neurological conditions, the raising number of manufactures investing more in the field and pushing for innovative ways to accelerate drugs to the market, while considering best value-based pricing strategies.

Quantitative findings also highlighted other general strategic opportunities:

- Advocate and negotiate with payors and policy makers for dynamic pricing models with commitments where prices could be adjusted up based on good drug performance (currently a major barrier specially in EU). Negotiating a value-based model that allows the potential for prices to be adjusted up based on performance provides an additional market pull for continuous innovation.

"(..)in Europe, invariably the price will be adjusted down. It will not go up. I think in Germany there's a theoretical chance that your price could go up, but in practice it never really does."

- Embrace early joint engagement boards with regulators and payors to minimise the gap between payors and regulators.

"You know you're clearly identifying the friction between regulatory and and access here. Regulators are looking at this more from a kind of safety and scientific perspective. But they don't have any money in the game, you know, whereas what payers are tasked with doing is to manage a finite budget and for them they have lots of different things"

- Proactively strategize since the beginning for accelerated development path based on Ph2 data for drugs with innovative potential, instead of using it only as rescue option to work around when their initial traditional development plans with full Ph3 data does work out as planned. This has proved as a benefit strategy not only in Oncology but already on the case study of Lecanemab versus Aduhelm.
- Use that time period between AA and FA to strengthen surrogate-clinical outcomes correlation in real world setting and use the feedback received from AA to strengthen Ph3 application.

5.2.3 Strategic leadership

Executive leaders have to balance daily tensions when making decisions that impact company profitability versus future growth. But their firms also play a fundamental societal role that is to shape the future of the disease area where they play. The findings on Alzheimer's case studies showed that innovation in this ecosystem benefited from the diversity and constant tensions from different cultural and strategic approaches. On one hand, Biogen leadership, influenced by the risk-taking American culture, and the other, Eisai leadership, based on consensus seeking and avoidance of confrontation.

Fig 68 - Illustration of the concept found during qualitative interviews that describes the positive impact the complementary Cavalier and Conservative leadership tensions had in fostering innovation in the ecosystem.

Qualitative interviews emphasised the positive effect of articulated tensions between “*the disrupter cavaliers*” and “*conservative collaborators*” in sparking innovation in the ecosystem. These complementary leadership styles should be situational and adapted to the specific environment of the company. Despite firms having rooted cultural dimensions that influence their strategic decision making, they should be capable to interchange the styles depending on the arena (e.g., position to market, asset position within class, media pressure, etc.).

From individual drug profit to global disease portfolio value maximisation

Company leaders could take the learnings from the cavalier/conservative leadership analogy from the broader ecosystem level and apply it deeper at their company's portfolio.

In this strategic leadership shift, when managing a company's portfolio, some assets may play the cavalier role in the bigger picture and others may be in for the more conservative run. Altogether, the sum of the parts should benefit the company portfolio and the broader innovation in the ecosystem, even if that means not going for the individual profit maximisation of every single individual asset.

In some environments it could be beneficial for the long run to trade-off the initial price potential of a given asset, while using it to generate evidence and catapult further other three. Launching one faster can open some regulatory doors and generate real clinical practise data that in return could reinforce evidence of value that would maximise the price and demand for the following asset in the pipeline.

Fig 69 - This project proposes to translate the *cavalier-conservative* leadership theory from the ecosystem level at the company's portfolio strategy level. Suggesting that certain companies, instead of aiming for individual asset revenue maximization, should instead shift their paradigm and focus on the broader disease strategy. This means leveraging the tensions from the complementary roles their assets play in their portfolio that ultimately will propel innovation in their disease area.

If a company is focused on a niche therapeutic area, its leadership should be committed to develop this ecosystem and needs to strategize at portfolio and disease level, with different product modalities. This could mean having focused programs to develop biomarkers for a new disease endpoint, using platform trials with all their best assets in their focused disease area or “sacrificing” some of the profit of their cavalier assets in order to maximise the value of the whole portfolio.

Strategizing at the portfolio level, requires having a roadmap of the interplays of each asset for the bigger picture. For example, the “cavalier” asset that the goal is to break ecosystem and generate learnings, the one that is “catapulting”. The assets that should avoid major chancy moves and opt to follow pre-established pathways once the risky doors are opened, the “catapulted” ones. As in chess, the cavalier asset might move faster in all directions to make sure the catapulted asset will have a linear path without checkmate.

Findings also showed that company leadership is often better at defining “*Why & Where to play*”, focusing on the right issues with big unmet needs. Though, most of the strategic errors start to arrive when making decisions on “*How to play*”, meaning, through which pathways, which access mechanisms, which risk trade-offs to make, or which stakeholders to engage. Despite the

analytical nature of this industry, a big component of these strategic decisions are influenced by intuition and tacit knowledge from executives:

*" If all we do is wait for these assets to go through some machine, we call development and then stare at the data and see which data is best. Board don't need highly paid executives to do that. Online chat bot could do that (...) **The art of it is to use our expertise, experience, and intuition.** And external consultation and advice to figure out which hypothesis are actually bolder and more robust. How salient, scientifically interesting and going to do something unique. (...) And it's our job to sort through the three and have kind of a trade-off prioritization based on that."*

Eisai got strategic advantage by making better trade-off correlations around societal forces and price sensitivity than Biogen. In part due to Biogen's champion bias and over-reliance on inside view, that could have been mitigated with a more open collaboration across the innovation helix. Yet, certain credit is to be given to the cavalier leadership from Vounatsos, that gathered some "effort force" that finally started propelling further innovation in the field.

These finding hint that, overtime, with the correct use of accelerated pathways, together with the other stakeholders "effort forces", the neurodegeneration ecosystem can benefit from similar innovation catapult effect as oncology.

However, for biopharmaceuticals companies to successfully adopt accelerated pathways in this field, it is important that their leadership make consistent good strategic decisions, discerning when and how to proactively plan for an **accelerated path (A in Fig 70)** or which cases to stick to more **traditional development (B in Fig 70)** based on internal and external environmental triggers.

Fig 70 - Outline describing the potential pathways and strategic queries company's leadership needs to consider since early stages when designing their development strategies. Their strategic choice of going towards path A or B is dependent on environmental context and the company's broader strategy, namely if the company has a bigger disease portfolio goal.

Considering a scenario where a company is just “**playing the single asset maximization goal**”,

of a company that only has one asset in the given disease area that is not the core of its pipeline, and not planning to lead in the field. Where the market already has some limited first-in-class solutions, and the main driver for development is to aim for best-in-class with thorough confirmatory data. In this environment, the companies might equate the longer development **path B** (Fig 70) where their strategy would be on thorough confirmation of their asset differentiation by profiting from the learnings from an already opened ecosystem and getting a premium price at first market entrance, even if with shorter overall time of market exclusivity. In this scenario, the company should be able to lean on established disease biomarkers and have less strategic pull to venture alone on disease biomarkers exploration.

However, in a situation where the company is “**playing for the bigger disease portfolio goal**”,

of a company that is dedicated to lead in a specific severe disease area with a sized pipeline of two or more assets tackling the disease in related mechanistic approaches. With no available solutions in the markets or clear signs of competitors ahead of their products. Here, the decision making should be founded on the broader disease area strategy and long-term shaping of the ecosystem. This company should consider since the start to venture their ‘cavalier assets’ in a narrowed limited sub-population faster to market through **path A** (Fig 70), probing the use of innovative dynamic study designs for hints of early clinical efficacy, such as dynamic expansion cohorts and platform trials. As well as deeper investment initiatives in biomarkers at the broader disease level in real world clinical setting, with the appropriate intellectual propriety protection for its pioneering biomarker efforts. If the right stakeholders in the ecosystems are engaged and value-based mechanisms actioned, this could be the source of earlier capitalisation and revenues to support further R&D. This would be a strategy for progressive shaping of the ecosystem and pulling further the company pipeline through the effort forces of the cavalier asset, while having confirmatory data ongoing through pathway B that provide evidence for upgraded asset value and demand expansions.

To be successful playing for the bigger disease portfolio strategy and applying accelerated pathways in the development of their innovative therapies, executives need to manage well their external and internal environmental competing forces (described in Fig 71).

Fig 71 - Outline of all tensions that need to be well managed by biopharmaceutical companies developing innovative therapies for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases, when aiming for a disease portfolio strategy per the successful adoption of accelerated development pathways.

Data findings showed that company leaders are more successful in bringing innovative products to market through accelerated pathways when they have: the right flexibility towards uncertainty and risk taking; the right touchpoints across the different external innovation stakeholders; the capacity to co-create with governmental agencies and payors with appropriate mix of push & pull incentives; and the grit to keep long-term sustained financial commitment.

Once executives understand the correlations between the emerging tensions from neurodegeneration external environment described in this paper, they need to build an Innovative Enterprise (Tulum, 2019) that will allow the company to best adopt accelerated development pathways for their innovative therapies.

5.3 Limitations

Critics on scope

In general, the scope of this research project is limited to the US. Considerations of the European market are only sporadically referred in a lighter touch. Assuming that EU ecosystem is slightly more rigid and less attractive for riskier innovation, having a softer analysis on this geography can be a limitation when aiming for a global insight on this topic.

As clarified in the initial aims from this dissertation, when generally referring to 'neurodegeneration' on all analysis throughout this project, the scope was meant to be limited to a specific sub-group of disease that are age-related and with high prevalence such as Alzheimer's. So, there is limitation to apply the reflections from this paper into other diseases within neurodegeneration, that are characterised by faster progression and lower prevalence, among other differentiates.

Quantitative limitations

Given the almost inexistent historical quantitative data on neurodegeneration field, all qualitative data collected (regulatory timelines, pricing, stock market) was in Oncology only. With the limitation that a lot of hypotheses were made assuming that similar quantitative trend would be translated from Oncology into Neurodegeneration.

The methodology for collecting stock market reactions to the approval announcements could be challenged. Namely the selected window period for calculation of CARs between the day before and the day of the announcement. This was chosen by design to make sure the immediate reaction from the market is captured, however it could be a limitation to capture pre-announcement market speculations, and longer post-announcement reactions.

There are inherent limitations on the nature of quantitative research, which has less insights into deeper strategic thinking behind the numbers. But this limitation is hence balanced by the mix methods used in this project.

Qualitative limitations

The organisation and structuring of primary quantitative data was influenced by research background hypotheses and selected theories. As well as by the researcher personal biases and idiosyncrasies. Hence naturally limiting to some extent the final results.

It was defined that eight interviews was the appropriate target for the context of this research sample size to prioritize deeper in-depth discussions with high expertise stakeholders. However, in the optic of critically evaluating this study, one could also argue that increasing the sample size even further to twelve could help to reach data saturation.

6. Conclusion

This project clarified the positive impact that the adoption of accelerated development pathways has had in stimulating increased levels of innovation in the oncology ecosystem.

Accelerated pathways brought opportunities for different stakeholders gains:

- People suffering from severe diseases have earlier access to promising new drugs.
- Regulators can benefit from a mechanism of continuous reduction of therapeutic uncertainty in real world throughout the medicines lifecycle, in a formalised controlled manner.
- Payers can leverage progressive schemes for a continuous flow of information in real clinical setting to support better evidence-based access decisions.
- Industry can increase investment in deeper research exploration with earlier revenue streams and reduction of risk of costly late-stage failures.

Analysis showed Oncology therapies gained (on average) four years of earlier entrance in the market under the US accelerated approval. This enabled a considerable reduction of uncertainty for companies that previously had a tough return-on-investment equation to solve when the initial market entry was limited to traditional long trials required to demonstrate clinical efficacy in overall survival. The shift to accelerated approval paradigms acted as a pull incentive for the market and made companies in the oncology field to progressively compete with higher investments in riskier innovation.

Despite literature evidence pointing that US market still has considerable progress to be made until formal value-based access mechanism are in place, this paper shows that the oncology market organically rewards the additional evidence of drug performance generated during the period of accelerated approval with an average drug price increase of 26% when it is converted to a full approval. This has been a positive informal reward mechanism that pulled for continuous investment to confirm and expand drug value after its first market entrance.

The findings from this project also concluded that financial markets responds more positively to announcements of FDA accelerated approvals of oncology drugs than to its later conversion to full approval. These represents valuable new knowledge in the field, as there was no known published literature to date that compared these variables. It also demonstrates the positive link between earlier firm capitalisation and sustained investment in its R&D costs.

Qualitative research disclosed the social conditions that triggered the “perfect innovation storm” observed in Oncology ecosystem, namely: the strong stakeholders alignment with regards to recognition of disease severity and its unmet need, the flexibility to share development risks among the different innovation intermediaries, and the acceptance to move the *access-versus-evidence* conundrum further in the product lifecycle into real world clinical setting.

This paper concluded that the catapult innovation seen in oncology ecosystem over the past decades was primarily pulled by the positive market dynamics that the proper adoption of FDA accelerated approvals generated. Without those, it would have been infeasible to endure such levels of continuous investment at earlier stages of disease progression and bring continuous value maximisation not only to the shareholders, but to all ecosystem stakeholders.

The qualitative findings of these research contrasted the oncology and neurodegeneration ecosystems, concluding that there has been a lack of innovation pressure in the latter over the past decades. This was due to:

- the weak alignment across various ecosystem stakeholders on the recognition, definition and measure of diseases severity and valuable clinical outcomes;
- the reduced acceptance to share risks between different stakeholders along the development pathways;
- the reduced tolerance for higher drug price environments.

With no historical pressure for innovation, the field has suffered from lack of proactive exploration of disease biomarkers that, could have enabled wider progress on the use of precision medicine and adaptive trial approaches in clinical development as it was witnessed in Oncology. This lower pressure also resulted in lower tracking of public-private brokering initiatives similar to the ones observed in Oncology.

Overall, this has historically attached a perception of high financial risks to this field. Consequently, companies have for long time avoided riskier investments in disease modifying therapies and opted for less uncertain short-term ventures that could reassure more shareholders return but limit long-term value maximisation for the broader stakeholders (health systems, patients, society, etc.).

The fact that the long list of FDA surrogate endpoints only have one is in Neurodegeneration, stresses the lack of innovation in this field. The pull incentives of using accelerated development pathways should spur companies to invest further in collaborative work for the development of broader knowledge of disease populations instead of 'just developing drugs'. With initiatives focused on the development of endpoints that would benefit the development of not only one drug but the boarder portfolio and field innovation.

The analysis of the qualitative findings, led to conclude that most of the strategies that have catapulted innovation in oncology field should be fungible into the Neurodegeneration space. Namely, focusing on cross-stakeholders alignment around disease severity & value definition, and acceptance of risk-sharing among innovation intermediaries with the adoption of accelerated development pathways.

The recent triggers seen on the analysis of Alzheimer's disease case studies showed that the increased flexibility from FDA towards "speed-over-perfection" approach in severe neurodegenerative diseases have sparked competition to move more investment into riskier R&D. The first approvals of disease modifying therapies allow to gather more evidence in real-world clinical setting and help to improve characterisation of disease pathogenesis and correlation with predictive and prognostic biomarkers. This also created momentum in the field that is expected to push for further public-private brokering that facilitates and encourages sharing of large datasets and biomarkers/clinical outcomes correlations. It is also concluded from case studies that the success of these strategies is dependent on the use of the right value-based access mechanisms that should be proactively negotiated with payors and policy makers since the very early exploratory phases.

Even if the core of the paper was focused on US market, some results allow to say that EU ecosystem is still slightly more rigid and less prone for innovative risk taking compared to FDA. This is something that global companies need to be mindful when development global therapies to make sure that the global environment do not risk getting stuck in the old cycle of long sequential development. Stakeholders in the ecosystem need to shift the paradigm and see healthcare as an

investment not a cost, especially in innovation of early stages of disease modification and prevention.

Company leaders have shared accountability to continuously punch ecosystem boundaries and collaborate to find innovative solutions for their areas of expertise. Findings from this paper showed how challenging it can be for healthcare decision makers to take difficult strategic choices and to continuously make sure access to patients is improved. Biopharma leaders do relatively well when defining the vision of *Why* certain healthcare problems deserve special attention, however, often fail when deciding *How* best to tackle them, missing on the quality of their correlations and trade-off judgement.

The neurodegeneration arena needs to embrace and integrate conflicting tensions in order to innovate. Analysed case studies show how cavalier & conservative contrasting leadership tensions contribute to ecosystem breakthrough. This paper also proposes a new thought movement that translates the cavalier-conservative leadership tensions from the broader ecosystem to the level of the companies' portfolio strategy. It is recommended to shift the focus from single drug profit maximization to a broader disease portfolio strategy. The new hypothesis generated by this research is that this shift will support future catapult innovation in the broader ecosystem. This is especially true for companies striving to lead in a specific therapeutic area. They should proactively strategize at disease level with combination of different product modalities, which could mean trading off some of the profit from their cavalier assets and instead use it with the strategic intent of preparing the healthcare ecosystem and maximise the potential of the overall portfolio.

Overall, it is concluded that the initial adoption of accelerated pathways in neurodegeneration was propelled by cavalier effort forces from first Alzheimer's drugs coupled with cross-stakeholders collaboration and sets the field with the potential to benefit from similar innovation catapult effect as seen in Oncology.

In order to effectively adopt these accelerated pathways, executives need to excel in creative thinking and have the capacity to discern from the contextual environment and be able to clearly articulate and align cross-functional stakeholders around a shared value proposition along the early development journey by:

- Proactively define the scenarios each drug is playing in the broader portfolio and design early on which ones have contextual triggers for accelerated approvals.
- Negotiating early with policy makers and payers for more dynamic pricing models, including up-adjustment pull incentives based on real clinical setting data that would match the accelerated regulatory flexibility and accommodate broader portfolio strategic thinking.

In situations where the company has a small pipeline and is not leader in a field that already has some first-in-class solutions on the market, they might still play a more passive macro role and limit themselves to single asset maximisation approaches. However, it is crucial that more companies with sized pipelines start to play a bolder role in their ecosystem and venture in a bigger disease portfolio strategy, designing accelerated pathways with cavalier assets with the intent to catapult the path for the broader portfolio and develop real world solutions at the disease level. Innovative companies playing for the bigger portfolio strategy will require increased organisation integration, strategic control, and financial commitment.

Future learnings

As debated in the limitations section, it would be interesting for future research to do a deeper analysis of this research topic from the angle of the European market. Considering its different policies, financial and strategic implications. This would be valuable knowledge for companies navigating the challenges of development a global product that needs to address different pressures from each geopolitical ecosystem.

It would be interesting to generate more knowledge with additional quantitative variables, e.g., comparing market responses of accelerated approvals with ones that went for full approval since the start; the split of revenue between the periods of accelerated approval and after conversion to full approval; or the comparison of the overall revenues until loss of exclusivity for comparable drugs that followed different strategic paths, between the ones that started with the accelerated approval and later converted to full approval, and the ones that waited to enter the market already with a full approval.

Given the uncertainty around the potential impact on US pharmaceutical market of the Inflation Reduction Act signed by President Biden in 2022, it would also be interesting to investigate further how this legislation could influence the topics addressed in this paper.

References

- Adams, B. (2022) Eisai, ever hopeful for an Alzheimer's drug win, hires former Lilly exec as new commercial lead Fierce Pharma [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/marketing/eisai-ever-hopeful-alzheimers-drug-win-hires-former-lilly-exec-its-new-commercial-lead>(Accessed March 2023)
- Agyeman AS, Siegel JN, Leptak C. (2022) Establishing a Public Resource for Acceptable Surrogate Endpoints to Support FDA Marketing Applications. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 9:820990. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2022.820990>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Albrecht, A, Ascher, J., Menu, P, Peters, M & Stiehl, L. (2018) Oncology drug launch success elements | McKinsey. [online] Available from: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/life-sciences/our-insights/launches-in-oncology-the-elements-of-success>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Alliance for Aging Research. What is ICER and how does it promote discriminatory drug pricing? Advocacy & Support. [online] Available from: <https://www.agingresearch.org/icer-facts/> (Accessed July 2022)
- Alzforum (2021) Lecanemab Follows Aduhelm's Path to Accelerated Approval | ALZFORUM. [online] Available from: <https://www.alzforum.org/news/research-news/lecanemab-follows-aduhelms-path-accelerated-approval>(Accessed March 2023)
- Alzheimer's Association. 2023 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. (2023). *Alzheimer's Dement*, 19: 1598-1695.. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.13016>(Accessed July 2022)
- Alzheimer's Disease International (2022) ADI - Gantenerumab fails to meet primary goal, Gantenerumab fails to meet primary goal | Alzheimer's Disease International (ADI) [online] Available from: <https://www.alzint.org/news-events/news/gantenerumab-fails-to-meet-primary-goal/> (Accessed March 2023)
- Alzheimer's Association (2016). 2016 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 12(4), pp.459–509. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2016.03.001>. (Accessed May 2022)
- Anderer, A., Bastani, H. & Silberholz J. (2022) Adaptive Clinical Trial Designs with Surrogates: When Should We Bother? *Management Science* 2022 68:3, 1982-2002 Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2021.4096> (Accessed July 2022)
- Angelis, A., Lange, A. and Kanavos, P. (2017) Using health technology assessment to assess the value of new medicines: results of a systematic review and expert consultation across eight European countries, *The European Journal of Health Economics*, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 19(1), pp. 123–152, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10198-017-0871-0>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Augustus, S. (2011, July). Drug Development in Oncology: A Regulatory Perspective. *American Journal of Therapeutics*, 18(4), 323–331. <https://doi.org/10.1097/mjt.0b013e3181d1d833>(Accessed June 2022)
- Austin, D. and Hayford, T. (2021). Research and Development in the Pharmaceutical Industry | Congressional Budget Office. [online] Congressional Budget Office. Available from: <https://www.cbo.gov/publication/57126>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/biogen-compiles-buyout-target-list-as-aduhelm-woe-deepens-stat>(Accessed March 2023)
- Avalere Health. (2022). Understanding the History and Use of the Accelerated Approval Pathway. [online] Available from: <https://avalere.com/insights/understanding-the-history-and-use-of-the-accelerated-approval-pathway> (Accessed July 2022)
- Beaver, J. A. et al. (2018) A 25-Year Experience of US Food and Drug Administration Accelerated Approval of Malignant Hematology and Oncology Drugs and Biologics. *JAMA Oncology*. [Online] 4 (6), 849. [online]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamaoncol.2017.5618>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Bell, J. (2022) Biogen, struggling to sell Alzheimer's drug, begins layoffs to save money. *BioPharma Dive* [online] Available from: <https://www.biopharmadive.com/news/biogen-layoffs-jobs-aduhelm/619768/>(Accessed December 2022)
- Bendicksen, L. (2020) Changing Drug Market Dynamics: An Interview with Craig Garthwaite. *The Incidental Economist* [online] Available from: <https://theincidentaleconomist.com/wordpress/changing-drug-market-dynamics-an-interview-with-craig-garthwaite/> (Accessed July 2022)
- Bendicksen, L. (2020), Interview with Craig Garthwaite, health economist and with research focused on the relationship between drug prices and innovation. *Incidental Economist*.
- Bendicksen, L. (2020). (2020). Incentivizing High-Value Drug Development: An Interview with Dr. Peter Bach. *The Incidental Economist* [online] Available from: <https://theincidentaleconomist.com/wordpress/incentivizing-high-value-drug-development-an-interview-with-dr-peter-bach/> (Accessed July 2022)
- Berman, E. P. (2014). Not Just Neoliberalism: Economization in US Science and Technology Policy. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 39(3), 397–431. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243913509123> (Accessed December 2022)
- Bhambra, R. (2022). High-value dealmaking strengthens big pharma's CNS ambitions. *Biopharma Dealmakers*. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d43747-022-00178-3>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Biogen (2020) Biogen to Webcast Prerecorded Presentation on Aducanumab Embark Study Design and Live Q&A from CTAD on November 4, 2020. Biogen [Online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/biogen-webcast-prerecorded-presentation-aducanumab-embark-study>
- Biogen (2020) Update on FDA Advisory Committee's Meeting on Aducanumab in Alzheimer's Disease Biogen [Online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/update-fda-advisory-committees-meeting-aducanumab-alzheimers>(Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen (2021) A Letter from Biogen's CEO on ADUHELM Biogen [Online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/letter-biogens-ceo-aduhelm>(Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen (2021) An open letter to the Alzheimer's disease community from our Head of Research and Development, Alfred Sandrock, M.D., Ph.D. Biogen, [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/open-letter-alzheimers-disease-community-our-head-research-and>. (Accessed March 2023)

- Biogen (2021) Biogen Announces Reduced Price for ADUHELM® to Improve Access for Patients with Early Alzheimer's Disease . Biogen. [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/biogen-announces-reduced-price-aduhelm-improve-access-patients>. (Accessed December 2022)
- Biogen (2021) Eisai and Biogen Inc. Announce U.S. FDA Grants Breakthrough Therapy Designation for LECANEMAB (BAN2401), an Anti-Amyloid Beta Protofibril Antibody for the Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease Biogen [Online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/eisai-and-biogen-inc-announce-us-fda-grants-breakthrough-therapy>(Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen (2021) FDA grants accelerated approval for ADUHELM™ as the first and only Alzheimer's disease treatment to address a defining pathology of the disease. Biogen [Online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/fda-grants-accelerated-approval-aduhelmtm-first-and-only>(Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen (2022) Biogen Names Christopher Viehbacher President and Chief Executive Officer Biogen [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/biogen-names-christopher-viehbacher-president-and-chief>(Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen (2022) Eisai Presents Full Results of Lecanemab Phase 3 Confirmatory Clarity Ad Study for Early Alzheimer's Disease At Clinical Trials On Alzheimer's Disease (Ctad) Conference Biogen [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/eisai-presents-full-results-lecanemab-phase-3-confirmatory> (Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen(2021). Investigational Alzheimer's Disease Therapy Lecanemab Granted FDA Fast Track Designation | Biogen. [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/investigational-alzheimers-disease-therapy-lecanemab-granted-fda>(Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen. (2021). Biogen R&D Day to Provide Overview of Diversified Pipeline and Capabilities with Potential for Multiple Novel Therapies in Neuroscience | Biogen. [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/biogen-rd-day-provide-overview-diversified-pipeline-and> (Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen. (2021). Eisai Initiates Rolling Submission to the U.S. FDA for Biologics License Application of Lecanemab (BAN2401) for Early Alzheimer's Disease Under the Accelerated Approval Pathway Biogen. [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/eisai-initiates-rolling-submission-us-fda-biologics-license> (Accessed March 2023)
- Biogen. (2022). Lecanemab Confirmatory Phase 3 Clarity Ad Study Met Primary Endpoint, Showing Highly Statistically Significant Reduction Of Clinical Decline In Large Global Clinical Study Of 1,795 Participants With Early Alzheimer's Disease Biogen [online] Available from: <https://investors.biogen.com/news-releases/news-release-details/lecanemab-confirmatory-phase-3-clarity-ad-study-met-primary>(Accessed March 2023)
- Bloom, D.E., Cafiero, E.T., Jané-Llopis, E., Abrahams-Gessel, S., Bloom, L.R., Fathima, S., Feigl, A.B., Gaziano, T., Mowafi, M., Pandya, A., Prettner, K., Rosenberg, L., Seligman, B., Stein, A.Z., & Weinstein, C. (2011). The Global Economic Burden of Noncommunicable Diseases. Geneva: World Economic Forum. Available from: https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Harvard_HE_GlobalEconomicBurdenNonCommunicableDiseases_2011.pdf (Accessed June 2022)
- Bloomberg (2022) Eisai CEO Bets On Alzheimer's Drug Approval. Bloomberg [online] Available from: <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/videos/2022-10-13/eisai-ceo-bets-on-alzheimer-s-drug-approval-video> (Accessed March 2023)
- Blume-Kohout, M.E. (2012). Does Targeted, Disease-Specific Public Research Funding Influence Pharmaceutical Innovation? *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 31(3), pp.641–660. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pam.21640>. (Accessed Jun 2022)
- Blume-Kohout, M.E. and Sood, N. (2013). Market size and innovation: Effects of Medicare Part D on pharmaceutical research and development. *Journal of Public Economics*, 97, pp.327–336. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2012.10.003>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Brennan, Z. (2022) The accelerated approval pathway is evolving in plain sight, with or without congressional help, *Endpoints News*, [online] Available from: <https://endpts.com/the-accelerated-approval-pathway-is-evolving-in-plain-sight-with-or-without-congressional-help/>.(Accessed June 2022)
- Budish, E., Roin, B. N. and Williams, H. (2015) Do Firms Underinvest in Long-Term Research? Evidence from Cancer Clinical Trials, *American Economic Review*, American Economic Association, 105(7), pp. 2044–2085, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1257/aer.20131176>. (Accessed July 2022)
- By 1. Fierce Biotech [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercebiotech.com/biotech/winner-crowned-head-head-battle-between-lilly-and-biogens-alzheimers-drugs>(Accessed March 2023)
- Califf, R. M. (2017). Balancing the Need for Access With the Imperative for Empirical Evidence of Benefit and Risk. *JAMA*, 318(7), 614. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.9412> (Accessed August 2022)
- Calvert, M. J., Marston, E., Samuels, M., Rivera, S. C., Torlinska, B., Oliver, K., Denniston, A. K. and Hoare, S. (2020) Advancing UK regulatory science and innovation in healthcare, *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, SAGE Publications, 114(1), pp. 5–11, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0141076820961776>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Carey, T. (2022) The Top Line': The initial reactions to Biogen's new CEO, plus this week's headlines. *Fierce Pharma* [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/fierce-biotech-homepage/top-line-biogens-new-ceo-plus-weeks-headlines>(Accessed March 2023)
- Carpenter, D., Kesselheim, A.S. and Joffe, S. (2011). Reputation and Precedent in the Bevacizumab Decision. *New England Journal of Medicine* [Online], 365(2), p.e3. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmp1107201>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services. CMS Finalizes Medicare Coverage Policy for Monoclonal Antibodies Directed Against Amyloid for the Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease | CMS.gov [online] Available from: <https://www.cms.gov/newsroom/press-releases/cms-finalizes-medicare-coverage-policy-monoclonal-antibodies-directed-against-amyloid-treatmen> (Accessed December 2022)
- Chappell, B. (2021) 3 Experts Have Resigned From An FDA Committee Over Alzheimer's Drug Approval. *NPR* [online]. Available from: <https://www.npr.com/2021/06/11/1005567149/3-experts-have-resigned-from-an-fda-committee-over-alzheimers-drug-approval?t=1656590685963>(Accessed December 2022)
- Chen, E. et al (2020), FDA Acceptance of Surrogate End Points for Cancer Drug Approval: 1992-2019. *JAMA Internal Medicine*
- Chen, E.Y., Haslam, A. and Prasad, V. (2020). FDA Acceptance of Surrogate End Points for Cancer Drug Approval: 1992-2019. *JAMA Internal Medicine* [Online], 180(6), p.912. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.1097>. (Accessed March 2023)

- Cherla, A., Naci, H., Kesselheim, A. S., Gyawali, B. and Mossialos, E. (2021) Assessment of Coverage in England of Cancer Drugs Qualifying for US Food and Drug Administration Accelerated Approval. *JAMA Internal Medicine*, American Medical Association (AMA), 181(4), p. 490, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.8441>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Comanor, W. S. (2007) *The Economics of Research and Development in the Pharmaceutical Industry*, Pharmaceutical Innovation, Cambridge University Press, pp. 54–72, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511618871.004>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (2018) Guideline on the clinical investigation of medicines for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. CPMP/EWP/553/95 Rev.2 CMPH [Online] Available from: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/guideline-clinical-investigation-medicines-treatment-alzheimers-disease-revision-2_en.pdf
- Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (2021) Withdrawal Assessment - report Aduhelm - International non-proprietary name: aducanumab Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/005558/0000 EMA/CHMP/557556/2022. CMPH [Online] Available from: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/withdrawal-report/withdrawal-assessment-report-aduhelm_en.pdf. (Accessed March 2023)
- Crossover Health (2023). Christopher Viehbacher. Crossover Health [online] Available from: <https://crossoverhealth.com/leaders/christopher-viehbacher/>(Accessed March 2023)
- Cubanski, J. & all (2023) *How will the prescription drug provisions in the inflation reduction act affect Medicare beneficiaries?* KFF Health News Available from: <https://www.kff.org/medicare/issue-brief/how-will-the-prescription-drug-provisions-in-the-inflation-reduction-act-affect-medicare-beneficiaries/> (Accessed February 2023)
- Cummings, J. and Fox, N. (2017). Defining Disease Modifying Therapy for Alzheimer's Disease. *The Journal of Prevention of Alzheimer's Disease*, [online] 4(2), pp.109–115. doi:10.14283/jpad.2017.12.
- Cummings, J. L. (2008). Optimizing phase II of drug development for disease-modifying compounds. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 4(1S1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2007.10.002> (Accessed July 2022)
- Cummings, J., Aisen, P., Barton, R., Bork, J., Doody, R., Dwyer, J., Egan, J. C., Feldman, H., Lappin, D., Truyen, L., Salloway, S., Sperling, R., & Vradenburg, G. (2016). Re-Engineering Alzheimer Clinical Trials: Global Alzheimer's Platform Network. *The Journal of Prevention of Alzheimer's Disease*, 1–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.14283/jpad.2016.93> (Accessed July 2022)
- Cummings, J., Aisen, P.S., DuBois, B., Frölich, L., Jack, C.R., Jones, R.W., Morris, J.C., Raskin, J., Dowsett, S.A. and Scheltens, P. (2016). Drug development in Alzheimer's disease: the path to 2025. *Alzheimer's Research & Therapy*, [online] 8(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13195-016-0207-9>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Cummings, J., Lee, G., Ritter, A. and Zhong, K. (2018). Alzheimer's disease drug development pipeline: 2018. *Alzheimer's & Dementia: Translational Research & Clinical Interventions*, [online] 4, pp.195–214. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trci.2018.03.009>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Cummings, J., Ritter, A. and Zhong, K. (2018). Clinical Trials for Disease-Modifying Therapies in Alzheimer's Disease: A Primer, Lessons Learned, and a Blueprint for the Future. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 64(s1), pp.S3–S22. doi:10.3233/jad-179901.
- Cummings, J., Ritter, A. and Zhong, K. (2018). Clinical Trials for Disease-Modifying Therapies in Alzheimer's Disease: A Primer, Lessons Learned, and a Blueprint for the Future. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 64(s1), pp.S3–S22. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.3233/jad-179901>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Cummings, J.L. (2008). Optimizing phase II of drug development for disease-modifying compounds. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 4(1S1), pp.S15–S20. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2007.10.002>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Dagenais, S., Russo, L., Madsen, A., Webster, J. and Becnel, L. (2022). Use of Real-World Evidence to Drive Drug Development Strategy and Inform Clinical Trial Design. *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, [online] 111(1), pp.77–89. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1002/cpt.2480>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Dagher, R. et al. (2004) Accelerated Approval of Oncology Products: A Decade of Experience. *JNCI Journal of the National Cancer Institute*. [Online] 96 (20), 1500–1509. [online]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djh279>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Dasari, S. and Bernard Tchounwou, P. (2014). Cisplatin in cancer therapy: Molecular mechanisms of action. *European Journal of Pharmacology*, [online] 740(1), pp.364–378. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2014.07.025> (Accessed October 2022)
- Dawson, V. L., & Dawson, T. M. (2019). Promising disease-modifying therapies for Parkinson's disease. *Science Translational Medicine*, 11(520). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.aba1659> (Accessed June 2022)
- Dawson, V.L. and Dawson, T.M. (2019). Promising disease-modifying therapies for Parkinson's disease. *Science Translational Medicine*, [online] 11(520). doi:10.1126/scitranslmed.aba1659.
- de Jong, M., Marston, N. and Roth, E. (2015). The eight essentials of innovation | McKinsey. [online] www.mckinsey.com. Available from: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/strategy-and-corporate-finance/our-insights/the-eight-essentials-of-innovation>. (Accessed October 2022)
- Dhingra, K. (2015) Oncology 2020: a drug development and approval paradigm. *Annals of Oncology*, Elsevier BV, 26(11), pp. 2347–2350, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdv353>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Dhingra, K. (2015, November). Oncology 2020: a drug development and approval paradigm. *Annals of Oncology*, 26(11), 2347–2350. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdv353> (Accessed June 2022)
- DiMasi, J.A. and Grabowski, H.G. (2007). Economics of New Oncology Drug Development. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 25(2), pp.209–216. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2006.09.0803>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Doroshov, D. B., & Doroshov, J. H. (2019, July). From the Broad Phase II Trial to Precision Oncology: A Perspective on the Origins of Basket and Umbrella Clinical Trial Designs in Cancer Drug Development. *The Cancer Journal*, 25(4), 245–253. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/ppo.0000000000000386> (Accessed July 2022)
- Eckford, C. (2023) Eisai submits MAA for lecanemab in Europe. *European Pharmaceutical Review* [online] Available from: <https://www.europeanpharmaceuticalreview.com/news/178399/eisai-submits-maa-for-lecanemab-in-europe/>(Accessed March 2023)

- Eisai Co., Ltd. (2023). Eisai's Approach to U.S. Pricing for Leqembitm (Lecanemab)
- Eisai US (2023). Eisai Submits Supplemental Biologics License Application to FDA for Traditional Approval of LEQEMBITM (lecanemab-irmb) for the Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease. Eisai
- Eisai US (2023). FDA Approves LEQEMBITM (lecanemab-irmb) Under the Accelerated Approval Pathway for the Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease. Eisai [online] Available from: <https://media-us.eisai.com/2023-01-06-FDA-Approves-LEQEMBI-TM-lecanemab-irmb-Under-the-Accelerated-Approval-Pathway-for-the-Treatment-of-Alzheimers-Disease>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Eisai US (2023). FDA Approves LEQEMBITM (lecanemab-irmb) Under the Accelerated Approval Pathway for the Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease. Eisai US [online] Available from: <https://media-us.eisai.com/2023-01-06-FDA-Approves-LEQEMBI-TM-lecanemab-irmb-Under-the-Accelerated-Approval-Pathway-for-the-Treatment-of-Alzheimers-Disease>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Emanuel, E. J. (2021) A Middle Ground for Accelerated Drug Approval—Lessons From Aducanumab. JAMA, American Medical Association (AMA), 326(14), p. 1367, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.14861>. (Accessed March 2023)
- European Commission. A pharmaceutical strategy for Europe. Health.ec.europa.eu [online] Available from: https://health.ec.europa.eu/medicinal-products/pharmaceutical-strategy-europe_en(Accessed July 2022)
- European Medicines Agency (2016) Adaptive Pathways Workshop Report. European Medicines Agency [online] Available from: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/adaptive-pathways-workshop-report-meeting-stakeholders-8-december-2016_en.pdf
- European Medicines Agency (2016) Final report on the adaptive pathways pilot. EMA/276376/2016 European Medicines Agency [online] Available from: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/final-report-adaptive-pathways-pilot_en.pdf. (Accessed October 2022)
- European Medicines Agency (2017) Conditional Marketing Authorisation: Report on Ten Years of Experience at the European Medicines Agency. London, England
- FDA-NIH Biomarker Working Group. (2020). Reasonably Likely Surrogate Endpoint. [online] www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov. Silver Spring: Food and Drug Administration (US)., Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK453485/> (Accessed July 2022)
- Feuerstein, A & Garde, D. (2021). Biogen's reckoning: How the Aduhelm debacle pushed a troubled company and its fractured leadership to the brink. STAT. [online] Available from: <https://www.statnews.com/2021/12/08/biogen-aduhelm-al-sandrock-michel-vounatsos-company-reckoning/> (Accessed March 2023)
- Frontier Economics (2014) Rates of return to investment in science and innovation A Report Prepared For The Department For Business, Innovation And Skills Frontier Economics Ltd, London [online] Available from: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/333006/bis-14-990-rates-of-return-to-investment-in-science-and-innovation-revised-final-report.pdf. (Accessed July 2022)
- Gatlin, A. (2021). The Fight Against Alzheimer's Reaches A Moment Of Truth For Biogen, Other Biotech Stocks. [online] Investor's Business Daily. Available from: <https://www.investors.com/news/technology/biogen-stock-and-aducanumab-what-this-alzheimers-treatment-means-for-biotech-stocks/> (Accessed March 2023)
- Giglio, P. and Micklus, A. (2023). Biopharma dealmaking in 2022. Nature Reviews Drug Discovery. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41573-023-00012-0>. (Accessed June 2022)
- GOV.UK. (2021). New plans to put UK at front of global innovation race. [online] Available from: https://www.gov.uk/government/news/new-plans-to-put-uk-at-front-of-global-innovation-race_(Accessed June 2022)
- Grace, C (2009) Comparative advantages of push and pull incentives for technology development: lessons for neglected diseases. [Online] Global Forum Update on Research for Health Volume 6. (Accessed June 2022)
- Groenewegen, A. (2019). Kahneman fast and slow thinking. [online] SUE Behavioural Design. Available from: <https://suebehaviouraldesign.com/kahneman-fast-slow-thinking> (Accessed June 2022)
- Grogan, R. (2022) Pivotal Period For Irlab And Its Parkinson's Pipeline Scrip . [online] Scrip Available from: <https://scrip.pharmaintelligence.informa.com/SC147148/Pivotal-Period-For-Irlab-And-Its-Parkinsons-Pipeline> . (Accessed June 2022)
- Gronde, T. van der, Uyl-de Groot, C. A. and Pieters, T. (2017) Addressing the challenge of high-priced prescription drugs in the era of precision medicine: A systematic review of drug life cycles, therapeutic drug markets and regulatory frameworks, PLOS ONE, Mihalopoulos, C. (ed.), Public Library of Science (PLoS), 12(8), p. e0182613, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0182613>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Grover, N. and Mishra, M. (2022). Biogen shares soar on landmark Alzheimer's data, lift rivals. Reuters. [online] 28 Sep. Available from: <https://www.reuters.com/business/healthcare-pharmaceuticals/biogen-eisai-stocks-soar-alzheimers-success-lifting-rival-shares-2022-09-28/>(Accessed March 2023)
- Gusmano, M. K. (2022) Aduhelm and the Politics of Drug Approval in the United States, Public Policy & Aging Report Volume 32, Issue 2, 2022, Pages 66–71 [online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ppar/prac005>(Accessed December 2022)
- Gyawali, B., Hey, S. P. and Kesselheim, A. S. (2020) Evaluating the evidence behind the surrogate measures included in the FDA's table of surrogate endpoints as supporting approval of cancer drugs, EClinicalMedicine, Elsevier BV, 21, p. 100332, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100332>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Gyawali, B., Hey, S.P. and Kesselheim, A.S. (2019). Assessment of the Clinical Benefit of Cancer Drugs Receiving Accelerated Approval. JAMA Internal Medicine, 179(7), p.906. Available from :<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2019.0462> (Accessed June 2022)
- Gyawali, B., Hey, S.P., and Kesselheim, A.S. (2019) Assessment of the Clinical Benefit of Cancer Drugs Receiving Accelerated Approval. JAMA Internal Medicine [online] 179 (7), 906. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2019.0462> (Accessed July 2022)

- Haigh, J. (2015) Medicines Adaptive Pathways to Patients (MAPPs): Saving Time, Saving Lives Efpia [online] Available from: https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.efpia.eu%2Fmedia%2F25535%2Fmapps-saving-time-saving-lives_-ppts.pptx&wdOrigin=BROWSELINK (Accessed September 2022)
- Haslam, A., Hey, S. P., Gill, J. and Prasad, V. (2019) A systematic review of trial-level meta-analyses measuring the strength of association between surrogate end-points and overall survival in oncology, *European Journal of Cancer*, Elsevier BV, 106, pp. 196–211, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2018.11.012>. (Accessed August 2022)
- Helmore, E. (2022). FDA under fire over approval of Alzheimer's drug Aduhelm. *The Guardian*. [online] 29 Dec. Available from: <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2022/dec/29/biogen-fda-alzheimers-aduhelm-congressional-report>(Accessed December 2022)
- Hemmings, R. (2015) EMA Adaptive licensing: a tool concept for accelerated access to innovative medicines? *European Medicines Agency* [online] Available from: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/presentation/presentation-european-medicines-agency-adaptive-licensing-tool-concept-accelerated-access-innovative_en.pdf (Accessed Dec 2022)
- Higgins-Dunn N. (2021) Biogen's shockingly broad Aduhelm label—and \$56K price—set up a \$10B launch, analysts say. *FiercePharma* [Online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/alzheimer-s-fda-nod-bag-biogen-faces-historic-drug-launch-and-10b-potential-sales-analysts>(Accessed December 2022)
- Higgins-Dunn, N. (2021) Biogen's shockingly broad Aduhelm label—and \$56K price—set up a \$10B launch, analysts say. *Fierce Pharma* [Online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/alzheimer-s-fda-nod-bag-biogen-faces-historic-drug-launch-and-10b-potential-sales-analysts>(Accessed March 2023)
- Hoekman, J. et al. (2015) Use of the conditional marketing authorization pathway for oncology medicines in Europe. *Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics*. [Online] 98 (5), 534–541. [online]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cpt.174>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Hoekman, J., Boon, W., Bouvy, J., Ebbers, H., de Jong, J. and De Bruin, M. (2015) Use of the conditional marketing authorization pathway for oncology medicines in Europe, *Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, Wiley, 98(5), pp. 534–541, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cpt.174>.
- Huber, M. & Huber, B. (2019) Innovation in Oncology Drug Development. *Journal of Oncology*. [Online] 20191–16. [online]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2019/9683016>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Huber, M. and Huber, B. (2019) Innovation in Oncology Drug Development, *Journal of Oncology*, Hindawi Limited, 2019, pp. 1–16, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2019/9683016>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Huber, M. and Huber, B. (2019). Innovation in Oncology Drug Development. *Journal of Oncology*, [online] 2019, pp.1–16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9683016>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Huber, M., & Huber, B. (2019). Innovation in Oncology Drug Development. *Journal of Oncology*, 2019, 1–16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9683016> (Accessed July 2022)
- Huber, M., & Huber, B. (2019, November 23). Innovation in Oncology Drug Development. *Journal of Oncology*, 2019, 1–16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9683016>(Accessed July 2022)
- Hughes, M. (2005) Experience with the Validation of Surrogate Endpoints in HIV EMEA / CHMP. *Biomarkers Workshop*. *ema.europa.eu* [online] Available from: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/presentation/validation-biomarkers-hiv-michael-d-hughes_en.pdf (Accessed July 2022)
- Hutton, J., Trueman, P. and Henshall, C. (2007) Coverage with Evidence Development: An examination of conceptual and policy issues, *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, Cambridge University Press (CUP), 23(4), pp. 425–432, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/s0266462307070651>. (Accessed July 2022)
- IQVIA (2022) Global Oncology Trends 2022 and outlook to 2026. Available from: <https://www.iqvia.com/-/media/iqvia/pdfs/institute-reports/global-oncology-trends-2022/iqvia-institute-global-oncology-trends-2022-forweb.pdf> (Accessed June 2022)
- Javadi SF, Giebel C, Khan MA and Hashim MJ (2021). Epidemiology of Alzheimer's disease and other dementias: rising global burden and forecasted trends [version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations]. *F1000Research* 2021, 10:425 Available from: <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.50786.1>(Accessed July 2022)
- Johnson JR, Ning YM, Farrell A, Justice R, Keegan P, Pazdur R. Accelerated approval of oncology products: the Food and Drug Administration experience. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2011; 103(8): 636- 644. [online]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djr062> (Accessed July 2022)
- Johnson, J.R., Ning, Y.-M., Farrell, A., Justice, R., Keegan, P. and Pazdur, R. (2011). Accelerated Approval of Oncology Products: The Food and Drug Administration Experience. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 103(8), pp.636–644. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djr062>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Kaaniche, A., Troubat, A. and Sherwood, A. (2015) Does Conditional Marketing Authorisation Influence Market Access in France, England, and Germany?, *Value in Health*, Elsevier BV, 18(7), p. A559, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2015.09.1815>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Kansteiner, F. (2022) Biogen CEO Vounatsos summons support to fight Aduhelm's paralyzing coverage decision. *Fierce Pharma* [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/biogen-ceo-vounatsos-issues-call-to-action-after-aduhelm-s-paralyzing-coverage-decision>(Accessed March 2023)
- Kansteiner, F. (2022) As US launch falters, Biogen ditches Aduhelm application in Europe. *Fierce Pharma* [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/aduhelm-loses-another-potential-sales-avenue-biogen-pulls-marketing-application-europe>(Accessed December 2022)
- Kansteiner, F. (2022) Biogen deflects claims it misled shareholders about Aduhelm's success *Fierce Pharma* [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/biogen-deflects-claims-it-misled-shareholders-about-aduhelms-success> (Accessed March 2023)

- Kansteiner, F. (2022) J&J research vet Mathai Mammen a top contender in Biogen's hunt for a new CEO: Stat Fierce Pharma [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/jj-research-vet-mathai-mammen-rumored-top-pick-biogens-hunt-new-ceo-report>
- Karran, E. and De Strooper, B. (2022) The amyloid hypothesis in Alzheimer disease: new insights from new therapeutics, *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 21(4), pp. 306–318, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41573-022-00391-w>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Katz, J., Kliff, S. and Sanger-Katz, M. (2021). New Drug Could Cost the Government as Much as It Spends on NASA. *The New York Times*. [online] 22 Jun. Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/06/22/upshot/alzheimers-aduhelm-medicare-cost.html>. (Accessed December 2022)
- Kerry, C. and Danson, M. (2016). Open Innovation, Triple Helix and Regional Innovation Systems. *Industry and Higher Education*, 30(1), pp.67–78. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5367/ihe.2016.0292>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Kim, C. & Prasad, V. (2016) Strength of Validation for Surrogate End Points Used in the US Food and Drug Administration's Approval of Oncology Drugs. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. [Online] 91 (6), 713–725. [online]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocp.2016.02.012>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Kimber, E. (2023). FDA proposes improvements for oncology clinical trials supporting accelerated approval. *PMLive*. [online] Available from: https://www.pmlive.com/pharma_news/fda_proposes_improvements_for_oncology_clinical_trials_supporting_accelerated
- Kunnumakkara, A.B., Bordoloi, D., Sailo, B.L., Roy, N.K., Thakur, K.K., Banik, K., Shakibaei, M., Gupta, S.C. and Aggarwal, B.B.(2019). Cancer drug development: The missing links. *Experimental Biology and Medicine* [Online], 244(8), pp.663–689. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1535370219839163>. (Accessed July 2022)
- LaHucik, K. (2022) Roche plans 4-year late-stage trial for Alzheimer's candidate while awaiting crucial H2 readout. *FierceBiotech* [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercebiotech.com/biotech/roche-plans-4-year-study-alzheimers-med-gantenerumab-once-failed-drug-has-key-2022-readout>(Accessed March 2023)
- LaHucik, K. (2023) Breaking: FDA clears second Alzheimer's drug in 'foundational spark' for field. *EndpointsNews* [online] Available from: <https://endpts.com/fda-approves-alzheimers-drug-lecanemab-from-eisai/>(Accessed March 2023)
- LaHucik, K. (2023) FDA squashes accelerated hopes for Eli Lilly's Alzheimer's drug as agency asks for more data. . *EndpointsNews* [online] Available from: <https://endpts.com/fda-rejects-eli-lilly-alzheimers-drug-donanemab-for-accelerated-approval/>(Accessed March 2023)
- Lakdawalla, D. N., Shafrin, J., Hou, N., Peneva, D., Vine, S., Park, J., Zhang, J., Brookmeyer, R. and Figlin, R. A. (2017) Predicting Real-World Effectiveness of Cancer Therapies Using Overall Survival and Progression-Free Survival from Clinical Trials: Empirical Evidence for the ASCO Value Framework, *Value in Health, Elsevier BV*, 20(7), pp. 866–875, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2017.04.003>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Lazonick, W., (2013), *The Theory of Innovative Enterprise*, University of Massachusetts
- Lenzer, J. & Brownlee, S. (2021) Should regulatory authorities approve drugs based on surrogate endpoints? *BMJ*. [Online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2059>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Lenzer, J. and Brownlee, S. (2021) Should regulatory authorities approve drugs based on surrogate endpoints?, *BMJ*, *BMJ*, p. n2059, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2059>. (Accessed December 2022)
- Lilly (2021) Lilly Announces Leadership Changes and Formation of Neuroscience and Immunology Business Units - Aug 17, 2021. *Lilly Mediaroom* [online] Available from: <http://lilly.mediaroom.com/2021-08-17-Lilly-Announces-Leadership-Changes-and-Formation-of-Neuroscience-and-Immunology-Business-Units> (Accessed March 2023)
- Lilly (2021) Lilly releases donanemab data that demonstrated relationship between reduction of amyloid plaque and slowing of cognitive decline - Jul 29, 2021. *Lilly MediaRoom* [online] Available from: <http://lilly.mediaroom.com/2021-07-29-Lilly-releases-donanemab-data-that-demonstrated-relationship-between-reduction-of-amyloid-plaque-and-slowing-of-cognitive-decline>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Lilly (2021) Lilly's Donanemab Slows Clinical Decline of Alzheimer's Disease in Positive Phase 2 Trial - Jan 11, 2021.*Lilly Mediaroom* [online] Available from: <http://lilly.mediaroom.com/2021-01-11-Lillys-Donanemab-Slows-Clinical-Decline-of-Alzheimers-Disease-in-Positive-Phase-2-Trial> (Accessed March 2023)
- Lilly (2022) Lilly Shares Positive Donanemab Data in First Active Comparator Study in Early Symptomatic Alzheimer's Disease.*Lilly* [online] Available from: <https://investor.lilly.com/news-releases/news-release-details/lilly-shares-positive-donanemab-data-first-active-comparator>
- Lindblom, C.E. (1977). *Politics and markets*. Basic Books.
- Link, A.N. and Link, J.R. (2009). *Government as Entrepreneur*. [Online] Oxford University Press.
- Liu, A. (2022) Biogen compiles buyout target list as Aduhelm woe deepens. *Fierce Pharma*
- Liu, A. (2022) Biogen sends CEO to the exit, abandons Aduhelm sales team in \$1B overhaul. *Fierce Pharma* [online] Available from: <https://www.fiercepharma.com/pharma/biogen-ceo-steps-down-amid-aduhelm-fallout-biotech-trims-commercial-team-1b-cost-cutting>(Accessed March 2023)
- Liu, A. (2022) FDA oncology chief aims to open up accelerated approval for earlier cancer treatment under 'Project FrontRunner'. *Fierce Biotech* [Online] Available from: <https://www.fiercebiotech.com/biotech/fda-oncology-chief-eyes-accelerated-approval-earlier-cancer-treatment-under-planned-project>(Accessed July 2022)
- LoCasale, R.J., Pashos, C.L., Gutierrez, B., Dreyer, N.A., Collins, T., Calleja, A., Seewald, M.J., Plumb, J.M., Liwing, J., Tepie, M.F. and Khosla, S. (2020). Bridging the Gap Between RCTs and RWE Through Endpoint Selection. *Therapeutic Innovation & Regulatory Science*, 55(1), pp.90–96. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s43441-020-00193-5>. . (Accessed June 2022)
- Lu, Y. F., Goldstein, D. B., Angrist, M., & Cavalleri, G. (2014). Personalized Medicine and Human Genetic Diversity. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 4(9), a008581–a008581. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a008581> (Accessed July 2022)

- MacEwan, J. P., Doctor, J., Mulligan, K., May, S. G., Batt, K., Zacker, C., Lakdawalla, D. and Goldman, D. (2019) The Value of Progression-Free Survival in Metastatic Breast Cancer: Results From a Survey of Patients and Providers, *MDM Policy & Practice*, SAGE Publications, 4(1), p. 238146831985538, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/2381468319855386>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Mahajan, R., & Gupta, K. (2010). Adaptive design clinical trials: Methodology, challenges and prospect. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 42(4), 201. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.4103/0253-7613.68417>(Accessed July 2022)
- Mahlich, J., Bartol, A. and Dheban, S. (2021) Can adaptive clinical trials help to solve the productivity crisis of the pharmaceutical industry? - a scenario analysis, *Health Economics Review*, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 11(1), [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13561-021-00302-6>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Mailankody, S. and Prasad, V. (2015) Five Years of Cancer Drug Approvals, *JAMA Oncology*, American Medical Association (AMA), 1(4), p. 539, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamaoncol.2015.0373>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Manne, U., Srivastava, R.-G. and Srivastava, S. (2005). Keynote review: Recent advances in biomarkers for cancer diagnosis and treatment. *Drug Discovery Today*, 10(14), pp.965–976. Available from:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s1359-6446\(05\)03487-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1359-6446(05)03487-2) (Accessed July 2022)
- Mannix, D. G. (2000) Irinotecan—A Case Study for the Transition from Accelerated Approval to Traditional Approval. *Drug Information Journal*. [Online] 34 (3), 737–740. [online]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/009286150003400309>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Masson, G. (2022) A winner is crowned in head-to-head Alzheimer's battle between Biogen's Aduhelm and Lilly Maximizing Value for All Stakeholders While Giving Back Value To Society. EISAI [online] Available from: <https://www.eisai.com/news/2023/pdf/enews202302pdf.pdf>(Accessed March 2023)
- MCCARRON, D. (2020) Alderley Park launches breakthrough Oncology Development Programme in collaboration with Cancer Research UK, Innovate UK, Medicines Discovery Catapult and global pharma and healthcare companies - Alderley Park.
- Meckler, M., & Boal, K. (2020). Decision Errors, Organizational Inogenesis, and Errors of the Seventh Kind. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 34(2), 266–284. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2017.0144> (Accessed June 2022)
- Medicines Discovery Catapult. (n.d.). Innovate UK funding for new precision cancer treatment technology. [online] Available from: <https://md.catapult.org.uk/news/innovate-uk-funding-for-new-precision-cancer-treatment-technology/>. (Accessed October 2022)
- Morant, A.V., Jagalski, V. and Vestergaard, H.T. (2019). Labeling of Disease-Modifying Therapies for Neurodegenerative Disorders. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2019.00223> (Accessed December 2022)
- Moreno, S. G. and Epstein, D. (2019) The price of innovation - the role of drug pricing in financing pharmaceutical innovation. A conceptual framework, *Journal of Market Access & Health Policy*, Informa UK Limited, 7(1), p. 1583536, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/20016689.2019.1583536>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Moreno, S. G. and Epstein, D. (2019) The price of innovation - the role of drug pricing in financing pharmaceutical innovation. A conceptual framework, *Journal of Market Access & Health Policy*, Informa UK Limited, 7(1), p. 1583536, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/20016689.2019.1583536>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Mueller-Langer, F. (2013) Ngelted infectious diseases: Are push and pull incentive mechanisms suitable for promoting drug development research? *Health Economics Policy and Law*.
- Mulberg, A.E., Bucci-Rechtweg, C., Giuliano, J., Jacoby, D., Johnson, F.K., Liu, Q., Marsden, D., McGoohan, S., Nelson, R., Patel, N., Romero, K., Sinha, V., Sitaraman, S., Spaltro, J. and Kessler, V. (2019). Regulatory strategies for rare diseases under current global regulatory statutes: a discussion with stakeholders. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases*, [online] 14(1). Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-019-1017-5>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Mulcahy, A.W., Whaley, C.M., Tebeka, M.G., Schwam, D., Edenfield, N. and Becerra-Ornelas, A.U. (2021). International Prescription Drug Price Comparisons: Current Empirical Estimates and Comparisons with Previous Studies. RAND Corporation. [online] Available from: https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RR2956. (Accessed July 2022)
- Mullins, L., Greene, D. and Mitchell, J. (2021). Biogen grapples with 'reckoning' over controversial Alzheimer's drug, reporters find. *Wburg News*[online] Available from: <https://www.wbur.org/news/2021/12/10/biogen-aduhelm-reckoning-alzheimers-drug>(Accessed March 2023)
- Naci, H., Smalley, K. R. and Kesselheim, A. S. (2017) Characteristics of Preapproval and Postapproval Studies for Drugs Granted Accelerated Approval by the US Food and Drug Administration, *JAMA*, American Medical Association (AMA), 318(7), p. 626, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.9415>. (Accessed December 2022)
- Nakata, B., Wang, Y.Q., Yashiro, M., Nishioka, N., Tanaka, H., Ohira, M., Ishikawa, T., Nishino, H. and Hirakawa, K. (2002). Prognostic value of microsatellite instability in resectable pancreatic cancer. *Clinical Cancer Research: An Official Journal of the American Association for Cancer Research*, [online] 8(8), pp.2536–2540. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12171881/> (Accessed July 2022)
- Narayan, V.A., Mohwinkel, M., Pisano, G., Yang, M. and Manji, H.K. (2013). Beyond magic bullets: true innovation in health care. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 12(2), pp.85–86. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd3944> (Accessed September 2022)
- National Cancer Institute (2020). Cancer Statistics. [online] National Cancer Institute. Available from: <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/understanding/statistics>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Nawrat, A. (2019). Industry review on UK drug discovery emphasises future of AI and CCMs. [online] *Pharmaceutical Technology*. Available from: <https://www.pharmaceutical-technology.com/news/industry-review-on-uk-drug-discovery-emphasises-future-of-ai-and-ccms/> (Accessed June 2022)
- NIH US National Library of Medicine (2022) A Study to Verify the Clinical Benefit of Aducanumab in Participants With Early Alzheimer's Disease (ENVISION) NIH US National Library of Medicine [online] Available from: <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT05310071>(Accessed March 2023)

- Orloff, J., Douglas, F., Pinheiro, J., Levinson, S., Branson, M., Chaturvedi, P., Ette, E., Gallo, P., Hirsch, G., Mehta, C., Patel, N., Sabir, S., Springs, S., Stanski, D., Evers, M.R., Fleming, E., Singh, N., Tramontin, T. and Golub, H. (2009). The future of drug development: advancing clinical trial design. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 8(12), pp.949–957. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd3025>. (Accessed October 2022)
- Paemel, R.V. (2019). Kaplan Meier curves. [online] Medium. Available from: <https://towardsdatascience.com/kaplan-meier-curves-c5768e349479?gi=1c36a2e9b83c> (Accessed July 2022)
- Park, J.J.H., Siden, E., Zoratti, M.J. et al. Systematic review of basket trials, umbrella trials, and platform trials: a landscape analysis of master protocols. *Trials* 20, 572 (2019). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-019-3664-1> (Accessed July 2022)
- Pazdur, R. (2022). FDA's OCE makes the case for accelerated approval rider in user fee reauthorization. *EndptsNews* [online] Available from: <https://endpts.com/fdas-oce-makes-the-case-for-accelerated-approval-rider-in-user-fee-reauthorization/> (Accessed March 2023)
- Petsko, G. A. (2012). The Coming Epidemic of Neurologic Disorders: What Science Is — and Should Be — Doing About It. *Daedalus*, 141(3), 98–107. Available from: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23240270> (Accessed July 2022)
- Pierson, J., Mante-Meijer, E., & Loos, E. (Eds.). (2011). *New Media Technologies and User Empowerment*. [Online] Peter Lang. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3726/978-3-653-00937-8>(Accessed June 2022)
- Planche, V. and Villain, N. (2021) US Food and Drug Administration Approval of Aducanumab—Is Amyloid Load a Valid Surrogate End Point for Alzheimer Disease Clinical Trials?. *JAMA Neurology*, American Medical Association (AMA), 78(11), p. 1307, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamaneurol.2021.3126>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Pollack, A. (2007). Pricing Pills by the Results. *The New York Times*. [online] 14 Jul. Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2007/07/14/business/14drugprice.html> (Accessed July 2022)
- Powaleny, A. (2022, March 17). The accelerated approval pathway: Helping patients with serious or life-threatening diseases.. [online] catalyst.phrma.org Available from: <https://catalyst.phrma.org/the-accelerated-approval-pathway-helping-patients-with-serious-or-life-threatening-diseases> (Accessed August 2022)
- Prasad, V., Kaestner, V. and Mailankody, S. (2018) Cancer Drugs Approved Based on Biomarkers and Not Tumor Type—FDA Approval of Pembrolizumab for Mismatch Repair-Deficient Solid Cancers, *JAMA Oncology*, American Medical Association (AMA), 4(2), p. 157, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamaoncol.2017.4182> (Accessed July 2022)
- Prince, M., Wimo, A., Ali, G.-C., Wu, Y.-T., Prina, M., Kit, Y., Chan and Xia, Z. (2015). World Alzheimer Report 2015 The Global Impact of Dementia An Analysis of prevalence, Incidence, cost AND Trends Dr Maëlienn Guerchet Alzheimer's Disease International. [online] Available from: <https://www.alzint.org/u/WorldAlzheimerReport2015.pdf>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Przedborski, S., Vila, M. and Jackson-Lewis, V. (2003). Series Introduction: Neurodegeneration: What is it and where are we? *Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 111(1), pp.3–10. doi:10.1172/jci200317522.
- Qiu, C., Kivipelto, M. and Von Strauss, E. (2009). Epidemiology of Alzheimer's disease: occurrence, determinants, and strategies toward intervention. *Alzheimer's Disease and Mild Cognitive Impairment*, 11(2), pp.111–128. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.31887/dcns.2009.11.2/cqiu>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Ramzi Dagher, John Johnson, Grant Williams, Patricia Keegan, Richard Pazdur, Accelerated Approval of Oncology Products: A Decade of Experience, *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, Volume 96, Issue 20, 20 October 2004, Pages 1500–1509, Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djh279> (Accessed July 2022)
- Ranga, M. (n.d.). Ranga, M. and H. Etzkowitz (2013), "Triple Helix Systems: An Analytical Framework for Innovation Policy and Practice in the Knowledge Society", *Industry and Higher Education* 27 (4): 237-262. www.academia.edu. [online] Available from: https://www.academia.edu/4807351/Ranga_M_and_H_Etzkowitz_2013_Triple_Helix_Systems_An_Analytical_Frame (Accessed June 2022)
- Reid, B. (2023) The press release from Eisai on how they priced their new Alzheimer's drug is absolutely incredible, and it sets a best practice for how companies *must* think about launch pricing LinkedIn [online] Available from: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/brianbreid_the-press-release-from-eisai-on-how-their-activity-7017260234607890432-8_Qr/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop(Accessed March 2023)
- Rennane, S., Baker, L. and Mulcahy, A. (2021). Estimating the Cost of Industry Investment in Drug Research and Development: A Review of Methods and Results. *INQUIRY: The Journal of Health Care Organization, Provision, and Financing*, 58, p.004695802110597. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00469580211059731>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Ribeiro, S. (2018) Data exclusivity, market protection, orphan and paediatric rewards. [online] Available from: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/presentation/presentation-data-exclusivity-market-protection-orphan-paediatric-rewards-s-ribeiro_en.pdf (Accessed June 2022)
- Richey, E. A. et al. (2009) Accelerated Approval of Cancer Drugs: Improved Access to Therapeutic Breakthroughs or Early Release of Unsafe and Ineffective Drugs? *Journal of Clinical Oncology*. [Online] 27 (26), 4398–4405. [online]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1200/jco.2008.21.1961>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Richey, E.A., et al (2009). Accelerated Approval of Cancer Drugs: Improved Access to Therapeutic Breakthroughs or Early Release of Unsafe and Ineffective Drugs? *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, [online] 27(26), pp.4398–4405. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2008.21.1961>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Richey, E.A., Lyons, E.A., Nebeker, J.R., Shankaran, V., McKoy, J.M., Luu, T.H., Nonzee, N., Trifilio, S., Sartor, O., Benson, A.B., Carson, K.R., Edwards, B.J., Gilchrist-Scott, D., Kuzel, T.M., Raisch, D.W., Tallman, M.S., West, D.P., Hirschfeld, S., Grillo-Lopez, A.J. and Bennett, C.L. (2009). Accelerated Approval of Cancer Drugs: Improved Access to Therapeutic Breakthroughs or Early Release of Unsafe and Ineffective Drugs? *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, [online] 27(26), pp.4398–4405. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2008.21.1961>. (Accessed June 2022)

- Roche (2022) Roche - Doing now what patients need next. Roche [online] Available from: <https://www.roche.com/media/releases/med-cor-2022-11-14>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Roche [2023]. A future in mind – rising to the challenge of Alzheimer's. Roche [online] Available from: <https://www.roche.com/stories/a-future-in-mind-rising-to-the-challenge-of-alzheimers/>
- Roser, M. and Ritchie, H. (2019). Cancer. [online] Our World in Data. Available from: <https://ourworldindata.org/cancer>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Rothenstein, J. M., Tomlinson, G., Tannock, I. F. and Detsky, A. S. (2011) Company Stock Prices Before and After Public Announcements Related to Oncology Drugs. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, Oxford University Press (OUP), 103(20), pp. 1507–1512, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djr338>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Rupp, T. and Zuckerman, D. (2017) Quality of Life, Overall Survival, and Costs of Cancer Drugs Approved Based on Surrogate Endpoints, *JAMA Internal Medicine*, American Medical Association (AMA), 177(2), p. 276, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2016.7761>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Sabbagh, M. N., & Cummings, J. (2020, November). Open Peer Commentary to "Failure to demonstrate efficacy of aducanumab: An analysis of the EMERGE and ENGAGE Trials as reported by Biogen December 2019." *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 17(4), 702–703. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.12235> (Accessed August 2022)
- Sabbagh, M.N. and Cummings, J. (2020). Open Peer Commentary to 'Failure to demonstrate efficacy of aducanumab: An analysis of the EMERGE and ENGAGE Trials as reported by Biogen December 2019'. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.12235>(Accessed December 2022)
- Salcher-Konrad, M., Naci, H. And Davis, C. (2020) Approval of Cancer Drugs With Uncertain Therapeutic Value: A Comparison of Regulatory Decisions in Europe and the United States, *The Milbank Quarterly*, Wiley, 98(4), pp. 1219–1256, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1468-0009.12476>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Samantha McGrail, S. (2021) Breaking Down the Approval of Biogen's Aducanuma. *TechTarget Pharmanews Intelligence* [online] Available from: <https://pharmanewsintel.com/news/breaking-down-the-approval-of-biogens-aducanumab>(Accessed December 2022)
- Scher, H. I., Solo, K., Valant, J., Todd, M. B., & Mehra, M. (2015). Prevalence of Prostate Cancer Clinical States and Mortality in the United States: Estimates Using a Dynamic Progression Model. *PLOS ONE*, 10(10), e0139440. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139440> (Accessed July 2022)
- Scher, J.U. and Schett, G. (2020). Key opinion leaders — a critical perspective. *Nature Reviews Rheumatology*. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41584-020-00539-1>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Schloesser, P. (2022) Ahead of lecanemab decision, Alzheimer's groups petition CMS to reverse coverage policy. *EndpointsNews* [online] Available from: <https://endpts.com/ahead-of-lecanemab-decision-alzheimers-groups-petition-cms-to-reverse-coverage-policy/>(Accessed March 2023)
- Schrijver, J. (2013) Analysis of stock market reactions to FDA and EMEA announcements. Ghent University [online] Available from: https://libstore.ugent.be/fulltxt/RUG01/002/062/116/RUG01-002062116_2013_0001_AC.pdf(Accessed July 2022)
- Schwaedlerle, M., Zhao, M., Lee, J.J., Eggermont, A.M., Schilsky, R.L., Mendelsohn, J., Lazar, V. and Kurzrock, R. (2015). Impact of Precision Medicine in Diverse Cancers: A Meta-Analysis of Phase II Clinical Trials. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 33(32), pp.3817–3825. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2015.61.5997>(Accessed July 2022)
- Scott, L. (2020). *100-YEAR LIFE : living and working in an age of longevity*. S.L.: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Scott, T.J., O'Connor, A.C., Link, A.N. and Beaulieu, T.J. (2014). Economic analysis of opportunities to accelerate Alzheimer's disease research and development. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1313(1), pp.17–34. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.12417>. (Accessed May 2022)
- Scott, T.J., O'Connor, A.C., Link, A.N. and Beaulieu, T.J. (2014). Economic analysis of opportunities to accelerate Alzheimer's disease research and development. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1313(1), pp.17–34. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.1241> (Accessed July 2022)
- Selkoe, D. (2016) The amyloid hypothesis of Alzheimer's disease at 25 years. *EMBO Molecular Medicine*. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27025652/> (Accessed June 2022)
- Sertkaya, A., Wong, H.-H., Jessup, A. and Beleche, T. (2016) Key cost drivers of pharmaceutical clinical trials in the United States, *Clinical Trials*, SAGE Publications, 13(2), pp. 117–126, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1740774515625964>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Seyhan, A. (2019). Lost in translation: the valley of death across preclinical and clinical divide – identification of problems and overcoming obstacles. *Translational Medicine Communications*, 4(1). Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s41231-019-0050-7>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Sharma, P., Jhawar, V., Mathur, P. and Dutt, R. (2022) Innovation in cancer therapeutics and regulatory perspectives, *Medical Oncology*, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 39(5), [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12032-022-01677-0>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Sharma, P., Jhawar, V., Mathur, P. et al. Innovation in cancer therapeutics and regulatory perspectives. *Med Oncol* **39**, 76 (2022). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12032-022-01677-0> (Accessed July 2022)
- Simon, F. (2014), *Managing Biotechnology: From Science to Market in the Digital Age*, Wiley
- Smith, D., Villiers, T. And Freeman, G. (2021) Taskforce on Innovation, Growth and regulatory Reform. UK Government. Available from: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/994125/FINAL_TIGRR_REPORT__1_.pdf (Accessed June 2022)
- Sosa-Ortiz, A.L., Acosta-Castillo, I. and Prince, M.J. (2012). Epidemiology of dementias and Alzheimer's disease. *Archives of Medical Research*, [online] 43(8), pp.600–608. Available from :<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arcmed.2012.11.003>. (Accessed May 2022)

- Spies, S., Shui D. & Corridon C. (2022). The evolution of accelerated approvals in oncology drugs. [online] ZS Available from: <https://www.zs.com/insights/the-evolution-of-accelerated-approvals-in-oncology> (Accessed July 2022)
- Steenhuysen, J. and Beasley, D. (2021). U.S. approval of Biogen Alzheimer's drug sends shares soaring, hailed as "big day" for patients. Reuters. [online] 8 Jun. Available from: <https://www.reuters.com/business/healthcare-pharmaceuticals/us-fda-set-rule-controversial-biogen-alzheimers-drug-2021-06-07/>(Accessed December 2022)
- Strimbu, K. and Tavel, J.A. (2011). What are biomarkers? Current Opinion in HIV and AIDS, [online] 5(6), pp.463–466. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/coh.0b013e32833ed177>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Subbiah, V., Wirth, L. J., Kurzrock, R., Pazdur, R., Beaver, J. A., Singh, H. and Mehta, G. U. (2022) Accelerated approvals hit the target in precision oncology, Nature Medicine, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 28(10), pp. 1976–1979, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01984-z>. (Accessed June 2022)
- Tafari, G., Stolk, P., Trotta, F., Putzeist, M., Leufkens, H.G., Laing, R.O. and De Allegri, M. (2014). How do the EMA and FDA decide which anticancer drugs make it to the market? A comparative qualitative study on decision makers' views. Annals of Oncology, 25(1), pp.265–269. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdt512>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Takahashi, R. H., Nagao, T., & Gouras, G. K. (2017). Plaque formation and the intraneuronal accumulation of β -amyloid in Alzheimer's disease. Pathology International, 67(4), 185–193. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/pin.12520> (Accessed July 2022)
- Taylor, P. N. (2021) UPDATE: Roche dismisses early filing chatter for its Alzheimer's drug as speculation, remains focused on phase 3 trial FierceBiotech
- Tenni, B., Moir, H.V.J., Townsend, B., Kilic, B., Farrell, A.-M., Keegel, T. and Gleeson, D. (2022). What is the impact of intellectual property rules on access to medicines? A systematic review. Globalization and Health, 18(1). Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-022-00826-4>. (Accessed June 2022)
- The Daily Upside (2022). Biogen's Alzheimer's Drug Success Pops Stocks Across the Industry. The Motley Fool [online]. Available from: <https://www.fool.com/investing/2022/09/28/biogens-alzheimers-drug-success-pops-stocks-across/> (Accessed March 2023)
- Theoret, M. R., Pai-Scherf, L. H., Chuk, M. K., Prowell, T. M., Balasubramaniam, S., Kim, T., Kim, G., Kluetz, P. G., Keegan, P., & Pazdur, R. (2015). Expansion Cohorts in First-in-Human Solid Tumor Oncology Trials. Clinical Cancer Research, 21(20), 4545–4551. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.ccr-14-3244> (Accessed July 2022)
- Thomas, D. & Wessel Chad (2019) Volume IV: Alzheimer's Disease Therapeutics. Biotechnology Innovation Organization (BIO) Available from: http://go.bio.org/rs/490-EHZ-999/images/BIO_HPCD4_ALZHEIMERS.pdf?_ga=2.68943441.1759484495.1627399346-1071669468.1611082403&mkt_tok=NDkwLUVlVi05OTkAAAF-I--ERMy1PPCo3gl68G2ZYCv_vTs04WQGoZxS5r7Vt6P9Uk
- Thomas, K. and Ornstein, C. (2017). Considering the Side Effects of Drugmakers' Money-Back Guarantees. The New York Times. [online] 10 Jul. Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/07/10/health/prescription-drugs-cost.html> (Accessed July 2022)
- Thomson, L. & Hughes, P. (2021) Alzheimer's Breakthrough Could Drive a New Wave of Biotech Innovation and Investment | AXA [online] Available from: <https://www.axa.com/en/insights/alzheimers-breakthrough-could-drive-a-new-wave-of-biotech-innovation-and-investment>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Thomson, L.; & Hughes, P (2021) Alzheimer's Breakthrough Could Drive a New Wave of Biotech Innovation and Investment AXA [online] Available from: <https://www.axa.com/en/insights/alzheimers-breakthrough-could-drive-a-new-wave-of-biotech-innovation-and-investment>(Accessed December 2022)
- Thorpe, K., Woodruff, R., Policy, C., Levey, A. and Thomas, J. (2021). Neurodegenerative Disease Burden on US. [online] Available from: <https://www.fightchronicdisease.org/sites/default/files/May%202021%20Neurodegenerative%20Disease%20Burden%20>
- Timmerman, L. (2012). The New Power Players in Drug R&D Are Wearing Bright T-Shirts. [online] Available from: https://www.nationalmssociety.org/NationalMSSociety/media/MSNationalFiles/Brochures/xconomy_power_players.pdf (Accessed June 2022)
- Toumi, M. and Jarosławski, S. (2018) Introduction to the Market Access, Pharmaceutical Market Access in Developed Markets2018, SEEd, pp. 3–19, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7175/747.ch1>.
- Truebel, H. and Seidler, M. (2022). Mitigating bias in pharmaceutical R&D decision-making. Nature Reviews Drug Discovery. Available from:<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41573-022-00157-4> (Accessed June 2022)
- Tulum, Ö. and Lazonick, W. (2019) Financialized Corporations in a National Innovation System: The U.S. Pharmaceutical Industry, International Journal of Political Economy, Informa UK Limited, 47(3–4), pp. 281–316, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/08911916.2018.1549842>. (Accessed July 2022)
- Tyndall, A., Du, W. and Breder, C.D. (2017). The target product profile as a tool for regulatory communication: advantageous but underused. Nature Reviews Drug Discovery, 16(3), pp.156–156. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd.2016.264>. (Accessed March 2022)
- United States Government Accountability Office (2009). FDA needs to enhance its oversight of drugs approved on the basis of surrogate endpoints. [Online] Available from: <https://www.gao.gov/assets/gao-09-866.pdf> (Accessed March 2023)
- US Food & Drug (2022). Table of Surrogate Endpoints That Were the Basis of Drug Approval or Licensure. FDA. [online] Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/development-resources/table-surrogate-endpoints-were-basis-drug-approval-or-licensure>. (Accessed December 2022)
- Vokinger, K. N., Hwang, T. J., Daniore, P., Lee, C. C., Tibau, A., Grischott, T., Rosemann, T. J. and Kesselheim, A. S. (2021) Analysis of Launch and Postapproval Cancer Drug Pricing, Clinical Benefit, and Policy Implications in the US and Europe, JAMA Oncology, American Medical Association (AMA), 7(9), p. e212026, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamaoncol.2021.2026>. (Accessed March 2023)
- Waldrop, T. (2021). Value-Based Pricing of Prescription Drugs Benefits Patients and Promotes Innovation. [online] Center for American Progress. Available from: <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/value-based-pricing-prescription-drugs-benefits-patients-promotes-innovation/>. (Accessed July 2022)

Wallmine (2023) Haruo Naito Net Worth. Wallmine. [online] Available from: <https://wallmine.com/otc/esaly/officer/2068052/haruo-naito> (Accessed March 2023)

Whittington, M. D., Campbell, J. D., Rind, D., Fluetsch, N., Lin, G. A. and Pearson, S. D. (2022) Cost-Effectiveness and Value-Based Pricing of Aducanumab for Patients With Early Alzheimer Disease, *Neurology, Ovid Technologies (Wolters Kluwer Health)*, 98(9), pp. e968–e977, [online] Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1212/wnl.0000000000013314>. (Accessed March 2023)

WHO report on Cancer (2020), Setting priorities, investing wisely and providing care for all (Accessed June 2022)

Woodcock, J. and LaVange, L.M. (2017). Master Protocols to Study Multiple Therapies, Multiple Diseases, or Both. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 377(1), pp.62–70. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmra1510062> (Accessed October 2022)

Wynn, A. (2018), *Transforming Technology into Profit: A guide to leading new ideas through the complexities of the corporate world and transforming them into successful new products.*

Wynn, A. (2020) *Cracking the Innovation Code: How To Unlock The True Potential of Your Business To Grow Through New Products.* Routledge & CRC Press. Available from: <https://www.routledge.com/Cracking-the-Innovation-Code-How-To-Unlock-The-True-Potential-of-Your-Business/Wynn/p/book/9780367567118>(Accessed October 2022)

Wynn, A. (2022), *Building an Innovation Powerhouse: Maximising People Potential to Grow Your Business.*
Yachu, S., (2021), Deal Trends in Alzheimer's Disease, IQVIA. Available from: <https://www.iqvia.com/-/media/iqvia/pdfs/library/publications/iqvia-deal-making-alzheimers-article.pdf> (Accessed June 2022)

Appendices

Appendix 1 - Outline data collected from Qualitative interviews clustered in respective dimensions

Area/Theory/ Hypothesis to contrast	Participant	Comments/ Clustering	Answers /comments
<p>Participants Category Expertise</p> <p>S - Scientific & Clinical / E - Executive & Investor / C - Commercial / I - Innovation Strategist / P - Payor & Market Access / R - Regulatory</p> <p><i>Some Participants can cumulate more than 1 category</i></p>			
DIMENSION 1 [Value Perception in Oncology vs Neurodegeneration: Policies & Regulations]			
<p>Moreno,S. (2019)</p> <p>To ensure that the industry develops valuable innovations, it is fundamental to remove any ambiguity around the 'value framework' used by stakeholders to appraise the value of pharmaceutical products. Clarification is important because value frameworks signal the type of innovation preferred and so it encourages the generation of socially valuable innovations.</p>	SEI	Hurdles in defining "value" in NG	"In Oncology to convey to payers and healthcare systems, if you can prevent death, if you can prolong life for x months, that's very easy to conceptualize and to quantify, to put a value or price tag on that, but for Neurodegeneration the majority of value is not easy to conceptualize. Healthcare systems essentially prolong time until you lose certain aspects of your autonomy and have to be hospitalized or put in a care home. It becomes a very difficult conversation, right, because people say, well, why is this so beneficial?"
	ICEP	Societal attitude towards unmet need in Onco vs NG	"In oncology (...) hope is provided by the tail end of the distribution, right? So it gives people a lot of hope even if the median survival time is 6 extra months. But one out of 100 has six extra years. So the science started to unlock oncology and it made a shift from it being, yeah, you're you have to have a fatalistic attitude towards that there was hope, right and reason to believe. I think there are the generation is on the same journey. There is an hypothesis that aging is the next crisis, we need to not have a fatalistic attitude towards aging as an inevitable thing, but we should start to unlock it as a disease as we have for oncology."
	ICEP	Societal and ethical aspects of drug affordability	"If you've got an epilepsy treatment that's a bit better than the next best one and in your seizures go down by 10%, you could argue ethically that mean people can disagree, but you could argue that some patients, if they're poor, should only have access to the mainstage therapy and not the latest innovation that was discovered 10 minutes ago. That's 10% better, but costs 100% more, right? Ethically, that's OK. It's not ethically OK to say there's a treatment that's available that will extend your life by six months on average, maybe six years, and you can't have it, right?"
	ICEP	Perfect storm factors in Oncology drug development innovation: - Societal alignment on the need, -sense of hopelessness of its fatality, -salience	"(...) the key to success in oncology drug development innovation: there was a confluence of factors, a perfect storm, if you like, that led to the spurring innovation and impact in both scientific innovation and Business model innovation. And the perfect storm was: The fact that we had a disease where there was no question from society and from patients of the unmet need, right, so you had that clear alignment. Unmet need whether it's at the level of the patient or at the level of governments. Those don't always align right because the governments don't care about ultra rare diseases, but patients do, right. But oncology is unique in its fear factor, right, because cancer has been pretty much the thing that everyone has been the most scared of getting for a long time. And then there is the hopelessness. The consciousness of something that is universally fatal and there's no good treatment. I mean, there's a reason, for example, that people fear Airline crashes more than car crashes even though car crashes are way more common and likely to kill you. It's partly to do with salience. And it's partly to do with the control. So oncology sphere represents an unmet need that society and patients are all fully aligned behind. And it's hard to argue that something that's gonna cure your cancer is not worth a lot of money."
	SEI	Hurdles in defining "value" in NG	"Healthcare systems, the understanding of what these drugs (Alzimeris anti-amiloide) contribute in terms of value is not there and that's something actually we are working on to try and bring more data that can then help inform those types of conversations."
	SEI	Hurdles in defining "value" in NG	"I think value based pricing is certainly one of the probably one of the more sustainable ways to go. The challenge with that is really the demonstration of value is the conceptualization and demonstration of value. It's harder in some areas than others. And the system will still be under a lot of pressure."
<p>TAKEAWAYS: Key problem on defining value in NG and societal perception of need & drug affordability Priorities for Executives: <i>- clear strategy since early development on how to conceptualize the value for the drug in NG wrt to value pricing</i> <i>- Create the environment for perfect storm that brings both scientific and business innovation together - Bring together unmet need/ societal perception of need and tolerance for risk - fully aligned behind like in Oncology. If there is no alignment for a specific indication/drug - careful should be taken</i> <i>- Have more fluid exchanges of data with clinics since early stages - make sure the class and potential value of drug is well understood in the two ways [from clinics to firms and from firms to clinics - Med Affairs / RWE] ?</i></p>			
<p>Beaver, J. et al. (2018) Huber, M., (2019)</p> <p>AA in oncology has been a successful strategy of balancing risk uncertainty while allowing enough regulatory flexibility to make safe & effective drugs available sooner to patients. Huber defends this earlier access to promising new drugs especially relevant and helpful for deadly diseases that progress slow, hence admitting they shift part of the evidence generation and safety risk from the pre-approval to the post approval period.</p> <p>Dhingra,K. (2015)</p> <p>Central philosophy behind this concept is that we need to move drug development from a series of linear, landmark events to a flexible and iterative process. "limited Approval" is proposed based on limited initial clinical investigation on small, targeted population. This approval shall not be the end, and the research work would continue to add the survival data and identify better biomarkers.</p>	SE	Use of AA in Onco	"(...) in my experience in Oncology, I can't think of any development program we did go for an accelerated approval, if it were an option."
	SE	Use of AA in Onco	"With regards to Accelerated approvals in Oncology (...) maybe it would be interesting to see how many conditional approvals have been withdrawn."
	IC	Positive wrt to FDA innovative approach	"I don't think the regulators are the problem here. They are actually slightly more proactive than reactive. Specially in US."
	SEI	Supporting a reagent adaptive pathway approach	"Many of us would love to see more of a gradual process of approval if you want where you get enough data to get on the market as soon as possible and those should be mainly safety data and some hints of efficacy. And then you keep reconfirm your approval by bringing in more data and more data and more data. That would shorten the time to get real world data actually and also then give the regulator much more interesting data because it would actually be data from the real clinical setting and not an artificial clinical trial." "(...) I think that concept of more of a process of approval rather than an event in time, more of a continuous research. (...) Because right now the system is just too inefficient. Frankly, I mean, we also don't have good enough drugs. But regardless of that, even with good enough drugs, the system is very inefficient. It's very slow."
	ICEP	Innovation in limited adaptive regulatory approval pathways	"There's a huge problem with adherence because if we don't experience the benefit, why would you keep taking it? And there's a huge problem for payers. And so this relationship between the problem at the individual patient level is it working and the problem at the level of the regulatory path and the statistics, I think there's room for regulatory innovation in kind of conditional or gated approval, right. Maybe you could start with an approval only for patients with known genetic marker for disease or certain risk factors that put them at the high speed progresses or high propensity to develop symptoms further quickly."
	ICEP	Innovation in limited adaptive regulatory approval pathways	"Maybe you could say instead of doing a big phase three study and having to enroll 3000 patients so that you can see a small effect size changing the slope over one or two year study. Maybe you can do a smaller study in an enriched population with an enriched population or you can do a bigger study and just submit a kind of a prespecified subpopulation analysis and show that for patients with this lock 2 mutation, or risk factors like being a ascensu? few or and having a loss of sense of smell and Constipation in the last year. These things will predict past accelerators and so you can have it approval for them because we're relatively confident there's an effect there, right. But doing it up front and saying this is part of our strategy to get on the market, right. And then and then having a clear expansion plan afterwards I think is important."
	ICEP	Innovation in limited adaptive regulatory approval pathways	"So there is regular room for regulatory innovation, I think there's room for statistical innovation. Intuition tells me we're not thinking creatively enough about signal detection technologies and other areas about whether 2 trajectories are diverging or not."
	SEI	Need to review AA	"(...) it is a complicated process (...) In Oncology with the accelerated approval pathway, a lot of drugs that were given accelerated approval then never came back with additional data. The agency now is coming back and saying, well, actually no, once you get your you have to come back every six months and show us what you're doing like how many clinical trials are running and where is the date and all of that. Otherwise you lose your accelerated approval stuff. I think it's totally fair. So I'd love to see something like that more for neurodegenerative conditions as well where you get on market."
	RE	Evolving scrutiny of FDA AA	"(...) they're actually maybe getting a little stricter (FDA) than what they required for a long time, showing tumor reduction was seen as a surrogate for treating the disease and possibly, extending mortality. But now, there is more scrutiny on the delivery of post-marketing commitments."
	SE	AA process in FDA	"(...) it's a good point because the FDA, it's a political body, it's part of the government's it's and the Pharma industry are actually going to look to influence you know, the best they can. I think it's important to maintain transparency of decision making and transparency of process."
SEI	different reg approaches EU vs US; EU criticised wrt to supporting innovation	"(...) it's still a little bit different in the US and Europe as well regularly in the US at least recently I've seen being more interested in actually having the dialogue with industry to try and find solutions; in Europe is still very much not the case where industry and the regulators are still seen as kind of being on opposite sides."	
<p>TAKEAWAYS: Described positive experience of AA in Oncology fostering continuous innovation in the field. However system, specially in NG is seen as too much inefficient, even when in presence of good enough drugs. Priorities for Executives: <i>- Discuss with Agencies since beginning of the program the options to design an "limited approval philosophy" - seen as a key opportunity for regulatory innovation - get drug asap in the market once cleared safety and hints of efficacy - keep reconfirming your approval with continuous more data - shortening the time to get RWE in real clinical setting</i> <i>- Working collaboratively with Agencies and policy makers to review AA, making sure the initial post-marketing commitments are well strengthened and fulfilled</i> <i>- Define the product global development strategy wrt to innovation limitations in EU - and how to bridge it with US to avoid a product strategy that is developed for one market cannot fit the other</i></p>			
IC	The challenge of the right AD population for prescription/reimbursement in the real world	"I think everyone's focused on Alzheimer's. But then the question is why they focus on Alzheimer's? And I think there's been too many false positive forecasts for revenue, for probably optimistic profiles. I think the payers might not necessarily be a barrier because I don't think they're worried about the cost. I think they worried about the process of getting to a prescription, who's gonna take responsibility and so forth."	
IC	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloide cases: challenging the current strategies wrt to the connections between accelerated approval & pricing	"(...) launch the drug, but don't charge anyone for it, you know, or hold on. Hold on to that money and their escrow or something until the drug passes a final regulatory hurdle to say it's a fully approved drug."	
<p>TAKEAWAYS: Policy makers concerns - in addition to the burden of the cost to the Health system is the process to get to the prescription of broad population ill defined Clear room for opportunity to develop better value-based price strategies that can fit an accelerated approval or even limited approval philosophy</p>			

DIMENSION 2 [Scientific hurdles on clinical development Innovation in Neurodegeneration space]

<p>Schwaederle, M., 2015</p> <p>Use of precision medicines strategy, i.e., clinical trials and regulatory approvals focused on targeted sub-population based on expression of predictive biomarkers, allowed increased success in the field.</p>	SEI	Scientific challenges in Neurodegeneration	"I think the basic problem starts with the understanding of the biology of neurodegeneration.,connection between these biologies and clinical benefit is still somewhat murky or incomplete.."	
	RE	Scientific challenges in Neurodegeneration	"For neurodegeneration, there's still a lot of unknowns.It's not just showing the the decrease in amyloid, it's showing that the way that amyloid decrease."	
	SE	Biomarkers driving progress in Oncology Drug Development	"In Oncology (...) the biggest progress I've observed is that you know no longer are necessarily defining cancers by their anatomical location. It's more about the molecular signature and we're now even starting to see agents that have proved the market on tumor tissue agnostic, only focused on biomarkers. "	
	<p>TAKEAWAYS:</p> <p>Concerns - connection between biology and clinical benefit, lack of use of molecular signature like it is seen in Oncology</p>			
	ICEP	Clinical challenges Onco vs Neurodegeneration	"One of the things I believe that's different between oncology and neurodegeneration is the ability to detect a difference versus competition. What is a clinically relevant difference between two products in terms of symptom reduction or new players, right? If it's less than five points on a Part 2 Part 3 combo, it's not really a meaningful clinical difference and you wouldn't claim that you should choose one product over the other, it's just noise. So we know that, is slowing the disease down by, you know, a couple of points on a scale over two years more than the competitor does a meaningful improvement that would justify a price difference? Or are you beholden to the first move as price? In oncology it is easier for people make their own judgment and they have an intuitive sense of what's worth something and what's not right. Few months may be worth a bit a year worth a lot a couple of days worth nothing, right. But in neurodegeneration, none of that's established."	
	IC	Biomarkers challenge in Neurodegeneration	"Main problems of Alzheimer's is that it's a poorly biomarker disease.It's hard to get good, definitive diagnosis, and not everyone wants good, definitive diagnosis cause actually in this early stage prodromal of the disease"	
	IC	Biomarkers challenge in Neurodegeneration	"I mean, the expensive imaging stuff, which is which you can do in a technical trial which you wouldn't expect people to do in the real world. The challenge is there are a lot of interesting biomarkers for Alzheimer's that are blood based or other things. It's just that they're not validated for use in a late stage clinical study. So I think the thing that could be done differently would be a more exploratory approach to using some of those to see well, less you there might be some other."	
	S	Biomarkers challenge in Neurodegeneration	"[...] More biomarkers to be evaluated and certainly there is going to be required for establishing target engagement and for giving you something to follow, but there's also they're also species of amyloid, like oligomers that can't be seen, can't be detected by either either in blood biomarkers or imaging. So there's still a lot of development just in the amyloid area. Now the the Tau either imaging or or biomarker biofluid biomarker seems to be a you know sort of the next step in the in the progression of the of the disease and another group of biomarkers that are being tested now are aimed at determining whether you could predict how rapidly someone will decline because there's a lot of inter individual variability and how rapidly people decline."	
	IC	Biomarkers challenge in Neurodegeneration & lack of use in real world clinical practise	"[...] I think if you were able to go back 10 years, I think there's more exploratory work that could be have been done. The challenge now is people are looking for biomarkers for just pure disease and they won't be able to stratify the response to the amyloid therapies predictive of onset of disease or predictive of your likelihood of getting it. But it won't have anything to do with an invalid outcome.Or effect size and then the real world use to say that there will be no way of tracking real world use of these drugs because you know the kind of studies that you do to measure the 27% decline, no one does in the real world. I mean there are clinical trial measures, they're not real world measures. No one does. Knowing how someone's doing on drugs, it's gonna be a hard thing to understand in the real world."	
	IC	Biomarkers challenge in Neurodegeneration & not investing early in its exploration by design	"One of the challenges that you see is if the biomarker isn't already in the phase two, it's not validated to go into a phase three. So if you weren't thinking about it at phase one, there's already a kind of time based issue. So although You know the the diversity of biomarkers today and the the digital solutions and other things are remarkable. They are either used to fix a problem, you know we've got a problem and we wish that we could stratify the patient population."	
	IC	Biomarkers challenge in Neurodegeneration & not investing early in its exploration by design	"[...] in psychiatry, where you've got very poor stratification of, you know, even significant diseases like MD doesn't tend to break down into its components very often. And they're all biomarkers, which would could be predictive, could be prognostic, could be, you know, measurement related.I just don't think companies are thinking early enough about integrating them into an exploratory phase instead of a confirmatory phase."	
	ICEP	Biomarkers challenge in Neurodegeneration & old clinical scales	"[...]Main reasons for lack of progress in Neurodegeneration drug development is partly a scientific one, specially due to the lack of biomarkers and other things that you can measure. And we have the same old clinical scales like UPDRS that useful for measuring symptomatic treatment, but using them to try and measure disease progression is just short sighted in my view. Also a statistical issue, You don't know if your treatment has zero effect and you're going down by three points, or if you would have been a person that was going down by 6 points and your treatment is having a big effect. So, so that's where narrowing down the population and having better biomarkers could help, because if they are closer, either genetically or whatever, probably the vibration will be less."	
	SEI	Limitations Clinical dev in Neurodegeneration	"Amyloid reduction usually takes years and their current therapies, if you look at least we can measure it pretty well with amyloid PET imaging. But if you look at clinical symptoms, right, it just takes 2 years to get anything out and it takes a sample size of thousands of patients, not just because of the nature of the disease, but because of the nature of the measurement as well"	
	RE	Clinical challenges Onco vs Neurodegeneration	"In neurodegeneration (...) clinically focused endpoints and actually showing that strong link with biomarkers, I think it's perhaps too early to tell. Maybe in oncology because of the disease it was more straightforward? Or those surrogates were more broadly accepted."	
	SEI	Potential for clinical trial innovation	"The potential to use adaptive and basket trials in Neurodegeneration is dependent on having things that can change relatively quickly and can be very accurately measured, so you can actually adapt the study in an agile way. So it is all dependent on having strong surrogate biomarkers in the field."	
SE	Potential for clinical trial innovation	"Use of umbrellas or platform trials today (...) I'm not saying they're solely in oncology, but again, they've been the big drive, the big driver for innovation in the field."		
<p>TAKEAWAYS:</p> <p>Concerns - no clear acceptability across stakeholders of what is a relevant meaningful change in ND</p> <p>confirming what is described already in literature - early development of biomarkers is the key issue in the field - need more early exploratory approach - if looking back past 10y that was not done on the field, now makes it impossible to stratify population in the real world. Companies haven't been investing early enough to invest exploratory biomarkers early enough.</p> <p>Challenging of current huge trials is not just nature of slow progressing disease, it's because of the nature of the measurements</p> <p>Use of adaptive basket and umbrellas trials drove the innovation in Oncology, but without biomarkers for stratification that can provide accurate measures to actually adapt the trial in Agile way, those cannot be used in ND</p>				

DIMENSION 3 [Pricing & Market Access Models of innovation]

<p>Moreno,S. (2019) Value-based pricing in Oncology</p> <p>Huber,H. (2019) Benefits of Pay for Performance models used in Oncology</p>	IC	Challenge of defining good patient population and payers	" (...) and then you charge a lot of money for people that are put into are Mild Cognitive Impairment patients in early stages. So the challenge is probably what will happen on market is it will go into later stage patients where you won't see a difference but also more risk. There's a big challenge. Who's gonna pay for it? What are they paying for? And so forth."
	IC	US pricing system - missing the quality adjusted life target	"The challenge in the states is that the value proposition was based on avoidance of expensive costs , so you know any model where you are mitigating expense, of course you're ending up in a spiral upwards of cost. the thing that you're comparing yourself to doesn't have to be, you know, nursing home or other? it's almost easier in the UK or somewhere else to say, look, there's a cost per quality that we're gonna stick to, the only question is what quality adjusted life here means on the drug. "
	ICEP	Positive view on Oncology pricing models Innovation	"I love what Pfizer did in a pilot with AIG in Oncology , where I think is not talked about enough where they instead of offering direct patient financial support Like Copay assistance in the US and things like that, and donating to foundations and setting up a patient assistance program for those that don't have insurance instead of the traditional things, they had AIG develop an insurance policy that protected the patient from financial exposure in case of clinical failure or in case of catastrophic cost. And so you just have an insurance that says if you have a catastrophic cost or or you spend a reasonable amount of money and the treatment doesn't work, you you're insured, you'll get a payout to cover some or all of those costs, right? And Pfizer just paid the premium for that policy. I think it's a great innovation and it just choose it as an example, because I think we should do more of things like that. But it's an example of the innovation that spurred by the pressure that oncology creates. "
	ICEP	Ethical aspects and societal role in implementing pricing models that support innovation	"But in the end of society has to choose, right. Do you want the freedom to have the best of the best? In which case free market economy tends to serve well? Or do you want regulation and regimented and formulaic approaches, in which case there's nothing sensitive to innovate. Typically in an area where the science is just hitting its sweet spot, you want to stimulate the crap out of innovation and the best way to do that is with high prices and therefore you've got to find the creative mechanisms to make it affordable for people. "
	ICEP	Drug pricing & Innovation	"Like in cases of antimicrobial resistance drugs , you don't want your rewards to be proportional to your volume sold. Because that's the problem with overuse of antibiotics. So you need to find a scheme in which selling less is in some way profitable , right? And maybe that one example would be a one time upfront innovation payment , right? "
	ICEP	Link between drug willingness to pay and disease seriousness	"Is this fascinating inverted U shape curve that describes the relationship between the degree to which someone wants a treatment or feels they need it versus their willingness to pay; What happens is at low a low demand for a treatment because it's not life saving or they don't think there's a likely chance they're gonna have the disease. They're willingness to pay is low, right. And as they're worry about the disease, their sense of it as a threat. When the seriousness of it goes up, the willingness to pay goes up. But then something very interesting happens when that seriousness is red lined all the way and now it's a life saving treatment and is and it's the only option available. Their willingness to pay goes to 0. Because all of a sudden I'm entitled to it. It's not a payment issue."
	P	Tensions between Regulators and Payers	"You know you're clearly identifying like the friction between regulatory and and access here. Regulators are looking at this more from a kind of safety and scientific perspective. But they don't have any money in the game, you know, whereas what payers are tasked with doing is to manage a finite budget and for them they have lots of different things. They can use that budget on. So for them it becomes they are inherently."
	P	Opportunity for dynamic pricing systems with payers	" (...) So if you're looking at something like Parkinson's or Alzheimer's, which are massive patient populations. Data collection infrastructure and the lack of linkages between the different data sets and the lack of kind of coherence in terms of data governance and all of these things. And then what they will do is that they will do a reassessment after a few years to see, OK, what's now that we have more, uh, more mature evidence. How does that price? We negotiated stack up towards that."
	P	Limitations in current pricing models in EU	" (...) in Europe, invariably the price will be adjusted down. It will not go up. I think in Germany there's a theoretical chance that your price could go up, but in practice it never really does."
	P	Emerging shift in payers models to supponor innovation	" (...) healthcare system budget is no longer kind of exclusively used to fund provision of care for patients, but it's also used as a means to explicitly stimulate scientific innovation. it's it's a massive shift, I think."
	P	Positive effect of companies in having early (and joint) interactions with Regulators and Payers	" (...) early engagement with regulators and importantly also payers and different countries has been like a cornerstone of their kind of access strategy and it's work. They've got very good results with that. I don't know kind of what the commercial bottom line looks like or I don't have a granular view on the uptake and so on. But in terms of. Then getting their products. Reimbursed reasonably quickly. Without incurring. Kind of. Massive restrictions has been has been quite impressive and at, you know, high price points as well or at least sort of price points that at the time were boundary pushing. So there's there's definitely, you know, there there's a needs to do it like that."
	P	Example of European country where joint body for Reg/Payor showing positive innovation practises wrt to reimbursement	" (...) like in Italy, you've got something called: innovation status for reimbursement , they do the assessment of drugs, it's like they will consider whether or not you're given something called innovation status, and that is something that, if you're granted innovation status, it means you're automatically reimbursed across the country, but also that there is allocated funding to actually pay for it. So even in like poorer regions where the organization in Italy is called IFA and that is that entails both regulators like the regulatory body and the HDA and reimbursement body. So in that context, it's actually it's actually together."
	SE	Relation between Oncology endpoints & drug prices	" (...) - Quantitative data actually shows that cancer drugs approved through AA, show response rate had higher prices than overall survival, which is very curious (...) - I suspect there's an element of playing there because those are the highest unmet needs and agencies are willing to accept."
	SE	Example of Chinese positive innovation practises wrt to access & practise*	" (...) again that same oncology drug I've worked and mentioned earlier, we came to this arrangement in China where basically patients of all the state would essentially get the drug for free for the first three months; whatever it I forget what it was, and then after will get paid for all the treatment beyond that point provided good drug real world performance. "
IC	Limitation to current US drug pricing models	" (...) In the US system of where the payers are interested in that anyway, you know, cause a lot of payers are unconcerned about prices because the more the drug cost them more they make. That's the the that's actually quite straightforward. So there's no incentive to to kind of lower that."	
<p>TAKEAWAYS: <i>Concern: difficulty of what we compare the drug cost when no quality adjusted life target defined. Tensions between regulators and payor goals. Limitations data collection infrastructure to provide real world evidence. Limitation in current pricing paradigm in Europe where price is mostly only adjusted down. However in some countries using innovation status for reimbursement.</i> <i>Key learnings to leveraged from Onco - using insurance, example AIG of Pfizer in US; Also used example in Chinese market. Huge benefits of engaging earlier with Payers and having joint triangle interactions with Payers and Regulators.</i> <i>Opposing views wrt to US - one side saying with the high prices it has stimulated the crap out of innovation together with finding the best creative mechanisms to be affordable and making sure the rewards are not proportional to volume.</i> <i>Otherside saying payers are just interested in higher prices, because the more they cost the more they make.</i></p>			

DIMENSION 4 [Cross Helix collaborations & Innovation strategies]			
Ranga and Etkowitz (2013) Innovation Intermediaries Albert N. (2009) "Government as Entrepreneur" Grace, C. (2009) Push & Pull Strategies Haddon (2004) The domestication approach	SEI	Positive relationship Reg & Industry - could be blue	"I do think the field is moving in the right direction. I'm not being excessively negative here. It is challenging on both sides (Industry vs Regulators) and I think we can do better. I think we can definitely accelerate more and do more things, but but we are doing more than we were."
	SEI	Innovation ecosystem in Onco vs Neurodegeneration	"The field in Neurodegeneration is just much further behind than Oncology. It is hopeful thought that we starting to see some changes coming, that could catapult the whole sector into higher levels of efficiency, and investment productivity."
	SEI	Need to have more innovative multiple helix collabs in Neurodegeneration	"We simply have not put in that in that effort into real world evidence of benefit, right. And having good Natural History for the large majority of these conditions. Yeah, these are a very significant investment to do those types of trials. There are some public private consortia who do it. Ads does that in the US, there's bio Finder in Europe. There's the NHS Foundation that has a number of these things, so you know there are a number of efforts if you want, which are ongoing, the scale is still not big enough"
	SEI	Change innovation paradigm focused around development of digital tools for a specific therapeutic area, instead of a drug	"One thing that may help is hopefully in the near future starting to deploy digital tools to measure behavior. Getting better measures that sit closer to the patient's, something you could do at home on a regular basis every day. So instead of in the doctor's hospital or in a doctor's office or in a hospital setting, where usually that's how you measure things, right, you bring people with Alzheimer's, for example, to a consult."
	IC	Criticism of innovation and development models, not doing enough deep exploratory work on Biomarkers - Could be green category	"If you were Google and you thought there was a future in self driving cars, yeah, you wouldn't expect people to buy the car as the first year you put them on sale or for them to work the first year. You're learning as you're going, right, and you're teaching your yourself something. I don't think our industry has done anything like that. I don't think we've done anything like enough exploratory work around biomarkers and predictive value or predictive validity. I think we've just gone with what was the old."
	IC	Criticism of current innovation process in Pharma drug development	"I mean, the good news is this is the this for me is like the the wonderful complexity of innovation. It's not as straightforward as you know, here's a disease with a huge unmet need of here's a drug and suddenly, you know, the equation looks golden. I think that they're in reality a lot of drugs hit market and then stumble across all of these challenges that were predictable, just they were typically ignored on the on the way through."
	ICEP	Describing the Innovation seen in Oncology ecosystem through a "box with four outlet valves" where the Innovation valve was allowed to be released	"[...] but really this pressure that happened in Oncology innovation business model, like creating a box with only one outlet valve: So you've got the aligned unmet need. You've got the ethical issue where it's not OK to deny treatment and you've got the justification of the high price (even if the realization that most people that won't be able to afford that or plans won't be able to afford that). And so you're only release Valve is innovation, right?"
	ICEP	Innovation in pharma coming from pressure and necessity	"Innovation never comes from a Pharma company and a payer sitting down and having academic conversation about whether a pay performance scheme is interesting, innovative, or whether we should pilot it or try it right, even if it's a win win, it comes from necessity. It comes from pressure, it comes from them trying to avoid a lose lose right."
	P	Oncology drivers supporting appetite for investment in Oncology drug development innovation	"(oncology) there's something about that kind of proximity to death which changes the dynamic a little bit. In addition to that, there's also the Council Drug Fund, which is just a massive allotted pot of money to pay for expensive cancer drugs because cancer is important to everyone and it's kind of like, uh, policy health hot potato"
	S	Positive presence of Innovation brokers in Oncology collaboration with all stakeholders in Ecosystem	"There are a lot of public private partnerships in in target discovery for Alzheimer's disease. There is an entity called the National Institute on Aging Accelerating Medicines Partnership amp AD. And this is exactly what they do, there's a an entity called the Foundation for the NIH that really, sort of brokers, this sort of thing"
SE	Lacking more collaboration across different helixes, including competitors, to foster innovation in ND	"[...] of course the whole Pharmaceutical industry is built on competition, you know? So we often compete and don't collaborate with our peers; compete with them and and it's all about proprietary information and it's all about beating them to the market, isn't it? Or that's how the industry is kind of work traditionally. And now we're asking them to come together to collaborate on them. But this could actually make the difference to spark innovation in this field."	
SE	Positive effect of brokering agents and helix collaboration in Oncology	"In Oncology arena there are a lot of non-commercial organizations, such as the UKERTC in Europe and the National Cancer Institute in the US, the NCIC, the Canadian equivalent. These groups you know are there to collaborate with industry, and act like an honest broker and the NCI in the US and you know, they will have platforms that is being run at their kind of sponsoring and then they're brokering with different pharmas to get them to the table alongside [...]"	
<p>TAKEAWAYS: <i>In experience from Oncology innovation comes from necessity, from pressure - Model describing innovation pressure seen in Oncology ecosystem of "box with four outlet valves" where the pressure needs to come out at least from one of them - 1) Unmet need 2) ethical issue 3) justification of high price 4) Innovation - all 3 first valves were assured, so the pressure was directed to innovation</i></p> <p><i>Recent signals seen in AD as a potential for future catapult like seen in Oncology, yet in ND there is need and big opportunity to put more effort in multiple helix collabs, eg with NHS Foundation, National Institute on Aging Accelerated Medicines Partnerships, etc. that are not yet leveraged for sponsoring and generating RWE, explore and develop biomarkers, including digital tools. In oncology a lot of these sponsoring allowed the needed brokering of innovation in the field.</i></p>			

DIMENSION 5 [Strategic learnings from Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloids case studies]			
Case study findings	ICEP	Problem of the public narrative and societal perception around Aduhelm approval	"It's not up to the public opinion of whether treating Alzheimer's disease is valuable, because that's clear it's on the efficacy of the product, right. And when you've got an FDA advisory committee that says that they wouldn't approve it, right? The narrative is that were so desperate for a treatment of Alzheimer's that the FDA may have approved the placebo, and then you're charging 50 grand. That's the problem."
	IC	Major issue in Aduhelm case	"The label was better than the company was asking for and the company asked for them to restrict the label to help their market access. I mean I'm on record of saying that none of the amyloids are gonna do anything commercially because they're actually terrible commercial proposition."
	S	Positive impact catapulting investment to innovate in ND area	"[...] But I think it has reinvigorated the idea of of doing clinical trials and and Alzheimer's disease which you know until now I've been universally negative"
	SEI	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloids cases: Biogen bad strategy in pricing but positive pull effect to further innovative investment in the field	"[...] I think the pricing was perhaps the biggest mistake which was made in the case of Aduhelm. I think the only good thing it did help pushing the door for for accelerated approval for new generation, right. The the concept of accepting amyloid. That is a win for the field generally for everyone, right."
	P	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloids cases: Biogen major error related to pricing strategy	"(Biogen) if they had a less aggressive pricing strategy, it might not have been an issue, and you'd still probably have some clinicians questioning data and how meaningful the results were. But certainly not creating the same very hostile environments for them."
	P	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloids cases: Esai pricing strategy seen as improvement	"(Esai) the approach is completely different and I think they've had to just they're taking there is that they're they're being super transparent upfront in terms of how they arrive at the price point, they do, the price point Pivot in terms of strategy completely after they saw what happened with Aduhelm"
	S	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloids cases: criticism of Aduhelm approach wrt to data workaroud used for AA, and lack of proactive stakeholders management to guide on how to monitor risk of safety issues	"I think that you know the main error that struck me was the different results from the two trials. You know, one trials are very promising and one trial looked futile. Then when the label was published, the indication was for all stages of Alzheimer's disease, which made, you know, absolutely no sense. You know, when the when the trial was focusing on people with only early MCI and early ad and the other, you know, main thing was that there wasn't really a a clear delineation of either guidelines for monitoring or for the risks of ARIA. (...) if if you were doing an experiment in the lab and you got conflicting results, you'd do a third experiment."
	IC	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamiloids cases: criticality of the double standards of public sphere when judging the close collaboration between company & regulators	"[...] the good thing, is that this was a very close relationship, a little bit like what we saw with COVID vaccines. And you know, they're working relationship was strong there. I mean, you know, so the same behavior for COVID vaccine development didn't look so good when it, when it when applied to Aduhelm. You know dialogues better than no dialogue. You don't wanna do all of the work and then find out that you were missing something. So I think you know, typically there is a positive movement there to have earlier, more productive dialogue."
<p>TAKEAWAYS: <i>Concerns of high uncertain efficacy for an very high price. FDA might have felt the pressure for approval can be criticised, yet clearly catapulted the field. Pricing clearly the biggest mistake. Positive that it opened the doors on the concept of accepting surrogate endpoints in the field. Esai strategy is an example of good stratigic decisions. Strong collaboration relationship should be praised.</i></p>			

DIMENSION 6 [Executive Leadership and strategic decision making]			
<p>Loos & Mante-Meijer (2007) and Mante-Meijer & Loos (2008)</p> <p>Decision Making & risk taking</p> <p>Jarzabkowski and Wilson (2006) Strategy formulation</p> <p>Trubel, H. (2022)</p> <p>Case study findings</p>	SEI	Executive Leadership and strategic decision making around Anti-betaamilooids cases : risks and opportunities when deciding for an accelerated versus a traditional approval	<p>"Our decision, which I'm not sure it's the right or wrong, but I'll tell you why we made it. Was made even before all the all the controversies around pricing and CMS reimbursement and everything else was always in this particular situation, like for a disease that affects hundreds of thousands of millions of people not having very clear evidence of clinical benefit we felt was always going to jeopardize the acceptability of the therapy and it's and it's adoption by physicians and access it's not about being first in class, right? It's really about creating the most compelling data package to justify the sustainable access and the sustainable price. This particular situation, it might not be true in other situations, right? There are other situations where actually being first in class becomes critical. Rare diseases quite often work like that. Very differently, we could say, OK, we've gonna gradually generate more data. So essentially our up front investment is also not as high. But that's a very different model of investment as well, right? Because we basically took all the investment upfront at risk. (...) Yeah, we decided not to, but I think it's a very specific decision based on the environmental context. And also about the competitive situation around us, right, because again we already knew we were not gonna be first anyway, Our strategy is going to be to try and get there with the best package."</p>
	SEI	Executive Leadership and strategic decision making around Anti-betaamilooids cases : The disruptor Cavaliers & the conservative collaborators	<p>" (...) I think philosophically there's in my mind, kind of two approaches and of course, lots of shades of Gray in between. But philosophically, I see two different approaches: There are some companies who take kind of a more cavalier attitude and essentially they create the conversation by creating a problem, right? So here's my therapy, I've developed it, it works. You don't like it, but there's a big pressure from the patient groups and so on, so you need to get it approved no matter what. But that's very different, you know, like it changes a lot of things like Japanese companies and Roche which is it's Swiss kind of like that as well. We don't like controversy in the public sphere, right? We are very discreet in that sense and also at the same time by nature, we tend to be very collaborative types of company, so our philosophy as always been, the more you dialogue, the earlier you dialogue the better. (...) Well, you can have to see like you can have many, many conversations and not have a dialog. When I mean dialogue is actually when you sit down and try to understand the other person's concerns and maybe even change your own mind and change what you're doing to accept some of those right, find that good balance.</p> <p>"I'm a big believer in diversity, right. I think we need different types of approaches. I think we need disruptors in the system. I think it's great that we have different companies with different styles and some more conservative. That's all good. The problem is, when disruptors crew create a mess for everybody else. (...) And this example I think is taught us all lesson on that is that you can actually create a lot of damage for the field when you do this cavalier. (...) The appetite for example for CMS to reimburse right will be much lower.</p> <p>" (...) We're jealous, but no kudos to the disruptors. (...) The only thing I worry about is when the disruptors just destroyed the system."</p>
	IC	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamilooids cases: Leaderships tensions within the same company from Regulatory & Commercial departments	<p>" (...) you got the problem of the hierarchy in the company. So does the regulatory veto mean that they don't do the thing that that might be more risky. You know, even though the commercial colleagues might be crying out for it, so that that tension is often seen as well."</p>
	IC	Aduhelm & Anti-betaamilooids cases: Making a point that having physical and cultural presence closer to US could help smooth things for a company. Contradictory to Biogen/Esai case.	<p>"Because the US is such an important market, if you're in the States and you've got Americans talking to the FDA, that's a lot easier than having a kind of, you know, flying in from Tokyo to have the same sort of conversation or even from Paris or whatever."</p>
	ICEP	Executive Leadership and strategic decision making around Portfolio : Treat each asset individually and optimize them VS optimize portfolio as a whole. Strategies dependent on macro and micro pressures & company size.	<p>"The analysis right and get the best expected return through the combination of different bets, right. So you offset them, you don't treat them as three individual assets and optimize them individually. And so you might want to say, OK, we'll take one say that and one risky bit, right and those are the two that will prioritize. You know the portfolio, so if the pressure that company is facing is cash crunch next five years or if the pressure they're facing is that they're running out of innovation. Or if they've kind of super big and just can't find a way to grow fast enough, then the answers are different to each of those situations, right? For samller company its more about modulating risk, right and long term sustainable growth. But for big pharma, if they were in that situation, they would have kind of quarterly earnings growth to go and they've gotta be bolder, right? Otherwise it's just, you know, a ripple in the ocean and they can afford for the entire generation platform to fail because they've got so many others, right. So the context matters a lot."</p>
	ICEP	Executive Leadership and strategic decision making around Portfolio : "A trade-off Art, not a process machine"	<p>"If all we do is wait for these assets to go through some machine, we call development and then stare at the data and see which data is best. Board don't need highly paid executives to do that. Online chat bot could do that. You know for free. The art of it is to use our expertise, experience and intuition. And external consultation and advice to figure out which hypothesis are actually bolder and more robust. Right. How salient scientifically interesting and gonna do something unique. Right. And it's our job to sort through the three and have kind of a prioritization based on that, right. But it's as alluded to, it's not just the prioritization, it's well, we can offset, right? I mean, if you only had one bet and you if you are funding only allowed you to fund one of the three that you have to have prioritize and say what's my preferred trade off?"</p>
	ICEP	Executive Leadership and strategic decision making around Anti-betaamilooids cases : Positive view on Biogen strategic decisions	<p>"(Biogen) I'm not sure they make development mistakes because in the end, right they had an asset they thought it was interesting. They tested it, they got no signal. They looked at a subpopulation. They thought they had a signal. They went back to the FDA. Nothing about that sounds stupid to me, right. I also don't think they're pricing was particularly stupid. I think we saw things that are more expensive than offer less value."</p>
	RE	Executive Leadership and strategic decision: Environmental context matters most than just being first to market	<p>"I think trying to be first to market is always a good strategy, but it's making sure that you know it's also case by case that it's making sure you take the environment in account and the data package that you have."</p>
	SE	Criticism on current strategic criteria wrt prioritize where to invest, where to innovate	<p>"There is an uncertainty about identifying the right patient to treat and yet the proposition from the Pharma it's kind of then, OK well put your money where your mouth is. If you say you can identify the patient's gonna benefit, then you know we'll pay you for those results. So there's a bit of an interplay there where you know we believe and we promote."</p>
<p>TAKEAWAYS:</p> <p>Decisions need to very specifically be adapted to environment and competitive context</p> <p>Innovation ecosystem need a combination of cavalier and conservative leadership styles</p> <p>Leadership added value is on a trade-off art, not on a process machine.</p> <p>Apart from evident mistakes in pricing, Biogen did not necessarily did development mistakes</p>			

DIMENSION 7 [Investment in Neurodegeneration business]			
<p>Tulum, O. et al (2019)</p> <p>Mahlich, J. (2021)</p> <p>Budish, E. et al (2015)</p>	SEI	Investor perspective: still skeptic to invest in ND, specifically antbetaamilooids cases in AD, compared to other TAs	<p>"I still feel regarding Alzheimer's and Neurodegeneration, that there's a lot of hesitancy still. You look around, there's not that many players working in this area, right? I think you know, frankly, it's because the the return on investment is turning out not to be as high as people thought. My former CMO used to say that Alzheimer's is so big that that, you know, anything that that works even if it's milk. You can get approval and not get reimbursed and therefore there's no return. (...) Precisely because it's so big, because perhaps if it was not so big and being given some early, they will not worry. I think that's the paradox. They won't get to blockbuster very fast. It'll take a long time. Not just because of reimbursement and access, but also because diagnosis is not in place, right. So there's no good funnels for diagnosis."</p>
	SEI	Investor perspective: still skeptic to invest in ND, specifically antbetaamilooids cases in AD, compared to other TAs	<p>" (...) it's an IV drug. Every two weeks. I mean, all those things will make these these markets very, very slow to to grow, right. So the idea that you're gonna reach blockbuster in a year, I don't know. I don't think. I don't know if that's true. Actually, I I think a lot of the a lot of us and I think a lot of the investors are going to be looking at the case of locator map and and seeing what happens, I think a lot of people will be kind of spooked. It will be and will say like, OK, maybe, yeah. Maybe investing a billion to get this. I'm not so sure it will be a shame it'll be a real shame because it's one of the huge medical needs in society right now, but again the the market then dynamics have to reward it."</p>
	SEI	Investor perspective: Neurodegeneration still an area for investment more for big pharma, but still big risk for smaller biotechs	<p>"How much do we want to do this? And then what I think will might happen is that, yeah, companies like Roche, etcetera, there has deep pockets and a lot of stability may still do that may still have. OK, fine. I'm still in because I think it's going to be we're going to figure this out. But other smaller companies and biotech made you say well, this is just too much which is cannot afford to do this. Right so you'll drift you'll drift but there are other areas right there are other areas which are nascent."</p>
	IC	Investors in Biopharma in Neurodegeneration: need shareholders that understand the long run in this industry, day trader type of	<p>" (...) the kind of day trader type investor, which is really what you saw with Jen and others, the kind of speculative. I don't think it's a very useful thing for the farmer industry because it tends to meet, you know, management by press, release management by investor relations, everything's polished to sound good instead of deliver actual value. But when you decide you got some people do understand it's at 2030 year horizon. But we don't tend to see much of that. You know the kind of support during long term risk, even internally in companies that are large enough like J&J where you know some of their innovation. But pro programs have been questioned, you know, by investors and by, you know, people internally. Because they might be turned C20 pay offs then you might not know that they're gonna work until then. Yeah. So you see more of the former activity, the kind of still people want to go JP Morgan and get the share price going up to."</p>
	IC	Changes in US Pricing ecosystem as Inflation Reduction Act: can investment strategies in Neurodegeneration	<p>"I think the Inflation Reduction Act is already making people think harder about their portfolios and economic evaluation of their portfolios. So I think the companies that are good at it will be better than the companies that aren't."</p>
	<p>TAKEAWAYS: Rat still and risk level still perceived as less attractive in this field compared to others</p> <p>The paradox of being a big population and slow progressing made the access (reimbursement) more challenging</p> <p>Specially challenging to attract investment on innovation from samller and agile biotech, the ones that had foster innovation in Oncology</p> <p>Without the flexibility and alignment on needs and urgency from stakeholders, only bigger stable companies afford to bet in the area, as it requires real long term investment at high uncertainty of return</p>		

Appendix 2 - Outline FDA table of Surrogate endpoints that were the basis of drug approval

Disease or Use	Patient Population	Surrogate endpoint	Type of approval appropriate for	Drug mechanism of action
Alzheimer's disease	Patients with mild cognitive impairment or mild dementia stage of Alzheimer's disease	Reduction in amyloid beta plaques	Accelerated	Monoclonal antibody
Anticoagulation reversal (needed due to life-threatening or uncontrolled bleeding)	Patients treated with a direct or indirect FXa inhibitor when reversal of anticoagulation is needed	Percent change in anti-FXa activity, from baseline to nadir	Accelerated	Binding and sequestering FXa inhibitors
Cancer: hematological malignancies	Patients with chronic myeloid leukemia	Major hematologic response	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: hematological malignancies	Patients with acute myeloid leukemia and acute lymphoblastic leukemia	Durable complete remission rate	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: hematological malignancies	Patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia; myelodysplastic/myeloproliferative diseases; chronic myeloid leukemia	Major hematologic response and cytogenetic response	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: hematological malignancies	Patients with B-cell precursor acute lymphoblastic leukemia in first or second complete remission	Minimal residual disease response rate	Accelerated	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: hematological malignancies	Diffuse large B-Cell lymphoma; hairy cell leukemia; follicular lymphoma	Durable complete response rate	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: hematological malignancies	Patients with T-cell lymphoma; B-cell lymphoma; mantle cell lymphoma; classical Hodgkin lymphoma; anaplastic large cell lymphoma and mycosis fungoides; non-Hodgkin lymphoma; multiple myeloma; chronic myeloid leukemia; acute lymphoblastic leukemia; chronic lymphocytic leukemia; acute myeloid leukemia; small lymphocytic lymphoma; Waldenström's macroglobulinemia; marginal zone lymphoma; follicular lymphoma; light chain amyloidosis	Durable objective overall response rate (ORR)	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: solid tumors	Patients with breast cancer	Pathological complete response	Accelerated	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: solid tumors	Patients with nonmetastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer	Metastasis-free survival	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: solid tumors	Patients with breast cancer; ovarian cancer; renal cell carcinoma; pancreatic neuroendocrine cancer; colorectal cancer; head and neck cancer; non-small cell lung cancer; melanoma; tuberous sclerosis complex-associated SEGA and renal angiomyolipoma; merkel cell carcinoma; unresectable or metastatic cutaneous basal cell carcinoma; urothelial carcinoma; cervical cancer; endometrial cancer; hepatocellular carcinoma; fallopian tube cancer; microsatellite instability-high cancer; gastric cancer; gastroesophageal junction cancer; thyroid cancer; astrocytoma; Kaposi's sarcoma; unresectable or metastatic squamous cell carcinoma; neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase (NTRK) gene fusion without a known acquired resistance mutation; prostate cancer; esophageal cancer; tumor mutational burden high solid tumors; cholangiocarcinoma; bladder cancer; neuroblastoma; mismatch repair deficient solid tumors	Durable objective overall response rate (ORR)	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: solid tumors	Patients with breast cancer; renal cell carcinoma; pancreatic neuroendocrine tumor; soft tissue sarcoma; ovarian, fallopian tube, or primary peritoneal cancer; prostate cancer; thyroid cancer; colorectal cancer; non-small cell lung cancer; head and neck cancer; tuberous sclerosis complex; merkel cell carcinoma; basal cell carcinoma; urothelial carcinoma; cervical cancer; endometrial cancer; hepatocellular carcinoma; fallopian tube cancer; melanoma; astrocytoma; gastrointestinal stromal tumors	Progression-free survival (PFS)	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: solid tumors	Patients receiving adjuvant therapy following complete surgical resection of colon cancer; colorectal cancer; melanoma; renal cell cancer; gastrointestinal stromal tumor; breast cancer and adjuvant therapy for stage III non-small cell lung cancer	Disease-free survival (DFS)	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Cancer: solid tumors	Patients with breast cancer; neuroblastoma	Event-free survival (EFS)*	Accelerated/Traditional§	Mechanism agnostic*
Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD)	Patients with DMD who have a confirmed mutation of the DMD gene that is amenable to exon skipping	Skeletal muscle dystrophin	Accelerated	Antisense oligonucleotide
Fabry disease	Patients with confirmed Fabry disease and amenable GLA gene variants	Reduction of GL-3 inclusions in biopsied renal peritubular capillaries (using the BLISS methodology)	Accelerated	Pharmacological chaperone
Hepatitis D Virus (HDV)	Patients with HDV infection with or without cirrhosis	≥ 2 log reduction in HDV-RNA plus normalization of ALT or HDV below the LLOQ†	Accelerated	Antiviral
Influenza vaccine	Persons to be immunized against influenza	Hemagglutination inhibition antibody	Accelerated	Induction of immunity
Mycobacterium avium complex (MAC) lung disease	Patients with MAC lung disease	Sputum culture conversion to negative by six months	Accelerated	Antimicrobial
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)	Precirrhotic NASH patients with liver fibrosis	Histopathologic findings of either 1) resolution of steatohepatitis with no worsening of fibrosis OR 2) improvement of fibrosis with no worsening of steatohepatitis OR 3) Both#	Accelerated	Anti-fibrotic; Anti-inflammatory
Nonmalignant hematology	Patients with methemoglobinemia	Serum methemoglobin	Accelerated	Oxidation-reduction agent
Nonmalignant hematology	Patients with sickle cell disease	Hemoglobin response rate	Accelerated	Hemoglobin S polymerization inhibitor
Pneumococcal conjugate vaccine	Persons (≥ 50 years of age) to be immunized against pneumonia and invasive disease	Opsonophagocytic antibody response	Accelerated	Induction of immunity
Polycystic kidney disease	Patients with autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease with or without associated polycystic liver disease	Total kidney volume *	Accelerated	Mechanism agnostic*
Preterm birth	Women with a singleton pregnancy who have a history of singleton spontaneous preterm birth	Delivery prior to 37 weeks gestation	Accelerated	Progesterone analog
Primary biliary cholangitis	Patients with primary biliary cholangitis	Serum alkaline phosphatase and bilirubin#	Accelerated	Farnesoid X receptor (FXR) agonist
Primary glomerular diseases associated with significant proteinuria	Patients with primary glomerular disease associated with significant proteinuria	Proteinuria (urinary protein/creatinine ratio)	Accelerated	Mechanism agnostic*
Pulmonary tuberculosis	Patients with active pulmonary tuberculosis	Sputum culture conversion to negative	Accelerated	Antimicrobial

Note: This is a non-exhaustive proxy representation of the table, that can be consulted fully at <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/development-resources/table-surrogate-endpoints-were-basis-drug-approval-or-licensure>. As of September 2022, 196 surrogate endpoints were listed on this table. Most of them in Oncology and in infectious/metabolic diseases.

Only one surrogate endpoint in this table is on the field of Neurodegeneration: the "Reduction in amyloid beta plaques" to be used in development programs as a surrogate of clinical efficacy in patients with mild cognitive impairment or mild dementia stage of Alzheimer's disease.

Appendix 3 - Design of Aduhelm clinical studies (PRIME, ENGAGE and EMERGE) that were used as the basis of the first FDA accelerated approval in the field of Neurodegeneration

Study ID No. of study centres/ locations Study period	Design Objective Duration	Dose at study initiation*	Subjects by arm (ITT) Subjects in PET-substudy	Male/Female Age (median; range) APOE-ε status Diagnosis (Mild AD/MCI)	Primary and secondary endpoints
221AD103 27 centres: US Oct 2012- Jul 2019 PRIME	Phase 1b RD DB PC MD Safety & tolerability 52 weeks PC + LTE up to 5 years	Fixed: 1, 3, 6, or 10 mg/kg Titration: 1 to 10mg/kg All cohorts were placebo-controlled	196 total: 48 (placebo) 125 (fixed) 23 (titration) 167 total: 42 (placebo) 107 (fixed) 18 (titration)	98/98 73 (51-91) Carrier: 65% Noncarrier: 35% MCI: 43% Mild AD: 57%	Primary: Incidence of (S)AEs e.g. ARIA-E/ARIA-H Secondary: Δ from BL to Week 26 in 18F-florbetapir PET signal
221AD301 169 centres: US/EUR/CAN/AUS/Asia Aug 2015- Aug 2019 ENGAGE	Phase 3 RD DB PC PA Efficacy and safety 8 weeks prior to 1 st dose + 78 weeks PC + 18 weeks safety FU / LTE up to 5 years	Low dose after 8wks titration: 3 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 carriers 6 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 non-carriers High dose after 24wks titration: 6 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 carriers 10 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 non-carriers	1647 total: 545 (placebo) 547 (low dose) 555 (high dose) 585 total: 204 (placebo) 198 (low dose) 183 (high dose)	784/863 71 (50-85) Carrier: 69.5% Noncarrier: 30.3% MCI: 80.4% Mild AD: 19.6%	Primary: Δ from BL in CDR-SB at Week 78 Secondary: Δ from BL in MMSE at Week 78 Δ from BL in ADAS-COG13 at Week 78 Δ from BL in ADCS-ADL-MCI at Week 78
221AD302 181 centres: US/EUR/CAN/Asia Sep 2015- Aug 2019 EMERGE	Phase 3 RD DB PC PA Efficacy and safety 8 weeks prior to 1 st dose + 78 weeks PC + 18 weeks safety FU / LTE up to 5 years	Low dose after 8wks titration: 3 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 carriers 6 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 non-carriers High dose after 24wks titration: 6 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 carriers 10 mg/kg for APOE-ε4 non-carriers	1638 total: 548 (placebo) 543 (low dose) 547 (high dose) 488 total: 159 (placebo) 159 (low dose) 170 (high dose)	795/843 72 (50-85) Carrier: 66.8% Noncarrier: 32.8% MCI: 81.6% Mild AD: 18.4%	Primary: Δ from BL in CDR-SB at Week 78 Secondary: Δ from BL in MMSE at Week 78 Δ from BL in ADAS-COG13 at Week 78 Δ from BL in ADCS-ADL-MCI at Week 78

* During studies 301 and 302, the high dose for APOE-ε4 carriers was increased to 10mg/kg (protocol versions 4-6) based on analyses from cohort 4, study 103.
AD = Alzheimer's Disease, ADAS-Cog13 = Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale - Cognitive 13-Item Scale, ADCS-ADL-MCI = Alzheimer's Disease Cooperative Study - Activities of Daily Living - Mild Cognitive Impairment, ApoE ε4 = apolipoprotein E ε4, ARIA-E = amyloid-related imaging abnormality-vasogenic edema, ARIA-H = amyloid-related imaging abnormality-microhemorrhage, macro-hemorrhage, or superficial siderosis, BL= baseline, CDR-SB = Clinical Dementia Rating-Sum of Boxes, DB = double-blind, FU = follow-up, ITT = intent-to-treat, LTE = long term extension, MCI = Mild Cognitive Impairment, MMSE = Mini-Mental State Examination, OLE = open label extension, PA = parallel group, PC = placebo-controlled, PET = positron emission tomography, PL = placebo, RD = randomised, Δ = change.

Source: adapted from https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/withdrawal-report/withdrawal-assessment-report-aduhelm_en.pdf

Appendix 4 - November 2022, Eisai presentation on Lecanemab clinical study results

Source: slides from Eisai presenting Clarity AD study results at the Clinical Trials on Alzheimer's Disease (CTAD) conference in November 2022. Results also published at <https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2212948>